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FEATURES OF QUANTITATIVE ASSESSMENT OF WAVELET PATTERNS OF VIBRATION SIGNALS DURING THE DEVELOPMENT OF IMBALANCE IN CENTRIFUGAL PUMP UNITS

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Abstract. *The paper considers the features of quantitative assessment of wavelet patterns of vibration signals during the development of one of the most common faults in centrifugal pump units, namely fault type “Imbalance”. The relevance of time-frequency analysis methods is substantiated under the limitations of the traditional spectral approach associated with the ambiguity of diagnostic features. It is shown that an increase in the length of recorded signals from 1024 to 16,384 points, due to the development of hardware and software, leads to significant changes in the visual structure of scalograms, which necessitates the development of new methods for their analysis to assess the technical condition of centrifugal pump units. An approach is proposed to formalize wavelet patterns as two-dimensional images with subsequent application of texture analysis methods, in particular the Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM), to extract quantitative features of fault development. Based on synthesized vibration signals simulating imbalance, dependencies of texture characteristics (contrast, homogeneity, correlation, energy, entropy) on the root mean square (RMS) value of vibration velocity were obtained, demonstrating sensitivity to changes in the technical condition of the equipment. The obtained results indicate the possibility of using the proposed approach in solving problems of automated vibration diagnostics of pump units.*

Keywords: *Vibration Diagnostics, Pump Unit, Vibration Velocity, Intelligent System, Wavelet Analysis, Wavelet transform, Image analysis, Gray Level Co-Occurrence Matrix, Texture Analysis*

Centrifugal pump units are widely used in the oil and gas industry – at production sites, in transportation systems, and at oil and gas processing facilities. Their reliable operation is critically important. However, despite the development of technical diagnostics methods, failures of units still occur.

According to statistics (Table 1), the largest share of failures is associated with bearings and mechanical seals of shafts – those elements whose condition is most accurately diagnosed using vibration diagnostics methods [1], which confirms the relevance of the research topic and the need for its further development.

Table 1 – Average distribution of failure causes of mainline pump units

Cause of failure	Number of failures, %
Mechanical seals of shafts	30,4
Bearings	15,4
Personnel errors	12,1
Oil system	9,3
Increased vibration	4,3
Leakage and unloading system	3,9
Others	24,6

The most common method for analyzing vibration signals remains spectral analysis. However, it has significant limitations. In particular, different faults may lead to similar spectral patterns, which complicates correct interpretation. An example in Figure 1 shows that in the presence of a fault such as “Loss of support stiffness,” the vibration spectrum exhibits an increasing amplitude peak at the second rotational frequency over time, which corresponds to the fault type “Misalignment”. Thus, the same diagnostic features may correspond to different faults and defects, which can lead to false diagnostic results.

Figure 1 – Dynamics of frequency components under the influence of the “Loss of support stiffness” fault

Therefore, alternative approaches to vibration signal processing are being developed to improve diagnostic accuracy, such as wavelet analysis, phase portraits, envelope methods, and others [2, 3]. In recent years, time-frequency signal analysis methods, particularly wavelet analysis [4–7], have become increasingly widespread, allowing the study of vibration signals with simultaneous localization of energy components in time and frequency. Representing vibration data in the form of wavelet patterns (scalograms) creates prerequisites for extracting informative numerical features reflecting the technical condition of pump units and the degree of fault development.

However, the combined use of wavelet and spectral analysis requires a high level of personnel qualification. A promising direction is the automation of diagnostics using artificial intelligence methods. Such systems can partially replace human involvement, reducing the influence of subjective factors and providing more stable and timely diagnostics [8].

The object of this study is a centrifugal pump unit with a rotational frequency of 50 Hz, which is common equipment in the oil and gas industry. Previous studies on this topic [4–7] were conducted using signals of length 1024 points. However, modern measuring equipment allows recording signals of length 16,384 points. Figure 2 shows a comparison of wavelet patterns obtained from signals of the old and new formats.

Figure 2 – Examples of wavelet patterns obtained from signals of the old (a) and new (b) formats

With an increase in signal length from 1024 to 16,384 points, wavelet patterns become less visually interpretable: bright regions are blurred, and the structure becomes “flattened” due to the high density of information. This leads to the loss of contrast features that previously [6, 7] allowed sufficiently accurate identification of faults and their development stages. Such changes make previously developed methods for constructing and processing wavelet patterns [6, 7] inapplicable and require revision of the mathematical apparatus and adaptation of processing

algorithms. This confirms the need to develop a new method for quantitative analysis of wavelet transform images.

Obtaining a large number of real signals corresponding to a single fault type during its development is labor-intensive. Therefore, in this work, a method for synthesizing artificial vibration velocity signals is used. To generate an artificial signal for the “imbalance” fault, the formula proposed in [9] was used:

$$y = A \cdot \sin(\omega \cdot t) + \text{random. uniform}(-b, b),$$

where A is the amplitude of the vibration signal (mm);

ω is the angular frequency (Hz);

t is the time interval with a specified step (ms);

b is the maximum amplitude of the noise component (mm);

$\text{random.unifirm}(-b, b)$ – is a function generating a random real number in the range from $-b$ to b .

To formalize the information contained in wavelet patterns, it is reasonable to consider them as two-dimensional images in which pixel intensity is determined by the magnitude or energy of wavelet coefficients. This approach allows the use of image analysis methods to extract numerical features characterizing the spatial structure and texture properties of wavelet patterns.

One of the most common and well-formalized methods of texture analysis is the Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM) [10]. This method allows quantitative evaluation of relationships between pixel intensity levels at a given distance and direction, making it sensitive to changes in structure and heterogeneity. In the context of vibration diagnostics, such changes may be associated with the emergence and development of equipment faults.

Table 2 presents examples of contrast (C), homogeneity (H), correlation (Corr), entropy (Ent), and energy (En) values obtained for wavelet patterns corresponding to different stages of the development of fault type “Imbalance”.

From Table 2, it can be seen that the nature of the dependence (direct or inverse) is preserved over the entire RMS range for all parameters except contrast. It should also be noted that energy shows a significantly stronger correlation with the increase in RMS and, consequently, with the deterioration of the technical condition of the equipment.

Thus, the use of GLCM features for analyzing wavelet patterns makes it possible to move from subjective interpretation of visual images to a formalized description of the structure of vibration signals. This approach is particularly relevant when analyzing high-density wavelet representations, where traditional parameter ranges require revision. The obtained numerical features can be used as input data for classification and pattern recognition algorithms of the technical condition of

pump units, forming a basis for further development of automated vibration diagnostics systems.

Table 2 – Parameters of wavelet patterns during the development of fault type “Imbalance”

RMS, mm/s	Wavelet pattern	GLCM parameters				
		C	O	En	Corr	Ent
1		36,34	0,5926	0,2083	0,9606	4,247
4		38,93	0,7943	0,3894	0,9645	3,055
11		37,9	0,8491	0,6232	0,9664	2,374

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VIBRATION DIAGNOSTICS OF THE ACTUAL STATE OF THE ELECTROMECHANICAL SYSTEM IN START-UP MODE**Derkachev Sergey Vladimirovich***Candidate of Technical Sciences (PhD), Head of Laboratory
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Annotation. *The development of industrial equipment is largely ensured by the use of electromechanical systems that include a drive element – an induction motor. The technical condition of an electromechanical system ensures the continuity and efficiency of the technological process, which determines the relevance of applying various diagnostic methods in operational practice. A brief literature review of research in this area indicates a general trend toward the use of acoustic-vibration signal visualization, along with thermography methods, for widespread application. It is a well-known fact that transient processes possess high informational value for diagnosing the actual condition of an electromechanical system. In this study, the condition assessment was carried out by recording time-domain realizations of vibration acceleration during the startup of an electromechanical system (fan-type) in three mutually perpendicular planes, which was implemented using smartphone applications. The main objective of the study was to determine the possibility of using a smartphone to recognize categories of the technical condition of an electromechanical system during startup.*

As a result, the main signs of malfunctions in the electrical and mechanical parts of the electromechanical system when measuring vibration acceleration on the housing of the electric motor – the drive element – in the startup mode have been identified. The difficulties arising in the formalization of time-domain realizations are compensated by an understanding of the physical processes accompanying the startup process, as well as by the creation of a reference guide for the manifestation of fault indicators. The obtained results were used to make decisions regarding the feasibility of repair work and demonstrated sufficient accuracy for non-disassembly diagnostics using the specified method, based on relative and mutual assessment.

Keywords: *electromechanical systems, condition monitoring, vibration analysis, startup transient, smartphone diagnostics, predictive maintenance.*

The development level of modern industrial equipment is largely determined by the extent of its use in implementing various complex technological processes of electromechanical systems. An electromechanical system is understood as a system that includes a drive induction or synchronous electric motor, a coupling, and an actuator in the form of a pump, fan, gearbox, etc., designed according to a two-support shaft scheme with a cantilever or between-bearings arrangement of the working element.

The actual technical condition of any electromechanical system in long-term operation is assessed using a number of diagnostic methods, which, based on various diagnostic features, can identify through spectral analysis of stator currents. To detect broken bars in the squirrel-cage rotor winding of an induction motor, the following are used: regression analysis of the resultant stator current vector module [1], development of algorithms based on various signal processing approaches [2], defect signatures extracted from the current signal according to load level, repetition rate, and signal amplitude [3], and spectral subtraction of the current signal [4]. The occurrence of bearing unit damage is proposed to be diagnosed using the direct spectrum of the consumed current [5], as well as inclusive damage diagnostics based on the frequency components of the load current sidebands [6]. Measurement and analysis of vibration indicators enable reliable diagnosis of rotor-to-stator displacement and the development of stator winding short circuits [7], as well as the occurrence of inter-turn short circuits by combining wavelet packet decomposition and statistical correlation analysis [8]. Particular attention is paid to studying the causes of increased vibration: imbalance, bearing wear, cavitation, etc., based on an integrated approach, including spectral analysis in an extended frequency and dynamic range, and envelope analysis of the original vibration acceleration signal [9]. One of the directions in diagnosing electromechanical equipment in the oil and gas industry is the monitoring of mechanical vibrations and noise parameters [10].

In [11], it is indicated that the analysis of vibration signals requires expert knowledge, and the use of multi-axis statistical characteristics, machine learning algorithms, the K-nearest neighbors method, and decision trees for model construction is proposed. Article [12] examines the application of acoustic signal analysis for detecting faults in bearings, stator, and rotor. Methods of time-domain and frequency-domain analysis, as well as features extracted from raw acoustic data, are discussed. Studies [13] based on machine learning methods apply a classification technique, converting one-dimensional sound signals of bearings into two-dimensional scalograms for transfer learning using a pre-trained model.

Image classification models to detect faults in electrical machines and drives use the visualization of sound signals [14].

The infrared thermography methodology [15] provides data for analyzing fault states under three conditions: two levels and an intermediate level of broken rotor bar faults in an induction motor. Study [16] proposes the use of two-dimensional self-organizing operational neural networks for diagnosing misalignment and rotor faults based on thermal images of squirrel-cage induction motors.

The brief review of methods used for fault detection in an induction motor as a drive element of an electromechanical system indicates a trend toward the use of acoustic-vibration signal visualization, along with thermography methods, for widespread practical application. Consequently, research in this direction is relevant at the current technological level of knowledge in the field of diagnostics.

It is a well-known fact that for diagnosing the actual condition of an electromechanical system, transient processes possess high informational value, even relative to such an inert indicator as temperature. One of the transient processes of interest for diagnostics is the startup mode of an electromechanical system; however, its short duration limits the possibilities for spectral analysis of current characteristics, as this requires specialized equipment and a long measurement interval; the analysis of noise patterns, since its perception is always subjective; and measurements of overall vibration levels followed by spectral analysis – the processing time of the initial data is limited by the startup duration.

Based on the foregoing, it seems advisable to record time-domain realizations of vibration acceleration during the startup mode of an electromechanical system in three mutually perpendicular planes. However, in operational conditions, it is not always possible to install special sensors on the housing of the electromechanical system for measuring vibration levels, which makes vibration analysis difficult for diagnosing the actual condition of the electromechanical system. In this case, the recording of time-domain realizations of vibration acceleration can be implemented using modern smartphones, which allow measurement of vibration acceleration of the electromechanical system in startup mode thanks to built-in accelerometers, thereby providing a real picture of the change in vibration acceleration in three mutually perpendicular planes.

In industrial operating conditions of electromechanical systems, it is advisable to use a relative evaluation method, relying on the indicator capabilities of the accelerometer built into the smartphone. Therefore, the aim of the study is to minimize the vibration acceleration monitoring points using a smartphone in startup mode to recognize the technical condition of an electromechanical system at two levels – ‘satisfactory’ and ‘unsatisfactory’.

The scientific significance of the study lies in identifying the main signs of malfunctions in the electrical and mechanical parts of an electromechanical system when measuring vibration acceleration on the housing of the electric motor – the drive element – in the startup mode. The difficulties that arise in the formalization of time-domain realizations can be compensated by an understanding of the physical processes accompanying the startup process, as well as by creating a reference guide for the manifestation of fault indicators.

The practical significance of the study lies in the ability, under operating conditions, to use a smartphone software application to identify signs of an unsatisfactory condition of an electromechanical system, in order to take it out of service and carry out further non-disassembly diagnostics using more precise methods, including the methodology of vibration analysis of direct spectra, envelope analysis, spectrum analysis, etc. Recording a satisfactory condition allows continued operation of the electromechanical system with the same maintenance schedule.

To solve the stated problem, the following limitations and assumptions are proposed: the electric motor is a complex system whose elements interact with each other through the electromagnetic field between the stator and rotor; vibration propagates along several paths – stator – housing – foundation, rotor – shaft – bearing – end shield – housing... Localization of each type of possible damage along these vibration signal transmission paths requires an increase in the number of measurements and the use of vibration measuring instruments. This problem has been sufficiently studied and, despite some difficulties, is generally solvable.

In this work, it is proposed to monitor the condition of an electromechanical system in startup mode using a smartphone with a built-in accelerometer and the AccelerometerMeter mobile application, which will allow recording vibration acceleration indicators in three directions relative to the electric motor housing (Fig. 1): X – transverse (horizontal); Y – longitudinal (axial); Z – vertical. Limitations when solving the problem: the readings of the accelerometer built into the smartphone enable relative rather than absolute comparison, based on the results of instrumental measurements; the frequency of the recognized processes is determined by the interval between measurements – 0.005 s (200 Hz). These data are insufficient for making an accurate diagnosis but are sufficient for comparing similar motors operating under identical conditions (startup).

In this work, vibration acceleration measurements using a smartphone in startup mode were carried out during the startup of a SAB-163 screw compressor, whose electric drive is a KA7315L-ABO1B-301 induction motor with a rated power of 200 kW and a rotor speed of 2975 rpm, as well as during the startup of two DN-21GM smoke exhausters, whose drive is implemented using induction motors with a power of 90 kW and rotor speeds of 590 rpm.

Figure 1 – Vibration measurement directions relative to the position of the electric motor of the DN-21GM smoke exhauster drive

In industrial operating conditions of electromechanical systems (EMS), it is advisable to use a relative evaluation method, relying on the indicator capabilities of the accelerometer built into the smartphone. In the context of serial or mass production of EMS (including electric motors of various power ratings), precise metrological support is required, which is implemented using a range of modern vibration analyzers. The basis of the analysis, as mentioned above, is an accurate understanding of the physical processes occurring during startup.

Monitoring changes in rotational speed requires a contact or non-contact tachometer, turning routine diagnostics into a small research task, especially given the unknown variation of the motor torque M_d and the load torque M_c . Measuring current characteristics during the unsteady transient startup process presents a particularly challenging task in terms of analyzing the obtained data. Temperature indicators remain unchanged over such a short period.

Figure 2 shows the results of recording time-domain realizations of vibration acceleration during the startup mode of a SAB-163 screw compressor. The startup was carried out in the first stage with the stator windings of the drive induction motor connected in a 'star' configuration, followed by a switch to a 'delta' configuration after 10–12 seconds. Since the screw compressor is mounted on vibration isolators, the most informative direction for assessing vibration acceleration is the vertical direction (Z-axis).

Figure 2 – Time-domain realizations of vibration acceleration during startup of the SAB-163 screw compressor motor with damaged bearings

As can be seen from Fig. 2, now of startup of the induction electric drive, a zone of vibration acceleration instability occurs for 2 seconds, with amplitudes reaching 9.0 m/s^2 . During operation of the induction motor in startup mode with the stator windings connected in a ‘star’ configuration, unstable and poorly defined oscillations and beats appear in the time-domain realization of vibration acceleration, with a gradual decrease in amplitude, while the dominant frequency is 100 Hz, periodically decreasing to 50 Hz. Now of switching the stator winding connection of the drive induction motor to the ‘delta’ configuration, an impact occurs, the amplitude of which reaches 10 m/s^2 , followed by damped oscillations. After switching to the ‘delta’ stator winding connection scheme, non-periodic beats with a frequency of 5 Hz occur, while the amplitude of vibration acceleration oscillations at the fundamental frequency of 50 Hz decreases to 3.0 m/s^2 . The occurrence of the described symptoms is characteristic of possible disturbances in the electromagnetic interaction inside the induction motor due to deviations in the kinematics and shape of the rolling elements of the 6314-type bearing. Based on the analysis performed, a decision was made to replace the bearings, which should reduce the impact of additional emerging forces.

Visual inspection of the 6314-type bearing after disassembly of the induction motor revealed the cause of the elevated vibration acceleration values, which lies in the presence of oxidized grease that becomes coked during prolonged stoppages of the electric drive. An additional factor affecting bearing failure is the absence of special holes for the discharge of used grease in the design of the motor bearing units.

Figure 3 shows the results of recording time-domain realizations of vibration acceleration during the startup mode of the SAB-163 screw compressor after bearing replacement.

From Fig. 3, it follows replacing the bearings on the drive motor of the SAB-163 screw compressor, a reduction in vibration acceleration amplitudes to

4.2 m/s² was recorded during startup, and the time to reach nominal operating mode was 2.7 seconds. At the moment of switching the stator winding connection of the induction motor during startup from the ‘star’ to the ‘delta’ scheme, the vibration acceleration amplitude was 11.0 m/s², which is due to the nature of the interaction between the magnetic fields of the stator and rotor.

Figure 3 – Time-domain realizations of vibration acceleration during startup of the SAB-163 screw compressor motor after bearing replacement.

Figures 4 and 5 show the results of recording time-domain realizations of vibration acceleration after passing the initial maximum during the startup mode of two similar DN-21GM smoke exhausters – DN-3 and DN-4, which are driven by induction motors with a power of 90 kW and rotor speeds of 590 rpm.

Figure 4 – Time-domain realizations of vibration acceleration along three axes during startup of the DN-3 smoke exhauster motors

Differences in the realizations of the vibration acceleration signal in three mutually perpendicular directions allow diagnostic symptoms to be formulated. The predominance of values in the transverse (horizontal) direction – the X-axis – indicates loosening of bolted connections. Practically similar values in the vertical direction – the Z-axis – are a consequence of a compliant foundation. Smaller but still quite high values in the axial direction – the Y-axis – occur when there are misalignments between the motor and smoke exhauster shafts. The results of recording the time-domain realizations of vibration acceleration during the startup mode of the DN-3 smoke exhauster, shown in Fig. 4, indicate an increase in the vibration acceleration amplitude after reaching the nominal operating mode, particularly in the axial and vertical directions, which allows a well-founded conclusion about the unsatisfactory condition of the DN-3 smoke exhauster.

From the results of recording the time-domain realizations of vibration acceleration during the startup mode of the DN-4 smoke exhauster, shown in Fig. 5, it can be seen that the vibration acceleration amplitude did not exceed 4 m/s^2 , and the stabilization of indicators after reaching operating mode indicates a satisfactory condition of the DN-4 smoke exhauster.

Figure 5 – Time-domain realizations of vibration acceleration during startup of the DN-4 smoke exhauster motors – Z-axis

These conclusions are confirmed by the analysis of the results of measuring the overall vibration velocity level during long-term operation of the electromechanical system, which are presented in Table 1. The vibration velocity was measured at 4 points: Point 1 – free bearing of the motor; Point 2 – motor bearing on the coupling side; Point 3 – intermediate shaft bearing on the coupling side; Point 4 – intermediate shaft bearing on the impeller side.

Table 1 – Vibration parameter values for the control points of the smoke exhausters

Measurement point	Root mean square vibration velocity (mm/s) for measurement directions, frequency range 2...200 Hz		
	Vertical	Horizontal	Axial
Smoke exhauster DN-3			
1	3,0	7,0	-
2	2,9	6,4	3,3
3	3,4	10,5	9,0
4	11,7	8,3	16,1
Smoke exhauster DN-4			
1	1,5	1,8	-
2	1,3	1,7	1,2
3	1,6	1,7	1,5
4	1,6	1,5	1,4

The vibration inspection was carried out in full compliance with the current regulatory framework: GOST 24346–80. Vibration. Terms and definitions; GOST ISO 5348–2002. Vibration and shock. Mechanical mounting of accelerometers; GOST ISO 20816–3–2023. Vibration. Condition monitoring of machines based on vibration measurements on non-rotating parts.

The assessment of the technical condition of the electromechanical system was carried out by measuring the vibration level and comparing it with the standard values regulated by GOST R ISO 20816–1–2021 ‘Vibration. Vibration measurement and evaluation of machine vibration condition. Part 1. General guidelines’ and GOST IEC 60034–14–2014 ‘Rotating electrical machines. Part 14. Mechanical vibration of certain machines with shaft heights of 56 mm and above. Measurement, evaluation, and vibration severity limits.’ The vibration velocity values defining the condition boundaries are up to 4.5 mm/s – operation without time limitation; 4.5...7.1 mm/s – operation for a limited period of time; above 7.1 mm/s – possible machine damage.

From the results shown in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5, it becomes possible to trace the changes between the electromagnetic torque of the electric motor and the load torque. The instability of the electromagnetic torque of the electric motor is determined by the mechanical characteristic and depends on the rotational speed, which could not be determined due to the presence of additional disturbances, mains frequency, rolling bearings, the condition of the actuator, etc. The differences between the vibration of the electric motor operating alone and after connection to the actuator make it possible to assess the level of additional forces acting on the motor components.

Another diagnostic parameter for the condition of electromechanical systems can be the system startup time and its reaching of nominal operating mode, especially when the moment of inertia of the working machine exceeds the moment of inertia of the drive motor rotor and when the load torque is unstable. As a rule, the values of the electromagnetic torque of the drive motor and the load torque of the driven mechanism are unknown; however, it is known that the startup duration is shorter, the greater the values of the load torque of the mechanism and the electromagnetic torque of the motor. Therefore, the startup time of an electromechanical system can be used for mutual and relative comparison when assessing the technical condition of the electromechanical system. Figure 6 shows the results of recording time-domain realizations of vibration acceleration during the startup mode of the DN-15 smoke exhauster.

Figure 6 – Time-domain realizations of vibration acceleration along three axes during the startup mode of the electric motor driving the DN-15 smoke exhauster

The startup duration of the DN-15 smoke exhauster motor was 11 seconds. The moment of reaching the nominal operating mode of the smoke exhauster is

characterized by stabilization of the vibration acceleration amplitude values at a high level of 40 m/s^2 . The unsatisfactory condition is confirmed by the instability of the vibration acceleration amplitude along the measurement axes. In this case, the cause of such high vibration acceleration amplitude values is a compliant foundation and impeller imbalance.

One of the signs of deviations in the operation of the mechanical system of an induction motor is the beat mode shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7 – Time-domain realizations of vibration acceleration during the occurrence of beats.

This mode was recorded on an induction motor with a power of 300 kW and a rotational speed of 2975 rpm after 28 years of operation. The damage manifests itself in the form of oscillations with a frequency of 5 Hz (period of 0.2 s) and beats with a periodicity of 3 s. This suggests the presence of loosening of bearing seats and non-uniformity of the air gap between the stator and rotor.

The obtained results allow us to draw the following conclusions:

1. It has been experimentally confirmed that the startup mode of an electromechanical system is sufficiently informative for making a preliminary diagnosis of the actual condition. Analysis of time-domain realizations of vibration acceleration in the startup mode makes it possible to identify hidden defects that may be masked or manifest with small amplitude in steady-state operation. Characteristic diagnostic signs have been established for defects in the mechanical (loosening of fasteners, imbalance, bearing wear) and electrical (electromagnetic asymmetry) parts of the system, manifested in changes in amplitude-frequency characteristics, the appearance of beats, and impact pulses in specific spatial directions.

2. A methodological approach has been developed and tested for rapid assessment of the technical condition of electromechanical equipment based on indicator measurements using a smartphone's built-in accelerometer. The possibility of using a mobile device as an accessible means of primary diagnostics for classifying

the condition into 'satisfactory' and 'unsatisfactory' levels has been demonstrated. The scientific novelty of the approach lies in substantiating the minimally necessary monitoring configuration (three mutually perpendicular directions) and using relative and mutual evaluation of signals, which compensates for the lack of metrological certification of the built-in sensor.

3. A set of diagnostic signs for interpreting vibration signals in the startup mode has been formed and verified on real industrial facilities, forming the basis for creating an expert symptom reference guide. Correlations have been established between the predominance of vibration acceleration in a certain direction (axial, transverse, vertical) and the type of potential defect (misalignment, imbalance, foundation compliance). The obtained results provide a foundation for knowledge formalization and subsequent development of machine learning algorithms for automatic fault classification.

4. The practical significance of the study lies in the proposal of a two-level monitoring system. At the first, operational level, it is proposed to use a smart-phone for screening and identifying systems with signs of deteriorating condition. At the second, in-depth level, such systems are subjected to detailed analysis using professional vibration diagnostic complexes (spectral, envelope, spectrum analysis). This allows optimization of maintenance resources, increased operational reliability through early defect detection, and minimization of equipment downtime.

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PROHIBITED INGREDIENTS IN NICOTINE-CONTAINING PRODUCTS: CLASSIFICATION, TOXICITY MECHANISMS AND CONTROL METHODS

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Abstract. *This article provides a review of substances prohibited for use as ingredients in nicotine-containing products, according to the draft technical regulation of the EAEU. A classification of banned compounds by risk groups is provided (organic acids, fat-soluble vitamins, tar oils, terpenes, flavorings, aldehydes, solvents, essential oils, plant extracts). The pathophysiological mechanisms underlying the toxicity of diacetyl (obliterative bronchiolitis), vitamin E acetate (EVALI syndrome), ethylene glycol (acute renal failure), thujone, and camphor (neurotoxicity) are described. The instrumental control methods reviewed include: gas chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry (GC–MS), high-performance liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (HPLC–MS), gas chromatography with flame ionization detection (GC–PID), spectroscopic methods, and thin-layer chromatography (TLC). It was concluded that banning the specified substances is justified, as well as the need to adapt existing analytical methodologies for controlling the component composition of the aerosol.*

Keywords: *nicotine-containing products, aerosol, banned ingredients, diacetyl, α -tocopherol acetate, EVALI, gas chromatography–mass spectrometry.*

Quality and safety control of nicotine-containing products (NSP) is a critical task, since consumer health directly depends on the chemical composition of the inhaled aerosol [1]. In response to growing concerns about the harms of traditional tobacco smoking, manufacturers have introduced innovative types of

nicotine-containing products to the market, fundamentally different from conventional combustible tobacco products [2].

The electronic nicotine delivery system (ESDN) represents an innovative product actively offered on the market. A distinctive feature of the ESDN is the absence of tobacco: instead of tobacco filler, they contain a specialized liquid. Upon heating of the electric element, the liquid is converted into an aerosol inhaled by the user. The liquid for ESDN includes glycerin, propylene glycol, flavoring agents, as well as nicotine salts (nicotine-free products also exist) [3].

Standardized analytical methods have been developed to assess safety and ensure quality control of traditional smoking products. In the Russian Federation, the primary regulatory document governing requirements for liquids used in ESDN is GOST R 58109–2018 “Liquids for electronic nicotine delivery systems. General technical specifications” [4]. However, this standard focuses predominantly on limiting nicotine concentration and basic physicochemical characteristics, leaving the chemical composition of flavorings, solvents, and other components insufficiently controlled [1].

The rapid development of the nicotine-containing product market has resulted in stricter safety requirements in several foreign countries [5]. Lists of substances prohibited as ingredients have been formulated. These restrictions are intended to reduce toxicity and decrease the appeal of these products to minors.

The Russian market faces significant regulatory gaps concerning the safety of nicotine-containing product ingredients, due to the regulatory framework lagging behind the technological development pace in the industry [2]. Current regulatory documents predominantly limit the concentration of nicotine; however, they do not provide adequate control over the chemical composition of substances, particularly under conditions of heating and aerosol formation.

In the draft technical regulation of the Eurasian Economic Union ‘On Requirements for Nicotine-Containing Products’ (2024 version, public discussion) [6], covering both nicotine-containing and nicotine-free products, a list of substances prohibited in the production of NSP has already been established. However, a mandatory toxicological evaluation of components in the aerosol consumed from NSP has yet to be established. When heated, organic compounds decompose, forming toxic products that pose direct health risks to consumers [7]. This gap can only be addressed through the implementation of mandatory laboratory monitoring standards encompassing both the source liquids and the final aerosol [8].

The objective of this study is to review literature data on the effects of substances listed as banned ingredients in nicotine-containing products, alongside an analysis of the mechanisms underlying their toxic effects during aerosol inhalation. Understanding these mechanisms is essential for substantiating

regulatory measures, developing analytical control methods, and establishing unified safety assessment criteria for NSP within the framework of EAEU technical regulation [5,6].

In the EAEU draft technical regulation [6], as well as in normative documents of several foreign countries [5], a list of specific compounds has been compiled, the use of which in ESDN liquids and nicotine-free mixtures is strictly limited or completely prohibited. The list presented includes compounds with proven toxicity, carcinogenicity, or the ability to cause serious health damage via inhalation, oral ingestion, or dermal contact.

A comparative list of banned substances, grouped by compound classes, indicating their status within the regulatory base of the Russian Federation/EAEU [4,9,10] and the main health risks, is presented in Table 1.

Table 1 – Comparative list of banned and restricted substances in nicotine-containing products

Substance group	Substance	Status (RF/EAEU)	Risks
Organic acids	Agaric acid	Prohibited	General toxic effects, mucous membrane irritation
Fat-soluble vitamins	Tocopherol acetate (vitamin E)	Prohibited	EVALI syndrome, alveolar epithelium destruction
Tar oils	Birch, juniper	Prohibited	Content of carcinogenic polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs)
Terpenes/ Ketones	Camphor, Thujone	Prohibited	Neurotoxicity
Flavorings	Diacetyl, Coumarin	Restriction / Prohibited	Bronchiolar damage, hepatotoxicity
Aldehydes	Bitter almond oil (containing free or bound hydro- cyanic acid)	Prohibited	Acute cyanide poisoning
Solvent	Ethylene glycol	Prohibited	Nephrotoxicity, metabolic acidosis upon inhalation and oral intake
Essential oils containing safrole	Sassafras oil, camphor oil	Prohibited	Carcinogenic potential, hepatotoxicity
Plant extracts	Safflower extract	Restriction	Risk of lipoid pneumonia associat- ed with inhalation of oily fractions

As evidenced by the presented data, banned substances belong to various chemical classes and manifest their toxic effects through diverse

mechanisms – ranging from acute cytotoxicity to long-term carcinogenic and neurotoxic effects. Presented below is a brief analysis of the key pathophysiological mechanisms underlying the toxicity of the most significant components from the list of banned substances.

Diacetyl (2,3-butanedione) – a flavoring agent that imparts a buttery taste to the product. Upon inhalation, this compound induces irreversible scarring of the bronchioles – a condition known as obliterative bronchiolitis (“popcorn lung”) [11]. The pathophysiological mechanism involves damage to the ciliated airway epithelium, disruption of mucociliary clearance, and subsequent bronchiolar fibrosis [11, 12]. The disease is characterized by progressive dyspnea, nonproductive cough, and respiratory failure; no specific treatment exists, except for lung transplantation at the terminal stage [12]. It is important to note that diacetyl is safe when ingested orally, but when inhaled, it bypasses the hepatic barrier and directly affects the respiratory epithelium [11, 12].

Tocopheryl acetate (vitamin E) became a key factor in the 2019 EVALI outbreak (e-cigarette or vaping product use-associated lung injury) [13]. Using neutron spin echo and X-ray scattering methods, it has been shown that vitamin E acetate causes softening of the membranes of the pulmonary surfactant – a critically important biological fluid that ensures alveolar stability during breathing [14, 15]. This disrupts surfactant adsorption at the air-liquid interface and contributes to alveolar collapse during exhalation, which clinically manifests as acute hypoxia and respiratory failure [13–15]. The substance also accumulates in alveolar epithelial cells, which explains its prolonged retention in the lungs [15].

Ethylene glycol – a toxic alcohol that can be present in nicotine-containing products as a result of using unrefined raw materials. Upon inhalation, ethylene glycol is rapidly absorbed and metabolized by alcohol dehydrogenase into glycolic and oxalic acids [16]. The accumulation of oxalic acid leads to the formation of calcium oxalate crystals in the renal tubules, causing acute renal failure [16, 17]. The clinical presentation also includes central nervous system depression and metabolic acidosis [17].

Thujone and camphor are classified as terpenoid ketones. Upon inhalation, these compounds can cross the blood-brain barrier. The neurotoxic mechanism of thujone involves non-competitive inhibition of GABA receptors, which reduces inhibitory neurotransmission and may induce seizure propensity. Camphor, in turn, inhibits nicotinic acetylcholine receptors, thereby disrupting neuromuscular transmission [18].

Monitoring the levels of banned ingredients in nicotine-containing products is based on instrumental physicochemical analysis methods, governed by regulatory standards [4, 8–10]. The primary methods (Table 2) include gas and liquid chromatography, which enable highly accurate compositional analysis [8].

Table 2. Instrumental methods of physicochemical analysis applied to the determination of banned substances in nicotine-containing products

Analytical method	Analytes	Principle of operation
Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS)	Diacetyl, thujone, coumarin, saffrole (component of saffras oil), camphor	Separation of volatile components followed by identification using mass spectra
High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC/LC-MS)	Vitamin E acetate, agaric acid, coumarin	Separation of non-volatile and thermolabile compounds in the liquid phase
Gas chromatography with flame-ionization detection (GC-PID)	Ethylene glycol, diethylene glycol, diacetyl	Quantitative determination of organic compounds
Infrared and ultraviolet spectroscopy	Coumarin, hydrocyanic acid derivatives	Identification by characteristic absorption bands
Thin-layer chromatography (TLC)	Vegetable oils and extracts	Rapid qualitative assessment of the presence of target components; preliminary screening

It should be noted that all the listed methods primarily focus on the analysis of the initial liquid [4], whereas actual consumer exposure occurs through inhalation of the aerosol generated during heating. Thermal degradation of liquid components may result in the formation of new compounds not present in the original sample [7], necessitating the development of additional methods for aerosol analysis under dynamic conditions that simulate real product use [8,19].

Thus, the current array of analytical tools is sufficient for detecting banned ingredients in liquids but requires expansion regarding the control of the final aerosol [7, 8].

As evident from the review above, the implementation of a ban on the use of these substances as flavor and aroma additives in the manufacture of nicotine-containing products is well justified, considered constructive, and consistent with the concept of reducing health risks for consumers [8, 12, 13].

Ensuring the safety of nicotine-containing products requires a comprehensive approach that combines the efforts of governmental regulators and manufacturers. It is essential to implement strict quality standards, conduct regular monitoring of product composition for banned substances, and limit availability to minors. Only the combination of legislative measures and laboratory chemical control can effectively minimize risks to public health.

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**ANALYSIS OF THE MAIN PHYSICAL PHENOMENA
IN CROSS-LINKED POLYETHYLENE DURING PARTIAL
DISCHARGES IN ORDER TO GENERATE INITIAL DATA
FOR ITS MODELING**

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Abstract: *Modern solid extruded polymer materials, such as cross-linked polyethylene (XLPE), have recently become widely used in the electrical insulation of underground high-voltage power transmission cables.*

However, the electrical strength of a high-voltage cable depends on a number of factors arising during the cross-linking process, installation, and operation of the cable. Cable electrical strength is affected by cross-linking methods, adherence to cross-linking process parameters, voids formed during extrusion, installation defects such as burrs, filings, and scratches on the cable insulation, and mechanical stress during bending. All of these factors reduce the cable's electrical strength to varying degrees. The processes occurring in the voids in the insulation deserve special attention. During installation and operation, when the insulation is subjected to electrical, mechanical, and thermal stress, these voids can create a noticeable discontinuity. The processes occurring in these gas inclusions have not yet been adequately studied, and there is no single theory with predictive power. This article analyzes a large number of experiments conducted in various laboratories and offers an explanation for some of the phenomena occurring in solid polymer dielectrics in the presence of gas inclusions.

Keywords: *cross-linked polyethylene, partial discharges, gas inclusions in cross-linked polyethylene, diagnostics, modeling, polyethylene cross-linking methods*

1. INTRODUCTION

The formation of small gas-filled cavities in solid dielectrics is virtually impossible to avoid during the manufacturing process. Under certain conditions, these cavities can be critical to the service life of high-voltage equipment.

Studying the formation and distribution of electric fields in insulating materials is of significant interest to electrical engineers during the design and operation of high-voltage equipment. The maximum field strength in an insulation system is an important parameter to control, as it influences the initiation and propagation of a discharge within the dielectric.

As is well known, a number of conditions are required for electrical breakdown to occur. One critical condition is increased field strength in certain areas of the insulation. High field concentrations occur in a heterogeneous environment. Local mechanical stresses, uneven crosslinking, residues from unreacted catalysts, insufficient antioxidants, and other factors can lead to heterogeneous formation of the molecular structure of cross-linked polyethylene. This, to some extent, leads to localized excesses of the electric field strength. A separate problem is the formation of gas-filled cavities in a polymer dielectric. As is well known, the permittivity of a gas is many times smaller than that of a solid dielectric. From the condition of continuity of the electric displacement vector in the absence of free charges at the dielectric boundaries, it follows [1]:

$$\varepsilon_V \cdot E_V = \varepsilon \cdot E$$

Где: E_V – field strength in a gas void,

ε_V – permittivity of a gas void,

E – field strength in a dielectric,

ε - permittivity of a dielectric,

$$E_V = \frac{\varepsilon}{\varepsilon_V} \cdot E$$

$$\varepsilon \gg \varepsilon_V$$

$$E_V \gg E$$

Thus, the resulting air inclusions are spatial entities and can have the highest electric field strength, which initiates partial discharges in the dielectric. Figure 1 shows a schematic of the field distribution in the dielectric in the case of a gas inclusion.

Figure 1. Distribution of electric field strength in a dielectric in the presence of a gas void.

This article is essentially devoted to the analysis of air inclusion ionization processes in polymers. This analysis provides a profound understanding of the physical and chemical processes occurring in cross-linked polyethylene during partial discharges. The goal of this scientific analysis is to develop the initial data for a mathematical model to study the dependence of oscillatory wave phenomena on the composition and cross-linking process of polyethylene.

2. THEORY

2.1. CROSS-LINKING METHODS AND INFLUENCE ON THE ELECTRIC STRENGTH OF POLYETHYLENE.

Cross-linking of polyethylene is a physical process that alters the molecular structure through the formation of cross-links. The molecules are linked into a cellular three-dimensional network. The chemical composition of the substance remains unchanged. There are three main cross-linking methods. Physical (radiation) cross-linking, in which ionizing radiation causes hydrogen atoms to break away from carbon atoms, resulting in the formation of cross-linkable bonds between carbon molecules [1–3]. This method produces the lowest percentage of cross-links. Chemical cross-linking methods include silane and peroxide cross-linking. The most common, less expensive, and faster method of cross-linking is silanol (silane) cross-linking of polyethylene, which involves the addition of active silane molecules (silicon compounds). Cross-linking is performed in a humid environment (steam, water) [4–7]. When cross-linking polyethylene using the silane method, water vapor is present, accumulating in the space between the insulation layers. When operating voltage is

applied to the insulation, water molecules polarize and are drawn into the intermolecular space of the cross-linked polyethylene, forming water treeing. This creates conditions for the formation of electrical treeing, which subsequently develops into a streamer and electrical breakdown.

Peroxide crosslinking has become more widespread because the resulting material possesses high mechanical and dielectric properties [4,7]. During polyethylene crosslinking, the starting material is melted with antioxidants and peroxides, followed by extrusion. As the temperature increases, the peroxides decompose into free radicals, which mediate the bonding of carbon molecules into a three-dimensional network of ethylene polymer chains, reminiscent of the quasi-crystalline lattice of solid insulators [5,6]. The production of crosslinked polyethylene using the peroxide method uses dicumyl peroxide as an additive and eliminates the need for an aqueous medium. This reduces the risk of water treeing. However, there are some peculiarities to the polymerization of polyethylene in the presence of dicumyl. Studies [4] show that increasing the concentration of dicumyl peroxide reduces the dielectric strength of polyethylene. According to [7], this occurs due to the high chemical activity of the remaining free radicals and the subsequent formation of a space charge, which contributes to a decrease in the dielectric strength of the material.

2.2. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM OF FORMING INITIAL DATA FOR MATHEMATICAL MODELING

During numerous experimental studies [8–12], a picture is observed in which the intensity of partial discharges is higher not at the maximum of the applied voltage, but during periods of its fastest increase, as shown in Figure 2. That is, at those moments when the derivative with respect to voltage has a maximum value

$$\frac{dU}{dt} = \max$$

Since an insulator located between two conductors is essentially an electrical capacitance, and the current in the capacitance, described by the expression

$i_c = C \cdot \frac{dU}{dt}$, is nothing more than the intensity of the discharge process in the die-

lectric. This is confirmed by the laws of electrical engineering. However, the fact that breakdown of an air dielectric does not occur at the peak value of the field strength E suggests a more complex mechanism for the formation of partial discharge conditions. These processes are likely related to polarization or the formation of space charges.

Figure 2. Voltage distribution in a dielectric during partial discharges. $U(t)$ – is the voltage applied to the test object; $U_{10}(t)$ – is the voltage across the gas cavity if no discharge occurs; $U_1(t)$ – is the voltage across the gas cavity during discharges.

The proposed process following the formation of the PD:

1. After the initial PD, gas ions contained in the cavity rush along the field lines and collide with the inner walls of the cavity. Possible outcomes: a) transition to a free state in the intermolecular space and rush toward the counter electrode; b) combine with free radicals remaining from the cross-linking process; c) form a covalent polar bond with the carbon molecules forming the polymer chain.

2. Before any of the above-mentioned outcomes occur, the ions released during the PD hit the inner walls of the cavity. As is known, charges do not move along the surface of an insulator perpendicular to the field lines. Remaining on the cavity walls for some time, they form an internal electric field $E/$ directed opposite to the external field E , as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Distribution of electric field strength immediately after partial discharge

3. As the external field strength associated with the line voltage decreases, discharges occur in the cavity under the influence of the internal electric field strength E' . This may explain the fact in Figure 1 that partial discharges of reverse polarity begin during the decreasing positive half-wave of the external voltage.

Between two successive partial discharges, time passes during which the capacitance charges and free ions in the cavity interact with the cross-linked polyethylene according to one of the aforementioned mechanisms. The fact that the discharges occur at the same voltage across the cavity indicates that, in the time interval between discharges, free ions formed as a result of previous partial discharges have had time to diffuse into the dielectric, as shown in Figure 4. The fact that the discharge intensity decreases for most of the period during which E reaches its maximum suggests a multiphase mechanism for the formation of conditions conducive to partial discharges. Clearly, the rate of voltage increase influences the process of ion diffusion into the dielectric.

A proposed explanation for this process is as follows: during the cross-linking process, not all carbon molecules formed covalent non-polar bonds with each other, resulting in cross-links that formed a cellular three-dimensional network [13]. Some carbon molecules remained bound to hydrogen in covalent polar bonds. This type of chemical bond has a dipole moment, which, according to dielectric spectroscopy, directly affects ion diffusion. An intense increase in the external field strength at the beginning of the period is accompanied by polarization of molecules bound by covalent polar bonds and changes in their spatial orientation. These orientational movements lead to vibration of the intermolecular space,

which ensures the movement of ions within the dielectric. As the intensity $\frac{dU}{dt}$ of vibration decreases, diffusion ceases. The ions remain within the gas cavity, preventing the formation of an avalanche with their field E .

Figure 4. The process of ion diffusion into a dielectric after a partial discharge in a void.

3. CONCLUSION.

Based on these considerations, we plan to develop a mathematical model that takes into account the influence of the electrical viscosity of a cross-linked polymer on the formation of partial discharges. The model's input parameters should include the cross-linking process characteristics: temperature, peroxide and anti-oxidant concentration, extrusion pressure, and the presence of nanofillers such as SiO₂, Al₂O₃, and TiO₂. The modeling results should enable the determination of the optimal composition and cross-linking mode for polyethylene that meets stringent operating requirements.

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**METHODOLOGY FOR TEACHING THE SECTION
“DIGITAL-TO-ANALOG AND ANALOG-TO-DIGITAL
CONVERTERS (DAC/ADC)” OF THE DISCIPLINE
“ELECTRICAL MEASUREMENTS”**

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Annotation. *The DAC/ADC section of the “Electrical Measurements” discipline includes a theoretical understanding of the principles of operation, classification of devices, analysis of their parameters, and practical research. To effectively master the material, it is necessary to use lectures, laboratory work, and software-based modeling. Independent work of students should also be provided.*

The article discusses various aspects of the methodology for teaching the DAC/ADC section of the “Electrical Measurements” discipline at USPTU in relation to automation specialties.

Keywords: *Analog-digital converter (ADC), digital-analog converter (DAC), digital counter, clock pulse generator (CPG), parallel-type ADC, serial-type ADC, tracking-type ADC, conversion time, conversion error, static and dynamic characteristics of DAC/ADC, voltage comparator, quantization step.*

1. Introduction

The lecturer of the discipline “Electrical Measurements” for the DAC/ADC section should formulate the following goals:

1. Educational: Studying the principles of information conversion, sampling and quantization, studying functional and structural schemes, static and dynamic characteristics of DACs and ADCs.

2. Practical: Acquiring the skills of choosing DAC/ADC for specific measurement tasks, calculating errors and working with measurement interfaces.

3. Metrological: Understanding the influence of bit depth, sampling frequency and noise on the accuracy of measurements.

The study of the DAC/ADC section of the Electrical Measurements discipline requires a certain balance between circuit theory, metrology, and practical application. In addition, the DAC/ADC section is studied in the fourth semester of the second year, at the same time as the courses “Analog Electronics” and “Metrology,” and the course “Digital Electronics” is studied in the fifth semester of the third year. This creates certain difficulties in the study of digital electronics.

2. Section structure (distribution of hours)

The section is divided into three logical blocks:

- 1) Theoretical foundations of the functioning and construction of DAC/ADC,
- 2) Digital-to-analog converters (DAC).
- 3) Analog-to-digital converters (ADC).

The sequence of study (first DAC and then ADC) is due to the fact that ADCs often use DACs in the feedback loop.

3. Content of the section by topic:

Topic 1. General issues of sampling and quantization (2 hours of lectures + 2 hours of practical classes)

Topic 2. Digital-to-analog converters (DAC) (2 hours of lectures + 4 hours of laboratory classes)

Topic 3. Analog-to-digital converters (ADC) (4 hours of lectures + 6 hours of laboratory classes)

Topic 4. Interfaces of measurement systems based on DAC/ADC (2 hours of lectures).

4. Content of the section topics

Topic 1. Theoretical foundations (sampling and quantization)

1) Basic concepts:

a) Continuous and discrete signals. The difference between them, the features of the mathematical description.

b) Kotelnikov (Nyquist-Shannon) theorem – restrictions on the sampling frequency.

c) The process of quantization: the step of quantization, the quantization noise.

2) Teaching methods:

a) Visualization: Use animations in Mathcad and Electronics Workbench, showing how a smooth sine wave or “saw” turns into step functions.

b) Demonstration of aliasing effect: Show the change in the spectrum, with an insufficient sampling rate.

Topic 2. Digital-to-analog converters (DAC)

1) Basic concepts:

a) Principles of summation of currents and voltages.

b) Schemes: weighing resistive DAC, R-2R ladder grid DAC (the most important scheme).

c) Characteristics: Resolution, differential nonlinearity (DNL), integral nonlinearity (INL), settling time.

2) Teaching methodology:

a) Analogy: Explain the R-2R principle through voltage division or binary weights (1, 2, 4, 8...).

b) Calculation task: Students are given an input binary code (e.g., 1011) and a reference voltage (U_{ref}). They must calculate the output voltage for an ideal DAC.

c) Metrology: Discuss static and dynamic errors. Explain why the actual DAC characteristic may deviate significantly from a straight line.

Topic 3. Analog-to-digital converters (ADC)

1) Basic concepts:

Classification: direct and balancing conversion. Types of ADC:

1. Parallel (Flash) – maximum speed, high consumption, low bit depth.
2. Sequential approximation (SAR) – the “golden mean”, the principle of half division.
3. Tracking type – continuous tracking and direct conversion of the input analog signal into a digital code, high accuracy with a slow change in the input signal.
4. Sigma-delta (Sigma/Delta) – oversampling and noise reduction, high accuracy (for precision measurements).

2) Teaching methods:

a) Algorithmization: For the successive approximation ADC, ask the students to play the game “Guess a number from 0 to 15” (Yes/No) to understand the logic of the successive approximation register (SAR).

b) Comparative analysis: Create a table with ADC types on the vertical axis and speed, resolution, cost, and consumption on the horizontal axis. The students should

5. Laboratory practice

Laboratory work is one of the basics in teaching methodology. It is necessary to use virtual tools (for example, Electronics Workbench) and real DAC/ADC modules.

Laboratory work No. 1: Research of DAC characteristics

Purpose: To obtain the transfer characteristic of the DAC.

Tasks:

1. To supply the input with a sequence of codes from 000...0 to 111...1.
 2. To measure the output voltage with a voltmeter.
 3. To plot the graph $U_{out}(\text{Code})$.
-

4. To calculate the absolute error at each point, to find DNL and INL.

5. Optional: Generate a low-frequency signal (“sin” or “sawtooth”) through the DAC and view it on the oscilloscope (comment, see the steps, explain).

Laboratory work No. 2: Research of the ADC of the sequential approximation

Purpose: To study the dependence of the result on the input signal.

Tasks:

1. To remove the characteristic of the conversion (to give a known voltage, to read the digital code).

2. To determine the resolution (in volts per 1 least significant bit – LSB).

3. To investigate the differential nonlinearity (loss of codes or extra codes).

Laboratory work No. 3 (Metrological): Dynamic parameters and the effect of overlapping spectra

Purpose: Practical confirmation of the Kotelnikov theorem.

Tasks:

1. Apply a sinusoidal signal to the ADC input.

2. Sample the signal at a frequency of F_s .

3. Restore the signal and plot the spectrum (FFT).

4. Change the input signal frequency so that it exceeds $F_s/2$ and register the appearance of a false low-frequency component (aliasing).

6. Independent work and control

To consolidate the material, it is proposed to use the following forms:

1. Solution of metrological measurement tasks:

Example: The ADC has a bit-depth of 12 bits and an input voltage range of 0...10 V. What is the quantization step? What will be the code at a voltage of 3.5 V?

Example: Calculate the maximum input signal frequency for an ADC with a conversion time of 20 μ s.

2. Case Study (Case Study):

Tasks:

1) Develop a temperature measurement system in a furnace (slow process, high noise)”.

2) Develop an oscilloscope (fast process). Students must choose the type of ADC and justify their choice (Tracking or Parallel).

3. Testing:

Checking the knowledge of definitions (appature uncertainty, quantization step, weight of the digit). Determining the type of DAC/ADC circuit from the circuit diagram.

7. Recommended learning tools

1. Software:

Electronics Workbench: Simulation of DAC/ADC circuits.

Mathcad: Visualization of signal sampling and reconstruction, and plotting of spectra.

2. Hardware:

Signal generator.

Digital oscilloscope.

Training stands.

8. Schemes for practical and laboratory classes

1) The appearance of the front panel of the measuring stand with a DAC/ADC is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 – Appearance of the front panel of the measurement bench with DAC/ADC

The part of the measurement bench shown in Figure 1 is designed for practical and laboratory exercises with R-2R-type DACs and parallel-type ADCs.

2) A schematic model of the interaction between the DAC and the ADC is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2 – Diagram of the “function generator” model for studying the interaction between DAC and ADC in a digital system

Figure 3 – Tracking-type ADC model diagram

The schematic is implemented in the EWB simulator. The model contains two library DACs, U1 and U2, and one library parallel-type ADC, U2. The word generator is connected to the DAC U1. The word generator is programmed in hexadecimal code. The DAC, U1, reproduces this code in analog form. The analog signal from the output of U1 is fed to the ADC U2. The digital signal from the U2 output is fed to the digital oscilloscope and the second DAC, U3. The analog oscilloscope shows the output signals from the DAC, U1, and the DAC, U2.

3) A working model of a tracking-type ADC is presented in Figure 3.

The circuit is implemented in the EWB simulator, and it is possible to trace the operation of the ADC and observe the oscillograms at various points in the circuit. The circuit includes a voltage difference detector A1, a two-threshold comparator (window comparator), AR1, AR2, U1, R1...R4, a clock generator, V3, a reverse counter U3, a digital-to-analog converter, U4, reference voltage sources V1, V2, and a logic circuit U2 that passes pulses from the V3 generator to the CP input of the reverse counter U3. The digital output of the ADC (N) is four-bit.

4) Figure 4 shows a diagram of a bit-by-bit balancing ADC model. The scheme works according to the algorithm given in the training materials on the theory of the ADC of the bit-by-bit balancing. At the first clock cycle, the senior digit of the DAC is turned on, forming a voltage of 8 V on the non-inverting input of the comparator. If the value of $U_x > 8$ V, then the senior (left on the scheme) digit of the register is transferred to the active state at the moment of writing. At the same time, a unit is supplied to the lower input of the OR logic circuit from the output of this digit, and in subsequent clock cycles, the 8 V source will participate in the formation of the output voltage of the DAC. If the U_x value is < 8 V, then the highest digit remains inactive for all subsequent clock cycles. On the second clock cycle, the next highest DAC discharge is turned on, and a voltage of 12 or 4 V is generated at the output (depending on the state of the highest discharge). This algorithm persists further.

The diagram in Figure 4 allows you to observe the processes in the ADC and obtain a characteristic of the ADC converter.

9. Conclusions

The article discusses the methodology of teaching the DAC/ADC section of the discipline "Electrical Measurements". The course is designed for one semester of the second year. The content of the section, the main topics of the section, and the methodology of teaching the topics of the section are considered.

The laboratory practice covers all the topics, which means that the theoretical and practical parts of the section are inextricably linked to each other. Independent work of students is provided.

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THE MAIN PROBLEMS OF WELL CEMENTING AUTOMATION

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Abstract. *This article examines the problem of limited automation in the cementing process of oil and gas wells. Existing cementing control stations (CCS) mainly perform measurement and recording of technological parameters but do not provide intelligent decision support when anomalies arise. Based on the analysis of the literature, the causes of the current situation have been identified: non-stationarity of the hydraulic process, absence of direct measurements in the annular space included in typical cementing control stations (CCS), limitations of actuators, as well as the transitional period between technological frameworks in the industry. The necessity to develop decision support systems (DSS) based on machine learning methods and fuzzy logic has been substantiated.*

Keywords: *well cementing, cementing control station (CCS), automation, cementing anomalies, decision support system (DSS), digitalization, machine learning.*

Cementing of casing strings is the final and most critical stage in the construction of oil and gas wells. The quality of these operations determines the durability of the well, the sealing integrity of the annular space, and the environmental safety of subsoil use [1].

The cementing process is characterized by high dynamism, irreversibility, and limited decision-making time in the event of abnormal situations. Currently, data during cementing are recorded by cementing control stations (CCS) equipped with sensors measuring pressure, temperature, density, and flow rate [1]. However, as noted in [1], a significant drawback of the cementing control station (CCS) is its mere recording of obtained data without involvement in process management.

The relevance of this study stems from the necessity to modernize existing cementing control systems by integrating intelligent decision support modules.

To ensure high-quality and reliable zonal isolation during cementing, two essential conditions must be satisfied: a strong bond between the wellbore walls and the cement stone, and the formation of a defect-free cement sheath behind the casing [1]. Meeting these conditions is achieved through control of the hydraulic process, which ensures regulation of fluid flow rates, pressure, and density at the wellhead and bottomhole of the well.

The turbulent flow regime of buffer fluids and cement slurry behind the casing enables removal of the loose part of the clay cake from the wellbore walls and ensures maximum displacement of the drilling mud [1]. The need to control hydraulic processes arises at two main stages of cementing:

- at the stage of preparing and pumping the cement slurry into the casing following the buffer fluid, which is necessary to prevent complications such as gas, oil, and water shows, losses, and wellbore wall collapse. These complications may occur due to a reduction in hydrostatic and hydrodynamic effects in the annular space [1];
- at the stage of displacing the cement slurry behind the casing, where it is essential to create and maintain a turbulent flow regime to enable the slurry to pass through the formation isolation intervals in the most critical sections of the behind-casing space [1].

The predominance of measuring and recording cementing control units over control systems is due to several objective technical and technological factors.

Unlike many continuous production operations where operational parameters can be stabilized, during well cementing the density, viscosity, and flow rate of the injected fluid fundamentally vary over time. As the annular space fills, the hydrostatic pressure of the fluid column increases, necessitating continuous adjustment of the pump operating conditions. The development of an automatic control system capable of adequately responding to such changes represents a complex technical challenge [3].

A key problem in cementing automation is that direct measurement of pressure and temperature in the annular space during standard cementing operations is not conducted. Existing field studies [5] and specialized continuous monitoring systems [8, 9] demonstrate the technical feasibility of such measurements; however, these are not included in the functionality of standard cementing control stations (CCS), which constitute the primary tools for the operator. Installation of SPCT sensors is performed at the wellhead—in the pumping line between the cementing units and the cementing head. Accordingly, the assessment of processes occurring behind the casing string is conducted indirectly:

- by the difference between the injected and discharged fluid volume (to detect fluid losses or gas-oil-water influxes);
 - by changes in wellhead pressure (for diagnosing casing string sticking or blockage).
-

This indirect method has fundamental limitations: it does not enable localization of the anomaly's origin, exhibits low accuracy, and provides a signal with significant delay relative to the emergence of the anomaly [4].

The study [6] presents the dynamics of cementing quality over the 2012–2022 period, which does not show sustained growth despite ongoing efforts. This confirms the necessity of changing the approach to improving the cementing process.

One way to achieve positive progress in production processes is the use of machine learning algorithms in the development of new technological solutions [2]. Both domestic and international oil and gas companies are already implementing digital technologies across many production processes: from seismic exploration to modeling energy demand [2].

In the field of well cementing, the application of machine learning methods provides new opportunities. As shown in [7], the accumulated cementing data from leading oil and gas production companies is sufficient to develop machine learning-based software products to enhance the sealing quality of well cementing [7].

The digitalization of the approach to improving the quality of well cementing involves:

- data collection and verification;
- visualization of input data;
- mathematical modeling based on standard methods and machine learning algorithms followed by comparison;
- expert analysis of the results [7].

One promising direction is the development of decision support systems (DSS) that, by analyzing measured parameters (pressure, flow rate, density), can automatically classify the type of emerging anomaly and provide the operator with recommendations for adjusting the operational mode.

As reasonably noted in work [3], the control system should incorporate more effective methods for regulating cementing processes, in particular by employing an open-closed loop control strategy. Based on real-time statistical analysis of current measurements and previously established dependencies, the automation of current situation assessment is achieved, which is used to adjust the parameters of the mixture preparation and fluid displacement program [3].

Methods of rough set theory (RST) can be applied to classify types of objects and cementing processes, enabling the identification of distinguishable classes of well models and their use in constructing rules for situation assessment and parameter adjustment within control algorithms [3].

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PROCESSING OF DATA FROM THE HETEROGENEOUS TELECOMMUNICATION NETWORK STATUS MONITORING SYSTEM

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***Abstract.** The article examines data processing methods for the monitoring system tracking the status of elements within a heterogeneous telecommunication network.*

***Keywords:** heterogeneous telecommunication network, monitoring system, data processing, statistics.*

Introduction

To date, one of the most important objectives of modern telecommunication networks is to provide high-quality transport services with minimal network equipment failures. In this regard, to enhance network reliability, studies on monitoring and management of telecommunication networks are pertinent [1].

Maintenance of telecommunication networks entails addressing a complex array of tasks, including network monitoring and management, detection and resolution of emerging issues, failure forecasting and prevention, resource accounting, network performance management, network infrastructure planning, service management, and quality monitoring [2].

Problem Statement

According to the recommendations of the International Telecommunication Union, telecommunication network management is constructed on a four-level scheme: network element management level; network management level; service management level; business management level [3].

To assess the condition of telecommunication network elements, it is necessary to process data from the network monitoring and management system.

Through processing the monitoring system data, a pie chart of damage causes will be constructed for detailed analysis. The pie chart of damage causes in the network is shown in Fig. 2.

This study will facilitate the identification of months during which the highest number of significant damages occurred. It will also enable the planning of the network expenditure budget based on the causes of failures.

The initial data presented in the table in Fig. 1 represent numerical values of the statistical indicator arranged chronologically as time series.

The analysis of time series is directed towards accomplishing two primary objectives: examining the internal structure and nature of the series under study and forecasting its future values based on historical data. These two key tasks are interconnected.

The resolution of the first problem is critically important for the development of the mathematical model, its precise definition, and formal representation. Any time series comprises two main components: a time scale with measurement points (e.g., failure moments) and observed values (equipment condition).

The second task holds particular significance, as forecasting constitutes the ultimate objective of the entire analytical process. The first analytical direction, although fundamental and mandatory, functions solely as a preparatory stage for addressing the main problem. Forecasting consists of extrapolating future values of a time series based on historical data processed using an identified mathematical model.

Figure 2 – Pie chart of causes of damage in the network

The moving average is a statistical data processing method that allows smoothing of a time series and the identification of main trends in the variation of the indicator. To obtain it, average values are computed over a specified number of consecutive points in the series, with the calculation interval gradually shifting forward. This approach reduces the influence of random outliers and fluctuations, thereby facilitating the identification of stable patterns in the analyzed data.

Moving averages are widely applied in the analysis of economic and financial time series, as well as in other domains where understanding the long-term dynamics of indicators is crucial.

Constructing a plot of the moving average enables a clear determination of the overall trend: if the line slopes upward, an increasing tendency is observed; if it slopes downward, a decline is indicated. This tool also facilitates the prompt identification of trend reversals and smooths irregular fluctuations in the input data.

A moving average will be employed for the analysis of dynamics. This approach will enable monthly forecasting for 2026, allowing the identification of periods most likely to experience the highest number of failures.

Figure 3 shows the graph of the number of failures for 2025 with the moving average, where the actual and forecast curves, which nearly coincide, are clearly visible.

Figure 3 – Graph illustrating the number of failures in 2025 with a moving average

Conclusion

The monitoring system enables the proactive detection of network problems to prevent losses, reduce the number of complaints from subscribers and affiliated operators, and minimize financial losses due to lost calls.

To solve the problem of loss minimization, it is necessary to process the data from the monitoring system of the heterogeneous telecommunication network, which are represented as time series.

It can be concluded from the foregoing that the application of probabilistic-statistical models in the monitoring and control of telecommunication networks enables comprehensive analysis of network status data and the forecasting of network behavior through statistical methods.

Such models facilitate the prediction of network failure incidents, the condition of network elements, and the optimization of network performance. Consequently, forecasting supports informed decision-making processes aimed at more effective management of telecommunication networks.

Processing time series data from the monitoring system statistics for 2023–2025 will allow forecasting the condition of network elements in 2026, enabling the implementation of preventive measures to avert damages and significantly improve the network's operational parameters and the quality of services provided to subscribers.

Furthermore, forecasting the condition of network elements will enable planning the budget for network repair and maintenance, thereby improving the company's planned economic and operational indicators operating this equipment [7].

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TRANSFORMATION OF THE RUSSIAN BANKING SYSTEM IN TIMES OF CRISIS: SPECIFIC DEVELOPMENTS UNDER SANCTIONS

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Abstract. *This article conducts a comprehensive analysis of the current stage of mergers and acquisitions in the Russian banking sector, aiming to clarify the direction of further development of Russian banks toward business consolidation through mergers with other market participants. The article provides an overview of the Russian and international banking sectors' mergers and acquisitions markets to facilitate an evaluation of the current status of this segment in Russia. Moreover, the author presents the dynamics of statistical indicators of the considered markets over recent years, as well as an analysis of the most significant strategic transactions involving major banks. Based on the conducted research, the article identifies key trends for the Russian banking mergers and acquisitions market at the current stage, including technological companies entering the credit institution market, the acquisition of small and medium-sized banks by large banks, the acquisition of non-financial companies by market leaders to develop an ecosystem approach, as well as banks acquiring companies offering fintech solutions. The author emphasizes that the identified trends will strengthen in the near future, as Russian regulatory authorities facilitate justified and prudent consolidation of the sector with the aim of preventing the persistence of weak market participants. The conclusion of the article focuses on forecasting the factors that will determine the further development of the Russian banking mergers and acquisitions market, the key among them being the macroeconomic and geopolitical conditions. The article is based on the author's master's dissertation research.*

Keywords: *Russia, sanctions, mergers and acquisitions, banking sector, consolidation, financial technology, ecosystem approach, integration.*

Under the current conditions of a complex conjuncture and elevated financial market volatility, alongside heightened competition among companies, mergers and acquisitions (hereinafter – M&A) transactions play a key role in business development strategy due to the strengthening trend of capital concentration within firms, particularly in dynamic and highly competitive sectors such as the banking industry. Thus, banks, particularly in the Russian Federation, have in recent years actively employed M&A to reinforce their positions and achieve sustainable growth through the optimization of business processes, expansion and diversification of the client base, and the adoption of new technologies. Consequently, since the global crisis of 2008, Russia has experienced a sustained trend towards a reduction in the number of commercial banks, driven by the exit of weaker institutions from the market and the consolidation of positions by larger entities. Overall, this is supported by the Central Bank of the Russian Federation, as capital consolidation facilitates the elimination of unreliable creditors and represents an optimal strategy for survival and enhancing the competitiveness of other banks. Nevertheless, mergers and acquisitions involving banks, particularly transactions among major banks, exert a substantial influence on the country's population, since credit institutions serve millions of retail clients and legal entities who depend on the stability of the banks' operational activities, given that these banks function as their creditors and holders of savings. In this regard, defining the direction of M&A activity development among Russian banks for the coming years is of paramount importance, as this will enable the formation of a clear understanding of the sector's current state and its anticipated transformations in the future.

The objective of the research presented in this article is to identify the key trends in M&A involving Russian banks and to develop a forecast for the further development of this segment based on a comprehensive analysis of the current situation in both the Russian and international markets, specifically the United States of America (hereinafter – the USA) and Europe.

To construct a reliable, comprehensive, and practically oriented informational base for the research, the article employs a wide range of sources, including public disclosures of Russian banks, regulatory and legal acts governing banking activities and merger procedures, as well as data on specific transactions from databases recording conditions, prices, terms, and participants. The theoretical section draws on monographs and articles published in specialized journals focusing on corporate finance, banking development strategies, and methods for investment efficiency evaluation.

Review of Russian and international experience in mergers and acquisitions in the banking sector

Mergers and acquisitions transactions in the banking sector possess a number of specific characteristics that distinguish them from analogous transactions in related and other industries. Furthermore, different phases of economic development

at the global level define M&A features relevant to particular time periods. To achieve a deeper and more accurate understanding of these characteristics at the present stage in Russia, it is necessary to analyze both domestic and foreign mergers and acquisitions experience from recent years.

First, it is necessary to define what is understood by an M&A transaction in the banking sector within the context of this article. The author refers to and examines two types of company consolidations under this term in the article. On one hand, this is the acquisition by a bank of a third-party business in a different industry – for example, a conglomerate transaction whereby the bank expands its areas of influence and creates an ecosystem of interconnected products under a single brand. On the other hand, an M&A transaction in the banking sector denotes a transaction involving the merger of two credit institutions into a new unified entity or the acquisition by one bank of a competitor within the industry [1].

The vast majority of M&A transactions involving banks take place within the framework of stringent regulatory requirements established by supervisory authorities. Depending on the jurisdiction of the companies, requirements may vary [2]; this section examines the regulatory specifics of transactions and their influence on the M&A market in the banking sector both in Russia and internationally.

In the Russian Federation, bank reorganization is governed by the Bank of Russia. It should be noted that the regulatory framework is subject to change, with trends in the formulation of regulatory procedures evolving in response to the level of economic activity, investment climate, exchange rate fluctuations, and the political situation in the country [3]. Thus, for example, at various times, the Federal Antimonopoly Service (FAS) strengthened and relaxed oversight over the banking M&A market, depending on the degree of risks related to competition restrictions, with the objective of controlling economic concentration. The Bank of Russia, in turn, consistently reviews the requirements for transactions in the banking sector: in 2024, the regulator abolished the requirement to submit a business plan when approving transactions involving the acquisition of more than 10% of shares (stakes) of a credit institution by another bank. The regulator justified this by eliminating regulatory redundancies. In 2026, the Central Bank announced its intention to increase the minimum capital requirements for Russian banks, adjusting them to the accumulated inflation rate. It is anticipated that this change will raise the regulatory standard to 540-600 million rubles, whereas about 20% of credit institutions currently do not meet these requirements. Therefore, such banks will need to increase their capital or, alternatively, consider the option of merging with larger organizations. Overall, regulatory requirements for M&A transactions in the Russian banking sector are designed to mitigate risks to the public, which is achieved through adaptive supervisory measures [4]. The prevailing

trend in Russia is to encourage interbank M&A transactions in order to reduce the number of high-risk banks and increase capital concentration.¹²

A similar strategy is observed among governments in international markets. For instance, in the United States, bank merger regulations are intended to ensure the country's financial stability, protect consumers, and promote fair competition [5]. In the United States, the Bank Merger Act (BMA) was enacted to oversee such transactions—this law regulates mergers between insured banks and savings associations. Banking mergers and acquisitions in the United States, as in the Russian Federation, require prior approval from the Federal Reserve Board (FRB) and/or the Office of the Comptroller of the Currency (OCC). Nevertheless, it is worth noting that the approval process for banking transactions in the United States has been less rigorous over the period from 2006 to 2022. The Federal Reserve approved 4,506 applications for bank mergers, while rejecting only one. Moreover, in May 2025, The OCC reinstated the simplified procedure for evaluating bank M&A, which had previously been complicated by the former administration. Regulation of bank M&A transactions in the USA is characterized by dynamic changes, with the strictness of the control measures applied depending on the policies of the federal government, individual states, and the overall economic situation in the country [6].³⁴

With regard to the European Union, the regulation of M&A transactions in the banking sector also encounters uncertainty. While the European Commission holds exclusive competence concerning such transactions, thereby ensuring uniform regulation throughout the EU based on the international regulatory framework for banks Basel III, which is to be implemented in the EU from 2025, national governments of individual Union member states continue to exert control

¹ The Central Bank cancelled the business plan requirement for M&A transactions – *Kommersant Finance*. 2024. URL: <https://www.kommersant.ru/doc/6715656> (access date: April 21, 2026).

² The Central Bank will double capital requirements for banks, allowing a five-year transition period – *Kommersant Finance*. 2026. URL: <https://www.kommersant.ru/doc/8481185> (access date: April 21, 2026).

³ Pam Martens, Russ Martens. In 16 Years, the Fed Has Approved 4,506 Bank Mergers and Denied One – *Wall Street On Parade*. 2023. URL: <https://wallstreetonparade.com/2023/01/in-16-years-the-fed-has-approved-4506-bank-mergers-and-denied-one/> (access date: April 21, 2026).

⁴ Max Bonici, Stepher T. Gannon OCC Reverts to Prior Merger Rules – *Davis Weight Tremaine LLP (DWT)*. 2025. URL: <https://www.dwt.com/blogs/financial-services-law-advisor/2025/05/occ-reverts-fintech-bank-merger-rules> (accessed: 21.04.2026).

over their domestic financial systems. This creates an unstable environment for mergers and acquisitions.¹

Let us briefly review the analyzed banking M&A markets to trace how regulation in the sector affects the deals conducted.

The United States has historically been the country with the highest M&A activity. In 2025, 179 deals were completed in the banking sector, totaling \$190 billion. in the United States, representing an increase of 129% compared to 2024. The average deal value has also nearly doubled. The largest deals are presented in Table 1.2

Table 1. Largest M&A Transactions in the US Banking Sector in 20253

Deal Participants	Type of Transaction	Transaction Outcome	Transaction Value
Fifth Third and Comerica	Merger	Formation of the 9th largest bank in the US by assets > \$288 billion	\$10.9 billion
Huntington Bank and Cadence Bank	Merger	Formation of the 10th largest bank in the US by assets > \$276 billion	\$7.4 billion
PNC and FirstBank	Acquisition of FirstBank	PNC's asset growth amounted to \$27 billion	\$4.1 billion

In the European market, the results for 2025, as in the United States, align with the overall trend and demonstrate positive dynamics. In the financial sector, the number of deals increased from 183 in 2024 to 219 in 2025, with the aggregate valuation of these deals rising more than fourfold: from \$17.5 billion USD to \$73 billion USD. Table 2 presents the largest banking deals of the year.⁴

¹ Basel III – Finance – European Commission, Directorate-General for Financial Stability, Financial Services and Capital Markets Union. 2024. URL: https://finance.ec.europa.eu/news/basel-iii-2024-07-25_en(accessed on: 21.04.2026).

² Bennet Habliston, John Hill, Brad Schaltenbrand Banking Industry Outlook: U.S. Banking M&A Caps Off a Historic 2025 – JD Supra. 2026. URL: <https://www.jdsupra.com/legalnews/banking-industry-outlook-u-s-banking-m-2687487/> (accessed: 21.04.2026).

³ Prepared by the author

⁴ Sarah Graham Global financial services M&A activity rose in 2025, with 93 deals over \$1b in value announced – Ernst&Young. 2026. URL: https://www.ey.com/en_gl/newsroom/2026/01/global-financial-services-m-and-a-activity-rose-in-2025-with-93-deals-over-1b-in-value-announced (date accessed: 21.04.2026).

Table 2. Major M&A Transactions in the European Banking Sector in 2025¹

Deal Participants	Type of Transaction	Transaction Outcome	Transaction Value
Mediobanca and Banca Monte dei Paschi di Siena	Mediobanca Takeover	Formation of the Third Largest Bank in Italy	\$13.7 billion
BPCE and novobanco	Takeover of novobanco	BPCE Market Expansion	\$7.4 billion
Erste Group Bank and Santander Bank Polska	Takeover of Santander	Entry into the Central and Eastern European Market	\$7 billion

Examples from the US and European markets demonstrate that banking M&A activity is gaining momentum, as many companies in the sector shift their focus from ‘survival’ to strategic development [7]. Overall indicators for M&A in the global financial sector demonstrate positive dynamics: in 2025, deals totaling \$418.9 billion were recorded. This figure for the USA is 48.5% higher than the corresponding figure for the previous year.²

In contrast, in Russia, the total amount of M&A deals reached \$27.6 billion. This amount for the USA is 37% lower than the corresponding figure for 2024. This represents the lowest level in the past 20 years. The number of transactions also declined by 23%, amounting to 290 transactions. The banking sector’s share in the overall statistics for Russia accounted for 8% by total value and 5% by number, with 14 transactions totaling \$2.2 billion USD. The largest transactions involving banks in Russia in 2025 are presented in Table 1.5.3.

Despite the fact that since 2022 the Russian M&A market has been under considerable pressure due to the high cost of deal financing, restrictions on attracting foreign investments, increased tax burden, as well as the overall challenging geopolitical and economic environment of the country, M&A activity among companies in the Russian banking sector has not ceased and remains quite noticeable and significant within the overall market dynamics.

¹ Prepared by the author

² Sarah Graham Global financial services M&A activity rose in 2025, with 93 deals over \$1b in value announced – Ernst&Young. 2026. URL: https://www.ey.com/en_gl/newsroom/2026/01/global-financial-services-m-and-a-activity-rose-in-2025-with-93-deals-over-1b-in-value-announced (date accessed: 21.04.2026).

³ Mergers and acquisitions market in Russia in 2025 – Kept. 2026. URL: https://assets.kept.ru/upload/pdf/2026/02/ru-kept-ma-2025-survey.pdf?utm_source=ma2026 (date accessed: 21.04.2026).

Table 3. The largest M&A transactions in the Russian banking sector in 2025¹

Transaction object	Acquirer	Acquired share, %	Deal amount, million USD
Avito (marketplace)	Rosselkhozbank	50	>1,000 (according to expert estimates)
Europlan (leasing company)	Alfa-Bank	87.5	647
Prosveshchenie (publishing house)	VEB.RF	25	614

The conducted review of domestic and international M&A markets and the latest trends in the banking sector reveals that the Russian market, due to a number of geopolitical, regulatory, and economic factors, does not align with general market trends. Nevertheless, Russian companies continue to pursue new strategies for growth in the complex prevailing context, emphasizing the acquisition of technology firms and the development of the fintech segment.

Key M&A Trends Involving Russian Banks

To outline the current trends characteristic of the Russian banking M&A market, it is necessary to highlight several principal distinctive features of this segment:

1) Extremely high concentration – as of early 2025 the 10 largest banks' share of sector assets reached 80.7% [8], and this indicator is steadily increasing, largely due to the strengthening of major banks' positions following the exit of foreign banks and consolidation among Russian banks. Consequently, a trend towards a reduction in the number of credit institutions and the displacement of weaker players can be observed [9]; the statistics are presented in Figure 1.2.

2) Adaptability and flexibility – under conditions of nearly constant uncertainty and challenges faced by the banking sector throughout the entire history of the Russian Federation, large domestic banks have learned to respond effectively to such challenges. For example, starting in 2022. The banking sector in Russia has encountered unprecedented pressure – the largest banks were disconnected from SWIFT, and a portion of assets was frozen abroad, compelling banks to urgently pursue new solutions, partly through mergers and acquisitions.

¹ Developed by the author

² Koshkina Y. Experts predicted that within a year fewer than 300 banks will remain in Russia // RBC Finance. 2025. URL: <https://www.rbc.ru/finances/25/02/2025/67bc4a7e9a794774b00d680b> (accessed: 21.04.2026).

Fig. 1 Number of banks in Russia from 2019 to 2026.1

3) A high level of digitalization – banks actively incorporate digital technologies into their business processes: artificial intelligence, automation of communications via chatbots and AI assistants, big data–driven solutions, biometric identification, and others [10]. Often, due to the high resource consumption involved in independently implementing high-tech solutions, banks turn to M&A to acquire companies offering ready-made fintech solutions.

4) Active interaction between the regulator and banks – the Bank of Russia maintains direct engagement with market participants not only within the framework of supervision but also concerning joint initiatives and the improvement of the regulatory and legal framework of banking regulation, aiming to maintain a healthy competitive environment, foster innovation, and overcome crisis-related challenges.

On the whole, the Russian banking sector can be characterized as a dynamic, highly concentrated yet flexible market that is actively evolving under adverse conditions. Concurrently, the industry exhibits features of an oligopoly, with the firm dominance of several large banks—significant resources are required for new entrants to penetrate the market. Nevertheless, due to the intensive growth of fintech, new banks established by technology companies have been able to achieve strong performance. Thus, in 2021, Wildberries acquired Standard-Credit, which

¹ Quantitative characteristics of the banking sector of the Russian Federation // Central Bank of the Russian Federation (Bank of Russia). Official website. URL: https://cbr.ru/statistics/bank_sector/lic/ (accessed: 21.04.2026).

was subsequently renamed Wildberries Bank; Ozon acquired Oney Bank, currently operating as Ozon Bank; Yandex acquired Acropol Bank, now operating as Yandex Bank. According to the 2024 results, these credit institutions demonstrated the highest market growth rates, while maintaining a relatively small share compared to 'traditional' banks. Table 4 presents the performance indicators of the main banks in the e-commerce sector.¹

Forecast for the Development of the Russian Banking M&A Market

The current situation in the Russian banking M&A market does not align with the global trend of market consolidation and acceleration of transactions. Thus, following a period of dynamic growth in both the number and volume of transactions—caused by the withdrawal of foreign companies from the banking sector and the general business imperative to emerge from the crisis associated with the coronavirus pandemic in 2020—a decline in business activity is observed. In forming a forecast for the market in the foreseeable future, it should be taken into account that over the next five years the macroeconomic situation in Russia will be determined by a combination of factors, including sanctions pressure, monetary-credit policy, legislative changes, and others. These conditions will exert a significant impact on the M&A market involving Russian banks. Taking into account this specificity and the trends examined earlier in the article, several tendencies can be identified that the Russian banking M&A market is expected to follow over the next five years.

Firstly, the growth rate of transaction volume is most likely to remain fairly moderate. Against the backdrop of the country's sluggish overall economic development, dynamic growth in M&A activity cannot be expected, as banks are under pressure from tight monetary policy, and credit institutions face severe limitations in funds for investment in expansion and growth. Nevertheless, if the key interest rate continues to decline in line with market expectations, debt financing will become more accessible, which may exert a positive influence on the M&A market, including transactions involving banks. However, with interest rates remaining high, deals will be restricted to the most profitable projects or to forced restructurings.

Secondly, sanctions will continue to play a significant role in banking M&A. On the one hand, existing measures limit the inflow of foreign investment that could otherwise facilitate the stimulation of M&A activity between banks and non-financial companies. On the other hand, restrictions on access to international capital markets will incentivize the search for domestic sources of financing and partnerships with state funds and development institutions [11].

¹ Fintech at full stake: how the largest marketplaces establish their own banks // Forbes Finance. – 2025. URL: <https://www.forbes.ru/finansy/533212-finteh-va-bank-kak-krupnie-jsie-marketplejsy-sozdaut-sobstvennye-banki> (accessed on: 21.04.2026).

Thirdly, the significant influence of the state on the banking market remains high. This will be reflected in the expected tightening of capital and liquidity requirements by the Bank of Russia, which will encourage smaller banks to merge with larger players to comply with regulatory norms, consequently continuing the consolidation of the banking sector [12]. Major players will aim to expand their client base, geographical presence, and product range through M&A. It is also important to note that the regulator will participate in the most significant transactions through direct investments, support for specific projects, or regulation of the terms of such deals [13].

Fourthly, a key driver of M&A activity among banks in Russia continues to be the digital transformation of business [14]. Fintech sector transactions are expected to continue developing as banks acquire companies to accelerate digitalization, expand their own ecosystems, and enhance competitiveness [15], particularly involving new banking entities established by the country's largest technology firms.

Conclusion

In summary, the research presented in this article allows us to conclude that the future development of the M&A sector involving banks in Russia, which is currently in a challenging situation, largely depends on the macroeconomic and geopolitical environment. Simultaneously, based on the analysis of the current stage of M&A transactions in the Russian banking sector and a comparison with the state of foreign markets, key trends for the Russian market have been identified that will enable the sector to continue its development despite existing barriers. Competent and precise coordination of business and governmental actions, along with the rationale and prudence of decisions in strategic planning to shield the Russian banking sector from crisis, constitute the foundation for its successful survival and effective further development.

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ECONOMIC THINKING AS A TOOL FOR RATIONAL BEHAVIOR IN MODERN SOCIETY

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Abstract. *This article explores the concept of economic thinking as a fundamental mechanism for optimizing individual and collective decision-making in the context of modern society. In an era characterized by information overload, global economic volatility, and diverse consumer choices, the ability to apply economic principles to everyday life becomes a vital competency.*

Keywords: *Economic thinking, rational behavior, modern society, decision-making, financial literacy, opportunity cost, utility optimization, behavioral economics, cognitive biases, resource allocation.*

In the context of rapid globalization, technological transformation, and increasing economic complexity, the ability of individuals to make rational decisions has become more important than ever. Modern society is characterized by a constant flow of information, uncertainty in financial markets, and the growing interdependence of economic actors. Under these conditions, economic thinking emerges as a crucial tool that enables individuals, businesses, and policymakers to analyze situations logically, evaluate alternatives, and choose the most efficient course of action.

Economic thinking can be defined as a systematic approach to understanding how scarce resources are allocated to satisfy unlimited human needs. It involves the application of key economic principles such as opportunity cost, marginal analysis, cost-benefit evaluation, and incentives. By applying these principles, individuals are better equipped to assess risks, anticipate outcomes, and avoid irrational or impulsive behavior. Thus, economic thinking not only enhances personal financial well-being but also contributes to the overall efficiency and stability of the economy.

However, despite its importance, rational behavior is not always observed in real life. Behavioral economics has demonstrated that individuals are often influenced by cognitive biases, emotions, and social factors, which can lead to suboptimal decision-making. This creates a gap between theoretical rationality and actual

behavior. Therefore, studying economic thinking as a tool for promoting rational behavior becomes highly relevant in the modern era.

In standard microeconomics, decision makers are assumed to use available information in an unbiased manner and to choose the option that maximizes expected utility. This framework allows diverse preferences to be translated into comparable “utils”, enabling analysis of how individuals allocate scarce resources among competing needs. Rational choice models provide a parsimonious mathematical basis for understanding consumption, saving and investment decisions.

However, psychologists and evolutionary economists have shown that human decision making deviates from strict utility maximization. People rely on heuristics that are adaptive in specific contexts but may not be globally optimal; they discount future benefits differently across domains, display risk aversion or risk seeking, and incorporate social motives such as altruism or conformity. An expanded view of rationality emphasizes domain-specific decision rules that are shaped by the environment and life-cycle stage. Behavioral economics integrates insights from psychology to explain anomalies like loss aversion, framing effects and time inconsistency.

Economic thinking provides tools to improve rationality despite cognitive limitations. Key principles include:

Scarcity and opportunity cost: resources (time, money, natural resources) are limited; choosing one option means forgoing another. Recognizing opportunity costs helps individuals compare alternatives objectively.

Marginal analysis: decisions should consider incremental costs and benefits. For example, consumption continues until marginal benefit equals marginal cost.

Incentives: people respond to incentives. Pricing, taxes or subsidies influence behavior by altering costs and benefits.

Trade-offs and time: intertemporal choices require discounting future benefits against current consumption. Rational decisions often balance short-term satisfaction with long-term objectives.

By applying these principles, individuals can analyse complex situations more systematically and reduce the influence of biases.

At the micro level, economic thinking helps households and consumers allocate budgets efficiently, plan savings and investment strategies, evaluate insurance options and avoid impulsive purchases. For instance, understanding opportunity cost encourages people to weigh the long-term benefits of education against immediate earnings. Marginal analysis helps in deciding how much leisure time to sacrifice for additional work or study. Economic thinking also enhances awareness of sunk costs; rational actors avoid letting past investments distort future decisions.

Nonetheless, rationality is bounded. Individuals face cognitive constraints, incomplete information and behavioral biases such as overconfidence, herd behavior and present bias. Evolutionary psychology suggests that domain-specific heuristics,

developed in response to survival and reproductive challenges, continue to influence modern economic choices. Recognizing these biases and applying economic reasoning can mitigate their impact but cannot eliminate them entirely.

Firms rely on economic thinking to set prices, decide on investment projects, manage inventories and allocate resources across divisions. Profit maximization requires understanding demand elasticity, cost structures and competitive dynamics. Marginal analysis guides production decisions by equating marginal cost and marginal revenue. Opportunity cost informs decisions to enter or exit markets or invest in research and development. Importantly, businesses must anticipate competitor reactions and regulatory constraints.

Governments apply economic thinking when designing public policies, taxation, social welfare programs and regulatory frameworks. Cost–benefit analysis assesses whether public investments (roads, schools, hospitals) generate benefits that exceed costs. Recognition of externalities motivates interventions such as pollution taxes or subsidies for education. Competition policy aims to ensure efficient resource allocation and innovation by preventing monopolistic practices. Economic thinking therefore plays a central role in achieving social objectives like growth, equity and sustainability.

There is broad consensus that competition delivers substantial benefits for consumers and the economy. The OECD notes that competition leads to more choice, advanced products and services, higher quality and lower prices, thereby enhancing consumer welfare and economic growth. Competition stimulates innovation by forcing firms to continually improve products and processes to maintain market share [1]. Open and contestable markets encourage efficient firms to expand and inefficient ones to exit, leading to productivity gains and sustainable growth. Historical experience shows that suppressing competition, as occurred under centrally planned economies, results in concentrated industrial structures and low innovation. Transition countries that successfully fostered competition achieved improved performance. Building an effective competition framework involves reducing state control, strengthening legal and institutional foundations, and promoting a competition culture [1].

Competition policy should prioritize the competitive process rather than outcome-oriented goals such as simply reducing prices. In Uzbekistan, price regulation remains a major task of the antimonopoly authority: the regulator controls prices for natural monopolies and numerous commodity exchange markets. Pricing abuses receive special attention in law. However, the OECD cautions that focusing on price outcomes instead of ensuring the competitive process works may be misguided. Outcome-oriented goals can divert resources away from core competition tasks and lead to over-regulation. The report recommends prioritizing process-based enforcement and ensuring that other policy considerations do not undermine core competition objectives.

Uzbekistan inherited a concentrated industrial structure and strong state involvement in the economy. Since the early 1990s, the country has adopted competition

laws, created enforcement agencies and sought to reduce monopolistic activities [3]. Reforms intensified after 2017 with the National Strategy of Development, establishment of an independent Antimonopoly Committee (ACRU) and adoption of roadmaps for competition development [4]. Despite progress, challenges persist: the regulatory mandate is broad, price regulation tasks remain extensive and enforcement resources are stretched.

To illustrate how economic thinking and competition relate to economic outcomes, this section reviews recent macroeconomic indicators for Uzbekistan. The Asian Development Bank (ADB) reports that GDP growth increased from 6.3% in 2023 to 6.5% in 2024. Industry growth accelerated from 6.4% to 6.8%, driven by strong demand for construction materials, petrochemicals and textiles, while services growth increased from 7.1% to 7.7%. Robust investment and rising household consumption contributed to demand-side growth: private consumption rose from 7.0% to 9.0%, and investment growth surged from 23.4% to 27.6% [2]. Inflation decelerated from 10.0% in 2023 to 9.4% in 2024 due to tight monetary policy and lower import transportation costs, although inflation in services spiked to 21.8% following increases in electricity and gas tariffs. These figures underscore that economic performance improved even as certain regulated prices rose.

Table 1. Macroeconomic indicators and competition context in Uzbekistan (2023–2024) [2]

Indicator	2023	2024	Source and notes [2]
Real GDP growth (%)	6.3	6.5	Growth accelerated due to expansion in industry and services.
Industry growth (%)	6.4	6.8	Reflects demand for construction materials, petrochemicals and textiles.
Services growth (%)	7.1	7.7	Growth driven by accommodation, food services, transportation and storage.
Agriculture growth (%)	4.1	3.6	Slowed due to weaker gains in wheat and livestock.
Private consumption growth (%)	7.0	9.0	Household consumption rose as inflation slowed and remittances increased.
Investment growth (%)	23.4	27.6	Surge in private and public investment.
Headline inflation (%)	10.0	9.4	Tight monetary policy and lower transport costs reduced inflation.
Inflation for food (%)	12.1	8.0	Food inflation fell as transport costs moderated.
Inflation for other goods (%)	8.5	6.9	Reduced due to lower import costs.
Inflation for services (%)	8.2	21.8	Surge due to increases in regulated electricity and natural gas tariffs.

This table shows that Uzbekistan's economic expansion coincided with moderated inflation and significant investment. Nevertheless, the spike in service prices highlights the impact of administered tariffs. Economic thinking suggests that while temporary price adjustments may be necessary for fiscal sustainability, long-term rational behavior requires transparent pricing and competition in utility sectors.

Despite the tools of economic thinking, human decisions often deviate from rational benchmarks. Loss aversion causes individuals to weigh potential losses more heavily than equivalent gains, leading to risk-averse or risk-seeking behavior depending on framing. Present bias results in undervaluing future benefits, affecting savings and investment choices. Social preferences drive individuals to consider fairness, altruism and social norms, sometimes at odds with self-interest [5]. These biases challenge the assumption that individuals always maximize expected utility.

Rational decisions require timely and accurate information about prices, quality and future conditions. In many markets, information asymmetry persists: sellers may know more about product quality than buyers, and complex financial products may obscure risks [6]. Digital technologies and online platforms can improve transparency but may also facilitate price discrimination or collusion if not properly regulated.

Economic thinking provides a powerful set of tools for rational behavior in modern society. By understanding scarcity, opportunity cost, marginal analysis and incentives, individuals and organisations can make better decisions under uncertainty. Yet rationality is bounded by cognitive biases, information gaps and institutional constraints. Competition plays a critical role in aligning private incentives with social welfare: it encourages innovation, lowers prices and enhances quality. However, competition policy must focus on maintaining the competitive process rather than imposing price outcomes. Empirical evidence from Uzbekistan shows that economic growth has accelerated and inflation has moderated amid ongoing reforms, but challenges remain in reducing state intervention and fostering market-based pricing. Strengthening economic literacy, enhancing competition frameworks, liberalizing markets and incorporating behavioral insights can collectively promote rational behavior and sustainable economic development.

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REGIONAL DIFFERENTIATION OF ROUGH AND SUCCULENT FEED HARVESTING VOLUMES ACROSS MUNICIPAL DISTRICTS OF THE IRKUTSK REGION (2020–2024)

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Abstract. *The article presents the results of an analysis of the volumes of rough and succulent feed procurement in 28 municipal districts of the Irkutsk region for 2020–2024. The study uses data from departmental statistics on straw, hay, haylage, and silage, as well as the costs of their production. A stable inter-district differentiation has been revealed: three districts (Usolsky, Ziminsky, Nukutsky) account for 34% (2024) to 45% (2020) of the regional feed volume. The unit cost of feedstuff ranges from 43 rubles per centner (hay, Alarsky District, 2020) to 1,572 rubles per centner (hay, Ust-Ilimsky District, 2022). In five districts, the procurement of certain types of feed has been absent throughout the entire period. The dependence of livestock farming on imported feed grain (22.8 thousand tons in 2024) is noted, alongside the complete absence of interregional imports of rough and succulent feeds.*

Keywords: *feed procurement, Irkutsk region, regional differentiation, feed cost, rough feed, succulent feed, haylage, silage.*

Introduction

The sustainability of livestock farming in regions characterized by a continental climate and an extensive agricultural structure is determined by the availability of locally produced rough and succulent feeds. Disruptions in feed procurement or a high dependence on imported feeds increase the production costs of livestock.

The Irkutsk region is classified as a risk-prone agricultural zone. The region possesses significant areas of agricultural land; however, the volumes of feed procurement in municipal districts differ by several tens of times. A quantitative assessment of this differentiation for the period since 2020 is lacking, which complicates managerial decision-making at the regional level.

The objective of this study is to quantitatively assess the inter-district differentiation in volumes and costs of procurement of straw, hay, haylage, and silage in the Irkutsk region from 2020 to 2024, as well as to identify districts with a sustained deficit of own feed resources.

Objects and Methods

The object of the study comprises 28 municipal districts of the Irkutsk region, for which departmental records of feed procurement are kept. The analysis encompasses the following indicators for the years 2020, 2021, 2022, 2023, and 2024:

- quantities of procured feed (centners) by four types: straw, hay, haylage, and silage;
- feed procurement costs (thousand rubles) by each type;
- calculated unit cost (rub./c), derived by dividing the costs by the quantities.

Data source – Department of Agriculture of the Irkutsk Region (departmental statistics).

Processing methods:

- calculation of average, minimum, and maximum values for each type of feed;
- grouping of municipal districts by gross procurement volume;
- calculation of the dynamics of 2024 relative to 2020 (in percentage);
- identification of municipal districts with zero values for specific feed types over a period of three or more consecutive years.

Data on livestock numbers and fodder crop yields were excluded from the analysis, as the study's objective is limited to assessing territorial differentiation in procurement volumes and costs.

Results

Total volumes of feed procurement in the Irkutsk Region. According to departmental statistics, in 2021 the Irkutsk Region procured: hay – 2,328 thousand centners, haylage – 1,748 thousand centners, silage – 1,798 thousand centners,

straw – 3.5 thousand centners. Comparison with data from 2020 indicates a reduction in volumes for all types of feed except straw (Table 1). The most significant decrease was recorded for silage.

Table 1 – Dynamics of feed procurement volumes in the Irkutsk Region, thousand centners

Feed type	2020	2021	2024	Change from 2020 to 2024, %
Hay	2,272.5	2,327.9	1,795.4	–21.0 %
Haylage	1,762.0	1,748.4	1,478.2	–16.1 %
Silage	2,424.3	1,797.6	1,703.2	–29.7 %
Straw	0	3.5	1.9	—
Total	6,458.8	5,877.4	4,978.7	–22.9 %

Source: authors' calculations based on the data of the Department of Agriculture of the Irkutsk Region.

The total volume of procurement of four types of feed decreased from 6,458.8 thousand centners in 2020 to 4,978.7 thousand centners in 2024 (–22.9%). The most significant decreases were observed in silage (–29.7%) and hay (–21.0%).

Leading and lagging districts. Throughout the entire period, five districts accounted for over 40% of the regional volume of rough and succulent feed procurement: Usolsky, Ziminsky, Nukutsky, Bayandaevsky, and Ekhirit-Bulagatsky. In 2024, the Usolsky district accounted for 3,742 thousand centners (21.7% of the procurement of these feed types in the region), Ziminsky district – 1,122 thousand centners (6.5%), and Nukutsky district – 1,063 thousand centners (6.2%). In specific years (2020–2021), the combined share of three districts reached 45%, but by 2024 it decreased to 34%.

The opposite group comprises districts with zero or near-zero volumes of procurement for certain types of feed (Table 2). In Kazachinsko-Lensky, Nizhneilimsky, Slyudyansky, and Chunsky districts, no centners of haylage or silage were procured during the five-year period. Hay procurement in these districts is also absent, except for isolated insignificant volumes recorded in 2020 in Kazachinsko-Lensky district – 23 centners. In the five aforementioned districts, straw procurement (where present) combined with zero volumes of hay, haylage, and silage paradoxically results in a statistical representation of feed production despite the actual absence of a forage base for ruminants.

The presence of straw harvesting with zero volumes of hay, haylage, and silage in four districts indicates the absence of specialized feed production. In these cases, straw is most likely a by-product of grain cultivation and is not used as a complete feed.

Table 2 – Municipal Districts of the Irkutsk Region with zero procurement volumes of specific feed types in 2020–2024

District	Straw	Hay	Haylage	Silage
Kazachinsko-Lensky	is procured	0	0	0
Nizhneilimsky	0	0	0	0
Slyudyansky	0	0	0	0
Chunsky	0	0	0	0
Kachugsky	is procured	0	0	0

Cost analysis. The cost per unit of feed demonstrates extreme variability (Table 3). The minimum value among verified data was recorded for hay in Alarsky district in 2020. – 43 rubles per centner (costs of 10,690 thousand rubles for 249,354 centners). The maximum – for hay in the Ust-Ilimsk municipal district in 2022: 1,572 rubles per centner (costs of 2,726 thousand rubles for 1,734 centners).

In the Kirensky district (classified among the northern territories of the region), the cost of hay exceeded 900 rubles per centner for three consecutive years (2020–934 rubles per centner, 2021–662 rubles per centner, 2022–981 rubles per centner). For comparison: in the Bokhansky district, the cost of hay in 2021 amounted to 15 rubles per centner.

Table 3 – Extreme values of the production cost of rough and succulent feeds in selected municipal districts of the Irkutsk region (RUB/centner)

Feed type	District (year)	Production cost, RUB/centner	Contrasting district (year)	Production cost, RUB/centner
Hay	Ust-Ilimsky (2022)	1 572	Alarsky (2020)	43
Haylage	Ust-Ilimsky (2023)	945	Bokhansky (2021)	80
Silage	Kirensky (2024)	1 045	Bokhansky (2021)	90
Straw	Ust-Kutsky (2024)	896	(no data)	—

Procurement structure of rough and succulent feeds by districts. The procurement structure varies considerably. In the Usolsky district, silage predominates (2,063 thousand centners in 2024, accounting for 55% of all district feeds) followed by haylage (1,452 thousand centners, 39%). In the Ziminsky district, haylage (380 thousand centners) and silage (259 thousand centners) constitute the primary components, with insignificant volumes of hay. In the Bayandaevsky district during 2020–2023, hay prevailed (up to 904 thousand centners), but in 2024, hay

harvesting ceased, with only silage harvesting maintained (122 thousand centners). Such a structural shift indicates a potential change in livestock specialization or a loss of the fodder base.

In five districts (Angarsky, Zhigalovsky, Olkhonsky, Slyudyansky, Chunsky), not a single centner of silage was harvested over the five-year period.

Procurement of feed from other regions. According to the accompanying information, in 2024 agricultural enterprises of the region procured 22.8 thousand tons of feed grain. For 2026, approximately 10.0 thousand tons are planned. Rough and succulent feeds are not imported from other regions. The deficit of hay, haylage, and silage in the lagging districts is not compensated by external supplies.

Discussion

The obtained data indicate a stable, long-term differentiation in the procurement of rough and succulent feeds across the districts of the Irkutsk region. The causes of differences can be categorized into three groups.

1. Natural and climatic factors. The districts of the Angara basin (Usolsky, Irkutsky) are located within a more favorable moisture regime. Northern and north-eastern districts (Kirensky, Kazachinsko-Lensky, Nizhneilimsky) are characterized by a harsher climate and a shorter growing season, which objectively constrains feed procurement.

2. Technological factors. The variability in cost price (a difference exceeding 35-fold between the minimum and maximum values for hay) indicates differing technological practices. Low production costs in the Alarsky and Bokhansky districts are achieved through herd concentration and the use of modern conservation techniques. High production costs in the Ust-Ilimsky administrative district and Kirensky district are associated with small volumes and high specific expenses for logistics (northern and remote districts).

3. Organizational factors. The complete absence of silage and haylage procurement in five districts over five years cannot be explained solely by natural factors. In these districts, livestock farming is either absent or relies exclusively on forage from natural pastures and purchased grain.

The absence of imports of rough and succulent feeds from other regions, alongside a 22.9% decline in local procurement over five years, suggests either a proportional reduction in livestock numbers or that the feed base was initially redundant. The reduction in purchased fodder grain from 22.8 thousand tons in 2024 to the planned 10.0 thousand tons in 2026, may indicate a further decrease in livestock pressure.

Comparison with data from other regions of Eastern Siberia (Krasnoyarsk Krai, Republic of Buryatia) is complicated by the lack of publications with comparable district-level detail for the years 2020–2024.

The obtained results are consistent with the conclusions of other researchers. Agafonov et al. [1] note that the efficiency of feed production directly depends

on the technologies applied for the cultivation of mixed crops, which explains the variation in the cost price of feeds between districts (ranging from 43 to 1572 rub./centner). Klyoshina, Klyoshin, and Buraev [2], based on the example of the Irkutsk region, demonstrated that existing feed procurement technologies are unevenly distributed across the territory, which is corroborated by the leading districts (Usolsky, Ziminsky) and the trailing districts (Kazachinsko-Lensky, Chunsky) identified in our study. Malygin, Kozub, and Alekseeva [3] link the level of feed consumption to a complex of technological and organizational factors – this same variability was manifested in our sample as a 35-fold disparity in the cost price of hay. Barkova and Kalinina [4] point to the dependence of regional livestock farming on external feed supplies; in the Irkutsk region, this dependence manifests itself through the procurement of fodder grain (22.8 thousand tons in 2024) in the absence of any imports of rough and succulent feeds. Yushkova et al. [5], who examined feeds in the Irkutsk region, also recorded inter-district differences in nutritional value, which indirectly confirms our grouping of districts based on the feed procurement structure. Soloshenko et al. [6] associate food independence with advancements in feed production; the reduction in procurement volumes by 22.9% over five years identified in our study poses direct risks to this independence. Anikienko and Savchenko [7] analyzed the feed base of dairy cattle breeding in the Irkutsk region and concluded it to be fragmented; our data indicate that five districts systematically do not procure haylage and silage, representing an extreme case of such fragmentation. Yanchenko, Shukhanov, and Golubev [8] emphasize the role of succulent feeds in balancing rations; the absence of silage procurement in five districts renders balanced nutrition in these territories impossible without procurement from external sources.

Conclusion

For the period 2020–2024, the volume of rough and succulent feed procurement in the Irkutsk region decreased by 22.9%. The reduction affected all types of feed. Inter-district differentiation remained: three districts (Usolsky, Ziminsky, Nukutsky) in 2024 concentrated 34% of the regional volume of rough and succulent feed procurement.

Five municipal districts (Kazachinsko-Lensky, Nizhneilimsky, Slyudyansky, Chunsky, Kachugsky) consistently do not harvest haylage and silage. Livestock production in these territories is entirely dependent on purchased fodder grain or is absent.

The cost of feed production varies from 43 to 1,572 rubles per centner. Such variability indicates the absence of unified technological standards for feed procurement.

The lack of interregional procurement of rough and succulent feeds amid a reduction in domestic production poses risks to livestock farming in the event of droughts or natural anomalies. It is advisable to develop a targeted support program for districts with a chronic deficit of domestic feed, including subsidies for the procurement of silage and haylage.

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ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR MITIGATING STAFF TURNOVER IN THE TOURISM INDUSTRY: AN ANALYSIS OF THE HOSPITALITY SECTOR¹

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Abstract. *The article examines the critical issue of high staff turnover in the hospitality sector of the Russian tourism industry, which reached 70% in 2025 alongside a concurrent staff shortage of 30%. This high volatility is primarily driven by the non-competitive wage levels of line personnel (who constitute up to 70% of the workforce) and the constrained financial capacity of hoteliers to increase remuneration due to the sector's low operational profitability.*

To analyze economic mechanisms aimed at reducing staff turnover in the hotel sector, evaluate the effectiveness of tools such as the establishment of corporate training centers and the reduction of insurance contribution rates, and formulate evidence-based proposals for enhancing human resources policy within the industry.

Keywords: *Staff Turnover, Hospitality Industry, Economic Mechanisms, Insurance Contributions, Corporate Training, Wage Competitiveness, Profitability, Labor Shortage, Tax Incentives, Human Capital.*

Introduction

The Russian hospitality sector is currently experiencing a systemic human resource crisis characterized by the dual phenomena of exceptionally high staff turnover and an acute shortage of labor. According to data released by the Russian Union of Travel Industry (RUTI) following the 2025 industry review, turnover rates in the hospitality and tourism sector approximate 70%, while the labor deficit has reached a critical threshold of 30% [1]. In absolute terms, of the 1.5 million individuals employed in the sector, approximately 450,000 positions remain unfilled.

¹ The article was prepared as part of the state assignment of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Bashkortostan

Furthermore, to accommodate the projected growth targets for the industry by 2030, an additional 300,000 specialists will be required, rendering the issue of staffing a primary constraint on the sector's sustainable development [2].

The primary driver of this situation is fundamentally economic: the base wage levels for line personnel – who represent up to 70% of the total workforce in the accommodation sector – are uncompetitive compared to alternative employment opportunities in other sectors of the national economy. Hotel operators, however, face significant fiscal constraints in addressing this wage gap. Payroll expenses constitute 60–65% of total operating costs for a typical hotel property, while the sector's EBITDA margin rarely exceeds 12–15%, with investment payback periods extending to 15–19 years [3].

This research aims to scientifically substantiate and develop economic mechanisms capable of resolving the inherent contradiction between the imperative to increase wages and the structural financial limitations of hospitality enterprises.

Methods

The methodological foundation of this research is grounded in a systemic approach to the analysis of economic relations in the sphere of personnel management within the hospitality industry. The study employs the following methods:

1. **Statistical Analysis:** Examination of labor market data for the hospitality sector for the period 2024–2025, including indicators of turnover dynamics, labor shortages, wage trends, and operational cost structures.

2. **Comparative Economic Analysis:** Evaluation of the cost-effectiveness of various staff retention models versus traditional recruitment and onboarding expenditures.

3. **Case Study Method:** Review of empirical data and implementation outcomes from corporate educational initiatives at leading Russian hotel operators, including Cronwell Hospitality Group, Mriya Resort & SPA, and Mantera Group.

4. **Regulatory Analysis:** Assessment of the legal and fiscal framework governing insurance premiums and tax incentives for priority sectors of the Russian economy.

The empirical base comprises data from the Russian Union of Travel Industry (RUTI), recruitment platforms (hh.ru, Avito Rabota), materials from industry strategic sessions, and peer-reviewed publications on human resource management in the hospitality sector.

Results and Discussion

1. The Economic Anatomy of the Hospitality Labor Crisis

An analysis of the current labor market reveals a structural imbalance between the demand for and supply of labor in the accommodation sector. According to hh.ru platform data, over 500,000 vacancies were posted in the tourism, hospitality, and restaurant sectors during the first three quarters of 2024, marking a 26% increase year-over-year. Critically, the hh-index (the ratio of CVs to vacancies) in

most regions of the Russian Federation stands at a mere 3.5, significantly below the normative range of 4.0 to 8.0, indicating a severe deficit of available candidates [4].

The demand surge is particularly acute for operational staff: vacancies for housekeeping personnel increased by 112%, waitstaff by 64%, and travel agents by 124% [5]. In large resort complexes on the Black Sea coast, staff shortages reached 20% during the 2024 high season, exacerbated by low levels of process automation and lagging wage growth.

Economic diagnostics point to the structural composition of hotel costs as the root cause. As noted by RUTI Vice-President Alexei Musakin, payroll accounts for up to 60–65% of hotel operating expenses, while EBITDA profitability remains constrained to 12–15% [3]. Under these parameters, a unilateral increase in wages without external fiscal relief or internal productivity gains inevitably erodes the already modest profitability margins of hotel operations. Despite a nominal 19% increase in advertised wages in the spring of 2024, the average income in hospitality (approximately 65,200 RUB) remains below the national market average (74,900 RUB) [2]. This gap perpetuates a vicious cycle: low wages drive high turnover, high turnover inflates recruitment and training costs, and inflated costs restrict the capacity for wage growth.

2. Corporate Educational Centers as an Economic Retention Mechanism

In response to the labor shortage, major hotel holding companies have begun developing proprietary educational centers, viewing investment in training as a strategic lever for reducing turnover. Empirical evidence suggests that in the hospitality sector, corporate training serves a dual function: standardizing service delivery and reducing the economic drag of staff churn.

Case studies from the Russian market illustrate the efficacy of this approach. In 2025, Cronwell Hospitality Group launched a dedicated training center to address both the quantitative shortage of staff and the qualitative deficit in practical graduate education. Similarly, the “Academy of Hospitality” at Mriya Resort & SPA in Crimea functions as an integrated development center facilitating career progression, while the “Mantera Academy,” established in 2024, operates as a continuous learning ecosystem focused on service excellence and internal mentorship.

The economic efficiency of corporate training centers manifests across several dimensions:

- **Cost Displacement:** With turnover at 70%, the cumulative direct costs of recruitment agencies, interviewing, and productivity loss during onboarding rival the investment required for a dedicated training infrastructure.

- **Revenue Uplift:** Enhanced staff qualifications correlate directly with guest satisfaction metrics and Revenue Per Available Room (RevPAR).

- **Career Path Transparency:** The existence of clear career trajectories – where a line-level employee can achieve supervisor status within 3–6 months – acts as a powerful retention anchor, mitigating the flight risk associated with perceived dead-end jobs.

Notably, only 15–20% of graduates from specialized tourism universities enter the industry, largely due to starting salary expectations. Corporate centers effectively bridge this gap by providing employer-specific curricula with a high practical component, reducing the cost of post-graduate remediation for employers.

3. Reduction of Insurance Contributions as a Macroeconomic Stabilizer

The second key economic mechanism identified is the reduction of the fiscal burden on the payroll fund through a decrease in insurance contribution rates. RUTI has consistently advocated for the extension of the preferential insurance rate of 7.6% (currently applied to the IT sector) to the hospitality industry. As of 2025, the sector operates under a reduced general rate of 15%, but further relief is deemed essential for structural transformation.

The economic rationale for this policy intervention is straightforward: the funds liberated by the reduction in fiscal burden are to be earmarked exclusively for increasing the base compensation of line personnel. Industry representatives argue that the differential saved via state concessions would be directly channeled into wages to surpass sectoral averages. With payroll comprising up to 55% of revenue for 3- to 5-star properties, even a marginal reduction in non-wage labor costs provides substantial fiscal space for salary adjustments.

Government Resolution No. 4125-r, dated December 27, 2025, which included tourism in the list of priority sectors eligible for a 15% insurance rate effective January 1, 2026, represents a critical first step in preventing a reversion to standard rates. However, a further reduction to 7.6% would unlock an estimated 10–15% increase in net take-home pay for line staff, a shift that would dramatically enhance the sector's competitiveness against industries with lower turnover thresholds.

Conclusions and Policy Recommendations

The conducted research confirms that the 70% turnover rate in the hospitality sector is not a cyclical fluctuation but a structural phenomenon driven by a fundamental economic contradiction: the necessity for wage growth versus the industry's low-margin financial reality. Traditional HR management tools have exhausted their potential in this environment, necessitating a complex intervention of fiscal and organizational innovation.

Based on the analysis, the following recommendations are proposed for the refinement of economic mechanisms aimed at reducing staff turnover:

1. Extension of the Preferential Insurance Rate (7.6%): The Government of the Russian Federation should extend the 7.6% insurance contribution rate to the accommodation sector, contingent upon the signing of sectoral agreements mandating the targeted allocation of 100% of the resulting savings toward increases in base wages for line-level employees.

2. Stimulus for Corporate Training Infrastructure: Implementation of a Public-Private Partnership (PPP) framework for educational centers, including

tax deductions for capital investments in training facilities and co-financing of training programs for operational staff through the “Tourism and Hospitality Industry” National Project budget.

3. Targeted Education Programs: Expansion of state-funded university places for hospitality specializations with mandatory tripartite agreements (Student – University – Employer). These agreements should stipulate a minimum three-year commitment to the sponsoring enterprise, with corresponding employer obligations regarding wage guarantees and career progression.

4. Network of Training Hotels: Establishment of regional “training hotel” facilities to ensure year-round practical preparation, allowing for early identification of motivated talent and significantly reducing the industry’s current expenditures on retraining academically qualified but practically unskilled graduates.

The implementation of these measures will establish a sustainable economic foundation for increasing wage competitiveness, reducing turnover, and consequently enhancing the overall quality and resilience of the Russian tourism and hospitality sector.

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ECONOMIC AND ORGANIZATIONAL MODELS OF THE FITNESS SERVICES MARKET DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. *The fitness services market in Russia has experienced significant transformations in recent years: the pandemic, the withdrawal of foreign brands, rising rent costs, and inflation. The models that were effective ten years ago (large all-inclusive clubs with annual subscriptions) are currently either faltering or require comprehensive restructuring. The author elucidates why trainers are increasingly transitioning to ‘workspace rental’ and how traditional clubs are being outcompeted by micro-studios and digital ecosystems.*

Keywords: *Fitness services, economic model, organizational model, sports services market, subscription-based membership, franchising, discount club, customer retention (LTV), hybrid fitness (offline+online), fitness club monetization, unit economics, regional fitness market.*

Introduction

Approximately ten years ago, opening a fitness club was a simpler endeavor. One would rent a basement, purchase a couple of treadmills and dumbbells, hire ‘large individuals’ as trainers – and the business would commence. Today, such an approach is no longer viable. The fitness services market in Russia, having undergone the boom of the 2000s and the shock caused by the pandemic, has advanced to a new level. Clients have become more demanding, capital investment horizons have extended, and competition has intensified.

We frequently encounter specialized terminology such as ‘monetization,’ ‘LTV retention,’ and ‘unit economics.’ However, underlying them is a fundamental question: how can one ensure that a client pays not for a mere formality, but for a tangible result, while avoiding losses on rental expenses? This article aims to focus on the primary models currently operational (or under significant strain).

Presentation of the main material

Do you recall ‘World Class’ and ‘Planet Fitness’ in their traditional formats? A large, three-story facility featuring a swimming pool, sauna, group classes, and a smoothie bar area. This is the ‘old-school’ model. The economic model here is simultaneously simple and alarming. The entry fee is substantial (in some cases, an annual subscription covers the rent for just one month), yet the expenses are enormous: 40–50% of revenue is consumed by rent and utilities.

The primary issue for these clubs today is the unprofitability of their square footage. Customers prefer to visit between 6 p.m. and 10 p.m., while at 10 a.m. the facility remains empty. The organizational model is based on a rigid hierarchy: manager, sales department, customer service department, and trainers treated as mere labor. Yes, trainers in such settings frequently operate on a commission basis from individual sessions and receive minimal compensation if they do not actively promote their services. This constitutes a significant challenge. This format remains viable only as long as there is an anchor tenant or an investor with substantial financial resources. In 2025, constructing a new traditional club ‘from scratch’ represents financial imprudence unless one owns the property.

Discount operators and 24-hour gyms: strategies for generating revenue from non-attending clients. This is the model that revolutionized the market approximately seven to eight years ago. The discussion pertains to formats such as ‘Fit-Curves’, ‘X-Fit’ within the ‘compact’ segment, alongside numerous independent 24/7 clubs. The economic model here is oriented towards optimization. Small premises (300–500 sq.m), minimal staff (a single administrator or solely an access chip at the entrance), no shower facilities or only very limited ones.

How do they sustain themselves? Through the effective formula of ‘low-cost membership fee combined with the forgotten card effect’. Individuals pay between 1500 and 2000 rubles per month. For a club to become profitable, it requires 50 people to attend simultaneously out of 1,000 who have purchased a gym membership. The remaining 950 pay ‘out of conscience’ or for the sake of a dream. The organizational model functions as a production line selling ‘hope.’ There is no costly coaching staff involved. The personnel consist of sales managers who process leads generated from social networks.

From a development perspective, this model has reached its ceiling. When the entry price falls below 1,000 rubles, random individuals begin to be attracted who damage equipment and write hostile reviews on Yandex.Maps. Additionally, there is an oversaturation of such venues in Moscow and St. Petersburg. Further expansion is only feasible in regions where people remain surprised that it is possible to visit a gym at three o’clock in the morning.

Franchising: a double-edged sword. It is necessary to discuss franchises separately. Within the fitness services market, this constitutes a distinct universe. Federal

chains offer a ‘happiness package’: brand, accounting system, manuals on floor cleaning, and guidance on how to ‘sell a dream.’ For a novice, this approach is safe. One does not have to devise the model oneself – simply implement it.

However, here lies the catch. The standard economic and organizational model of a franchisee presupposes that royalties and marketing fees severely erode profit margins. I have observed clubs where, despite revenues of 3 million, the franchisee’s net profit was only 200 thousand. The remainder was effectively absorbed by the ‘parent company’ for the brand name. And when a crisis occurs (such as in 2022 or following increases in equipment costs), the first action of prudent owners is to relinquish the brand and operate as ‘simply Vasily’s club.’ Does this approach prove effective? Yes, provided there is a strong personal brand of the manager and exceptional trainers. Otherwise, the club ceases operation.

Currently, there is a market trend toward ‘soft franchising’ or partnerships without royalty fees, limited solely to discounted equipment procurement. This indicates the maturing of the market.

Corporate model: fitness as a service for the workplace. At this point, it is pertinent to share an observation. The boom in remote work has undermined the B2B fitness segment. Previously, large factories and offices procured 300–500 memberships wholesale for their employees. Currently, it is easier for companies to provide compensation for sports activities than to establish contracts with specific clubs. The survivors were those who transitioned to the ‘personal trainer at the office’ model. Although it may seem costly, it is economically advantageous.

Organizational model: there is no need to lease a gym space. One arrives at the company’s conference room during lunch, lays out mats, and conducts ‘office yoga’ or ‘crossfit performed on chairs.’ Expenditures: trainer’s salary and transportation costs. Contract with a legal entity for outsourcing. Development in this area is driven by HR directors. If you are included in the pool of recommended suppliers for Gazprom or Sberbank, you hold a competitive advantage. Otherwise, you remain insignificant. The model is complex within the sales funnel but characterized by a very high price point (2–3 thousand per 45-minute session for 10 participants; for business, this is negligible).

Hybrid models and online services: in which direction is the trend moving? The 2020 pandemic achieved what the market had been unable to accomplish in 20 years – it legitimized home training. A successful fitness club today is not merely a gym. It encompasses a mobile application, a Telegram bot, a YouTube channel, and a ‘closed club’ within Sferum or Telegram.

According to certain authors: ‘...Innovative aspects of managing client behavior in the fitness services market constitute the foundation for developing the fitness services market strategy’ [1]. The economic model in this context is hybrid. There is a fixed cost associated with the ‘physical infrastructure’ (renting the facility for live training

sessions) and an almost negligible marginal cost for the digital version of the trainer (recorded training sessions). Organizationally, these function as two distinct companies within one entity: the IT department (or at minimum, an SMM manager) and the coaching division. For most clubs, these elements fail to effectively integrate. Coaches resist surveillance cameras, while IT specialists lack understanding of biomechanics.

I consider the future to be represented by the ‘subscription plus entry point’ model. An individual pays, for instance, 2000 rubles for access to a home workout library. If they wish to attend a live group class, they pay an additional 300 rubles as a one-time attendance fee. This undermines the traditional model of “freezes” and refunds. Unfortunately, standard CRM systems for fitness inadequately support this logic, which is why many resort to Excel workarounds and manual checks [3].

Organizational distortions: why do trainers resort to undeclared (“black”) salaries? Any economic model depends fundamentally on people. In the fitness sector, this role is played by the trainer. The classical exploitation model (where the trainer receives 30% of the session fee, and the club retains 70% for “facilities and utilities”) is becoming increasingly ineffective. Trainers rapidly calculate their earnings. They observe that if they rent a hall themselves in a basement for 500 rubles per hour and assemble a group of five people, they earn 5000 rubles per hour, compared to 1000 rubles in a club.

Consequently, progressive clubs are transitioning to a workplace rental model. A trainer pays the club a fixed rental fee per hour for the use of equipment (200–300 rubles). The trainer independently acquires clients and retains 100% of the revenue. The club transforms into a ‘platform’ and ceases to be burdened with employment issues, sick leave payments, and payroll taxes (a grey zone in legal terms, yet a market reality). This enables the club to grow without an overstaffed workforce. The organizational structure becomes flat: only a manager, cleaning personnel, and outsourced accounting.

Regional specificity: Moscow is not representative of Russia. A significant mistake made by metropolitan chains is entering regional markets with the same economic model as used in the capital. In Krasnodar or Voronezh, consumers will not pay for a heated swimming pool if there is a free sports facility at the stadium nearby. Purchasing power is lower, but the demand for higher-level service is greater [4].

The development model for the regions currently is the ‘fitness club’ (analogous to the Soviet cultural centers). Modest in appearance, yet sincere in essence. The principal cost element is not equipment (Chinese equivalents have become adequately reliable), but community management. The organizational model is constructed around a ‘social gathering space’. Clients pay not for the treadmill itself, but for the fact that Mrs. Lyuda knows everyone by name and provides tea with cookies following the stretching sessions. Marketing operates primarily through word-of-mouth.

There are cases where such a grassroots club generates more revenue than a premium one due to zero client turnover. Individuals attend it for five years. This justifies any intelligent investment in onboarding.

Conclusion

What is currently trending? The fitness services market has matured towards personalization. General-purpose gyms will cease to exist. Three models will survive:

1. Micro-studios (exclusively Pilates, exclusively shadow boxing) – low rent, narrow specialization, high fees justified by ‘expertise’.

2. Digital ecosystems integrated with a physical club (as described above, the hybrid model).

3. Clubs operating on a membership economy model (as in the USA: you pay \$50 annually for access rights, with training sessions paid for separately).

Most importantly, it is necessary to cease constructing complex financial models with projections spanning ten years. Currently, the market evolves every six months. Develop a flexible organizational model that allows for the swift dismissal of ineffective sales managers, replacement of CRM systems within two weeks, and rapid leasing of space in a nearby shopping center if displaced. Only then will your fitness business sustain itself. Reserve the elaborate multi-page ‘development roadmaps’ for investors who have never engaged in training. They prefer reviewing documents. Clients value the preservation of their health.

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**REGULATORY AND LEGAL FRAMEWORK OF CHINA'S
COSMETICS MARKET AS A FACTOR IN SHAPING BRAND
MARKETING STRATEGIES IN THE FIRST QUARTER
OF THE 21ST CENTURY**

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the regulatory and legal framework of the cosmetics market of the People's Republic of China (PRC) as a key factor in shaping the marketing strategies of local brands in the first quarter of the 21st century. Drawing on the cases of the brands Flower Knows and Perfect Diary, the article demonstrates how legislative prohibitions are implemented within marketing models grounded in aesthetics, emotional value, and cultural identity. The study concludes that the stringent regulatory environment, combined with digitalization – despite imposing certain restrictions – serves as a stimulus for the development and enhancement of the global competitiveness of the PRC beauty industry.*

Keywords: *China, beauty industry, color cosmetics, regulatory and legal framework.*

The beauty industry of the People's Republic of China demonstrated high growth dynamics in the first quarter of the 21st century, becoming one of the world's largest and most technologically advanced consumer markets. The success of Chinese cosmetics companies in both domestic and foreign markets is contingent upon a complex of factors, among which the regulatory and legal framework of the sector occupies a special position. The legislative framework, establishing requirements for product safety, the veracity of advertising claims, and consumer rights protection, shapes a competitive environment in which brands are required to adapt to constraints. The objective of this article is to identify the influence of the PRC's regulatory and legal framework in the sphere of cosmetic products on the formation of marketing strategies for local color cosmetics brands in the 21st century.

The foundation of legal regulation for the PRC cosmetics market comprises several key legislative acts, each defining specific parameters for manufacturers' marketing communications. The most significant document in this domain is the Advertising Law of the People's Republic of China, the latest revision of which came into force in 2015 with subsequent amendments [1]. This law establishes several fundamental restrictions that directly influence the promotional strategies of cosmetic brands.

First, Article 4 of the Law imposes full responsibility on the advertiser for the accuracy of the information provided, and Article 9 prohibits the use of superlative degrees of comparison. This provision precludes the possibility of comparative advertising and compels Chinese brands to seek alternative means of demonstrating competitive advantage – through an emphasis on aesthetics, the emotional value of the product, and the creation of a unique visual image. Second, Article 17 of the Law prohibits cosmetic brands from using medical terminology and making claims about “therapeutic” properties of products without corresponding clinical evidence. This provision addresses a historically entrenched issue within the PRC market, where skincare and color cosmetic products were often positioned as medicinal preparations. The prohibition incentivizes companies to invest in scientific research and laboratory collaborations to substantiate any functional claims, which, in the long term, contributes to enhancing product quality and consumer trust. Third, Article 38 of the Law requires advertising representatives, including Key Opinion Leaders (KOLs) and live-stream hosts, to have personal experience using the advertised product and holds them liable for the accuracy of the information provided. Given the role of KOLs in the PRC e-commerce system (over 34% of consumers acknowledge that the popularity of opinion leaders significantly influences their purchasing decisions [2]), this regulation elevates the level of trust in recommendations and compels brands to approach partner selection with greater scrutiny.

The provisions of the Advertising Law are supplemented and specified by the Law of the People's Republic of China on the Protection of Consumer Rights and Interests, as amended in 2024. The most significant innovations for the beauty industry are found in Articles 9 and 14. Article 9 prohibits the creation of false product popularity through fake reviews and fictitious transactions, thereby affecting the reputational strategies of brands on social networks and marketplaces. Article 14 imposes an obligation on live-streaming platforms (e.g., Taobao Live, Douyin) to retain broadcast recordings and facilitate the resolution of consumer disputes. The legal codification of platform liability enhances the transparency and security of online commerce, which is particularly crucial given the rapid growth of live-streaming's share in cosmetics sales [3].

The technical regulation directly governing the product itself is the “Measures for the Administration of Cosmetics Labeling,” issued by the National Medical

Products Administration (NMPA) of the PRC and effective from 2022. Articles 8 and 19 of this document prohibit the use of medical terminology and false descriptions. A key requirement stipulated in Article 12 is the mandatory disclosure of the full list of ingredients on the packaging, listed in descending order of concentration. This provision has led to shifts in product development and brand communication strategies: companies have begun to emphasize key active components (e.g., hyaluronic acid, niacinamide, retinol) and their precise concentration, thereby contributing to the growth of consumer literacy and the formation of a culture of conscious consumption [4].

Taken together, the examined normative acts establishes a predictable and transparent regulatory environment. On one hand, it imposes stringent boundaries on marketing activities; on the other, it mitigates operational risks and stimulates investment in innovation and product quality.

Beyond direct legislative restrictions, the consistent state policy aimed at stimulating domestic consumption and supporting high-tech industries exerts a considerable influence on the development of the PRC beauty industry. As outlined in the 2024 Report on the Work of the Government of the PRC, a key objective is the “comprehensive expansion of domestic demand,” with consumption viewed as a “stabilizing anchor” for economic growth [5]. Specific measures include the allocation of 300 billion yuan from ultra-long-term special treasury bonds to support consumer goods renewal programs, which indirectly stimulates the cosmetics market as well. The policy direction toward “supporting innovation in the private sector,” “accelerating the building of a Digital China,” and “stimulating the innovative vitality of the digital economy,” as articulated in state programmatic documents, creates a favorable institutional and infrastructural environment for the development of the beauty industry. The advancement of e-commerce and the adoption of big data technologies, artificial intelligence, and live-streaming occur within the framework of nationwide digitalization strategies, thereby affording local cosmetic brands access to cutting-edge marketing tools.

An additional impetus for the qualitative growth of the sector is provided by export support policies. The “Action Plan for Promoting the High-Quality Development of Services Outsourcing” (2025), jointly issued by the Ministry of Commerce and other departments, aims to cultivate a cohort of “leading service outsourcing enterprises competitive on an international level” [6]. The expansion of Chinese cosmetic brands into overseas markets is proceeding in alignment with the overall state strategy for diversifying and expanding high-tech service exports. Thus, while the regulatory and legal framework and state policy impose constraints, they also act as stimulants for the development of local brands.

The legislative and policy factors discussed above have a direct impact on the formation of marketing strategies for Chinese cosmetic companies. An analysis

of the activities of two leading local color cosmetics brands – Flower Knows and Perfect Diary – allows for the tracing of how regulatory constraints are realized in specific marketing decisions.

The brand Flower Knows, established in 2016, constructs its positioning on an aesthetic inspired by European fairy tales and art. The brand’s slogan – “Live your Fairytales” – shifts the emphasis from the functional characteristics of the product to its symbolic and emotional significance [7]. This approach is a direct consequence of the legislative prohibition on the use of superlative degrees and false efficacy claims. Instead of aggressive advertising, Flower Knows offers the consumer a holistic aesthetic experience, wherein packaging design and the visual concept of collections become key elements of the value proposition. Compliance with labeling requirements is manifested in the transparency of product composition information: on the brand’s official website, ingredients are listed in English in descending order of concentration, including natural components (rose extract, cherry blossom extract, camellia oil). The absence of animal testing aligns with the global trend toward ethical consumption.

The pricing policy of Flower Knows positions the brand within the premium segment for Chinese cosmetics; however, the price point remains lower than that of Western premium analogues, providing a competitive advantage. It is important to note that the brand actively utilizes digital promotional tools allowed under current legislation: collaboration with KOLs (e.g., Tuanzi Kun_Alice, Yao Yaoshuo, Viya, Li Jiaqi), live-streaming on platforms such as Taobao and Xiaohongshu, as well as big data technologies for analyzing the effectiveness of advertising campaigns and adjusting strategy. Consequently, legislative restrictions have stimulated Flower Knows to develop innovative, trust- and aesthetics-based marketing approaches, garnering the brand recognition both in the domestic market (first place in the “local brand cosmetics stores” category on Tmall) and abroad (400% sales growth in the USA from 2023–2024) [8].

The brand Perfect Diary, founded in 2017 by parent company Yatsen Holding, demonstrates its adaptive strategy within the existing legal framework. The company’s mission – “developing high-quality, creative, and amazing products so that everyone can easily express themselves and highlight their beauty” [9] – reflects an aspiration to forge an emotional connection with the consumer. A key element of Perfect Diary’s marketing strategy has been its appeal to guochao – the national wave of popularizing Chinese cultural values among the younger generation. Collaborations with the China Aerospace Science and Technology Corporation, the National Geographic Museum of China, and the release of New Year collections in a traditional red-and-gold palette featuring zodiac symbols enable the brand to cultivate cultural identity and audience loyalty within boundaries that do not contravene advertising legislation [10].

The social and environmental responsibility professed by Perfect Diary (charitable projects for animal protection, eco-certification of packaging) aligns with global sustainable development trends and contributes to fostering the image of a “responsible brand,” thereby enhancing consumer trust within a context of stringent regulation. The brand’s official website and WeChat store display the cosmetics production license and information on trademark validity, a consequence of the information disclosure requirements enshrined in consumer protection legislation.

Perfect Diary actively employs digital promotional tools that are permitted and even encouraged by state digitalization policy: collaboration with KOLs (including actress Zhou Xun), live-streaming, email marketing, and personalized offers. The application of big data technologies for audience analysis and content adaptation also aligns with the nationwide course toward developing the digital economy. High operational metrics – including an average order dispatch time of 7 hours, customer service response time of 17 seconds, and a product rating of 4.89 out of 5 based on 196,000 reviews – demonstrate the effectiveness of the adopted strategy within the established regulatory framework [11].

The analysis conducted leads to the conclusion that the regulatory and legal framework of the PRC cosmetics market in the first quarter of the 21st century, while restrictive in nature, also exerts a stimulating influence on the formation of local brand strategies. Stringent legislative requirements concerning the veracity of advertising claims, transparency of product composition information, and consumer rights protection have compelled Chinese companies to abandon aggressive comparative and unsubstantiated claims in favor of strategies grounded in the creation of emotional value, aesthetics, cultural identity, and trust. State policy aimed at stimulating domestic consumption and digitalizing the economy has created a favorable institutional environment for the development of innovative marketing tools – live-streaming, collaborations, and the utilization of big data and artificial intelligence. Local brands such as Flower Knows and Perfect Diary have successfully adapted to the regulatory constraints. The experience of the PRC demonstrates that a well-conceived and systematic regulatory and legal framework, combining product quality and safety control with support for innovation and digital transformation, can stimulate the qualitative growth of the national beauty industry and enhance its global competitiveness.

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MODEL OF TOURISM INDUSTRY DEVELOPMENT THROUGH COOPERATION: INTERACTION OF KEY SECTORS, ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE KAMCHATKA KRAI

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Abstract. *This article examines the system of stakeholder interaction for the effective regional development of the tourism industry. The participants include the government, business communities, and tourists themselves. The article analyzes the theoretical foundations of this approach and its practical application in the Kamchatka region. It also highlights the system of public-private partnership and the conceptual model of financial interaction between the elements of an investment project. The article presents an analysis of the dynamics of tourist flows from 2020 to 2024, based on key indicators of tourism industry development. A SWOT analysis of the tourism industry in the Kamchatka Territory is conducted. Strategic directions are identified to overcome existing barriers (seasonality, infrastructure, and logistics issues). Special attention is given to the need to diversify tourism offerings, attract investments, and create competitive tourism products based on sustainable development principles and effective cooperation among all stakeholders.*

Keywords: *tourism, public-private partnership, stakeholders, sustainable development, tourist flow, tourism potential, SWOT analysis.*

Introduction.

The relevance of this study stems from the fact that the tourism industry plays a unique role in socioeconomic development as a cross-cutting sector that impacts all areas of the economy, regional characteristics, and human capital. The development of tourism reflects societal demand, contemporary trends, and new technologies, and contributes to improving the quality of life for the population within the country. Many different challenges have been identified for the development of the tourism industry, the resolution of which requires the collaboration of all stakeholders: the government, the business sector, tourists, academia, and the workforce.

Scientific interest in the interaction between these spheres is reflected in a wide range of studies that analyze various tools for effective interaction and cooperation. Mechanisms and models for interaction are being developed, but in a rapidly changing world, these concepts need to be updated.

Economic interests represent the orientation of economic activity toward maintaining or improving the socioeconomic status of economic actors. This orientation is achieved by meeting the needs of both the internal and external environments. The status of economic interest holders within the system of socioeconomic relations is a determining factor in the formation and realization of these interests. This study describes several models of stakeholder interaction that reflect the phased improvement of systems. Initially, the state, private, and nonprofit sectors interacted; subsequently, a social model and Public-Private Partnership (next – PPP) investment projects were formed, through which large-scale investment projects are created.

Materials and Methods

The scientific, theoretical, and methodological foundation of this study was based on domestic and international research in the field of stakeholder systems and PPP as they relate to tourism.

Results and Discussion.

The approach to stimulating investment in the development of the tourism industry is designed to address a range of challenges: reducing the country's balance of payments deficit, strengthening support for investors directing their investments toward regional development, leveraging a variety of supporting instruments, revitalizing cluster activities, and assisting investors in technology transfer.

This development is possible through the tripartite interaction of «stakeholder theory» [2, p. 153], which asserts that long-term success in any industry is possible only through the systematic consideration of the interests of all stakeholders. This approach requires a constant balance between economic efficiency, social justice, and environmental sustainability. The triadic approach is also complemented by the theory of PPP, which describes in detail the mechanisms of risk allocation, the integration of regulatory and market instruments, as well as the specifics of

long-term investments. The concept of tourism clusters adds value by emphasizing the importance of concentrating resources and forming value chains, as well as the «triple helix» model, adapted to tourism, where science acts not merely as an expert but as a key driver of innovation – from the development of environmental standards to the implementation of modern digital solutions.

In this complex system, the state plays a multifaceted and decisive role. As a regulator, it establishes the legal framework, including the Federal Law «On the Fundamentals of Tourism in the Russian Federation», which protects tourists' rights to recreation and safety, and sets quality standards and competition rules for the market. The state is also actively working to create favorable conditions for business development and supports international and interregional cooperation in the tourism sector [6, p. 2735]. For example, businesses in Kamchatka benefit from the preferential regimes of the Advanced Development Zones (ADZs) and the Free Port of Vladivostok. These regimes have enabled residents to implement more than 270 business initiatives with a total investment exceeding 160 billion rubles [8 el. res.].

As an investor, the government is investing in the development of key infrastructure projects, specifically transportation systems, environmental initiatives, and tourism infrastructure. For example, in 2022, as part of the national project «Tourism and Hospitality Industry», the region received a subsidy of approximately 300 million rubles. These funds made it possible to support 54 small and medium-sized businesses in the industry. A total of 600 million rubles, including co-financing, was allocated to the creation of new recreational sites, the improvement of the local area, the modernization of facilities, and the development of new tourism products.

Its marketing function includes actively promoting national and regional tourism brands in both domestic and international markets. In addition, the state acts as a defender of citizens' interests by ensuring the safety of tourists, preserving cultural heritage (in accordance with the Federal Law «On Cultural Heritage Sites»), and protecting the environment (in accordance with the Federal Law «On Environmental Protection»). These legal foundations for the state's activities are enshrined at various levels, including the Constitution of the Russian Federation, ensuring the stability of the industry and the preservation of national values.

The business, in turn, performs key operational functions within the tourism sector. It offers a wide range of services, including lodging, transportation, dining, and entertainment. The main tasks of the business sector are to develop new markets for tourism products, ensure strict compliance with current legislation, and provide the necessary information to government agencies and national statistics offices regarding its activities, measures, and the extent of government support, as well as tourist flows. The private sector actively implements innovative technologies to improve service quality, invests in infrastructure development, and creates new jobs, thereby stimulating local economic growth.

The local community, including both residents and tourists, also plays a key role. It shapes demand and sets service quality standards, participates in the preservation of cultural heritage through involvement in local tourism, and exercises public oversight through reviews and ratings, which serves as a powerful incentive for the continuous improvement of service quality in the industry.

The company is also actively involved in the development of the tourism industry through the implementation of social initiatives. For example, in 2024, the Kamchatka Krai implemented programs offering free social tours for combat veterans and children of military personnel, as well as free helicopter tours to the Valley of Geysers for 11th-grade graduates, which promotes social inclusion and raises the region's profile.

Main Section. The sustainable development of the tourism industry is based on several key partnership models, each of which plays a vital role in creating an effective and balanced ecosystem. The first model is the tripartite partnership [1, p. 101–120], which includes the public, private, and nonprofit sectors. In this model, the government is responsible for establishing the regulatory framework and developing the infrastructure that provides the necessary conditions for the tourism industry to function. The private sector is responsible for diversifying services and introducing innovations, thereby increasing the appeal of destinations for travelers. Non-profit organizations also play an important role, focusing on the preservation of cultural and natural heritage, which ensures the long-term sustainability of tourism clusters.

The next model is based on social partnership [4, p. 81], involving the active engagement of local communities in the decision-making process and promoting the development of socially responsible tourism. This approach not only generates economic returns but also improves residents' quality of life while preserving their traditions and cultural identity.

The third model is a PPP, which combines government resources and business expertise to implement large-scale tourism initiatives (Figure 1).

Source: Compiled by the author, based on [7, p. 79].

Figure 1. Conceptual model of financial interactions among the components of a public-private partnership investment project.

The key advantage of this model lies in the balanced distribution of risks and areas of responsibility among partners, which is crucial when launching large-scale projects. Thanks to PPPs, investment in tourism infrastructure is being attracted more actively and cutting-edge technologies are being implemented, which directly impacts service quality and strengthens the region's competitive position in the market.

The use of these partnership models allows for a comprehensive approach to addressing challenges in the tourism sector, ranging from the construction of infrastructure facilities to initiatives for the preservation of cultural heritage.

This approach creates a sustainable ecosystem for tourism development that fosters economic growth and social progress while ensuring a balance of interests among all stakeholders.

An analysis of the current situation shows that the dynamics of tourist flows in the Kamchatka Krai for the period 2020–2024 demonstrate significant progress in the development of the tourism industry. According to data for 2024, the region's tourism sector was experiencing an intense boom, made possible by an increase in the number of tour operators, a rise in the number of accommodation facilities, and growth in the number of professional staff (Figure 2).

Source: Compiled by the author based on data from [9. el. r.].

Figure 2. Trends in tourist arrivals in the Kamchatka Krai for the period 2020–2024, in persons.

According to the findings presented in Figure 2, the number of tourists visiting the Kamchatka Territory has shown impressive growth, rising from 91,486 in 2020 to 406,565 in 2024. This more than fourfold increase (approximately 344%) over such a short period underscores not only the region's high and continuously developing potential but also the effectiveness of measures taken to promote it, as well as the growing interest in Kamchatka as a unique tourist destination.

The data for the Kamchatka Territory for 2018–2023 presented in Table 1 demonstrate positive changes in the tourism sector. An analysis of tourist flow volumes and financial indicators confirms the sector's sustainable development and underscores the importance of partnerships between the government, business, and society in this process.

Table 1 – Indicators of Tourism Development in the Kamchatka Region.

Key indicators	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Number of travel agencies that provided information on tourism activities, units	85	78	67	103	112	114
Number of tour packages sold to the public, units	13 494	12 817	6 167	8 655	11 894	13 095
Cost of tour packages sold to the public, million rubles	1 427,8	1 465,2	472,2	1 027,5	1 383,3	1 721,0
Funds received from sales of tourism products (net of VAT, excise taxes, and similar mandatory payments), million rubles	999,6	749,9	472,4	1 347,2	1 488,3	1 910,3
Paid services to the public, million rubles	30 303,1	32 039,1	29 179,5	31 160,9	31 603,1	33 409,9
of which:						
tourism	736,0	734,3	441,9	745,0	924,0	1 011,7
physical culture and sports	290,2	293,6	217,5	281,6	363,6	356,3
hotels and similar accommodation facilities	458,3	469,7	446,0	707,8	966,0	1 175,9
specialized collective accommodation facilities	211,9	232,1	94,5	90,7	100,4	110,8
of which: health resorts	42,4	47,0	17,3	22,8	30,7	26,4
culture	461,8	460,8	227,6	247,2	273,3	312,4

Source: Compiled by the author based on data from [10, p.10].

The data presented in Table 1 show that, despite a decline during the 2020 pandemic, the number of travel agencies had recovered by 2023 and even exceeded pre-pandemic levels, reaching 114. This indicates market stability and the emergence of new participants. The volume of travel packages sold also shows a recovery following a sharp decline in 2020, approaching pre-pandemic levels (13,095 units in 2023 compared to 13,494 in 2018). However, the value of sold tour packages and revenue from tourism services show more impressive growth, significantly exceeding the figures for 2018–2019 (1,721.0 million rubles and 1,910.3 million rubles in 2023, respectively). This trend may indicate both an increase in the average spend per tour and an overall increase in industry revenue, possibly due to the offering of more expensive or comprehensive services.

Paid tourism services for the general public are also showing steady growth, reaching 1,011.7 million rubles in 2023, which is significantly higher than the 2018 level (736.0 million rubles). Positive trends are also observed in the cultural, sight-seeing, and sports tourism segment, where the volume of services in 2023 amounted to 356.3 million rubles, exceeding pre-pandemic levels. Particularly noteworthy is the growth in the «Tourism and Exhibition Accommodation» category, where revenue by 2023 more than doubled compared to 2018 (1,175.9 million rubles versus 458.3 million rubles), indicating significant investment and development of accommodation infrastructure. However, it is worth noting that the number of specialized group accommodation facilities and health resorts has not yet fully recovered to 2018–2019 levels following a significant decline in 2020–2021, which may indicate a need for structural changes or targeted support for these segments.

Conclusion. Overall, the data presented confirm the strong positive growth of the tourism industry in the Kamchatka Territory. There has been not only a quantitative increase in tourist arrivals but also a significant rise in the economic returns from tourism. The data presented above and the analysis of the current situation allow us to systematize the key factors influencing the development of the tourism industry in the Kamchatka Territory within the framework of a SWOT analysis (Table 2).

Table 2 – SWOT Analysis of the Tourism Industry in the Kamchatka Territory

Strengths	Weaknesses
Unique natural and cultural potential; Steady growth in tourist traffic (344% from 2020–2024) and economic indicators; Government support (priority development areas, the Free Port of Vladivostok, national projects, grants); Development of key infrastructure (new airport, subsidized flights); Expansion of the number of tour operators and accommodation facilities.	High transport accessibility and travel costs; Underdeveloped tourism infrastructure outside the main centers; Pronounced seasonality of the industry; Natural risks (seismic activity, unpredictable weather); The problem of unorganized tourism and uneven distribution of traffic.
Opportunities	Threats
Significant increase in airport capacity (up to 1.5 million passengers per year); launch of subsidized flights; development of ground infrastructure (road to Khalaktyrsky Beach); creation of large all-season resorts (Three Volcanoes Park); expansion of social tourism programs; diversification of tourism products to smooth out seasonality (balneological, business).	Insufficient investment in infrastructure, lagging behind growing demand; deteriorating environmental conditions due to uncontrolled tourism; geopolitical and macroeconomic risks; natural disasters that could damage infrastructure and reputation.

Source: Compiled by the author

This SWOT analysis shows that, despite significant internal strengths and favorable opportunities, the region faces a number of serious constraints and potential risks. To ensure sustainable growth and overcome these challenges, it is crucial to deepen synergistic cooperation between the government, business, and society. Key prospects for the development of the tourism industry in the Kamchatka Territory are linked to addressing the identified issues and include improving transportation accessibility, which will be achieved through the opening of a new passenger terminal at Petropavlovsk-Kamchatsky (Elizovo) on March 31, 2025, capable of handling up to 1.5 million passengers per year. In addition, in September 2025, subsidized flight programs from Kamchatka to Vladivostok at reduced prices (ranging from 9,000 to 12,000 rubles) were launched, which should significantly improve pricing dynamics, increase domestic tourism, and make the region more accessible. The completion of the paved road to Khalaktyrsky Beach in 2025 will also contribute to the development of ground infrastructure, facilitating access to one of the most popular natural attractions. Addressing the shortage of quality housing and mitigating seasonal fluctuations involves the creation of large, year-round resorts, particularly as part of the «Three Volcanoes Park» project, which is expected to become a key element of the new tourism infrastructure.

There are already successful examples of cooperation that demonstrate the potential of this approach. These include projects implemented as part of the national «Tourism and Hospitality» initiative in 2022, which supported dozens of small and medium-sized enterprises and contributed to the creation of new recreational areas. Private-sector initiatives, such as grant support for individual entrepreneur Ivan Zybin's project to develop a beach on Lake Tolmacheva [5, el. r.] – including campgrounds, a dining hall, and restroom facilities – also demonstrate the potential of small and medium-sized enterprises in developing local infrastructure and enhancing the tourist experience. The further development of the tourism industry in the Kamchatka Territory requires a comprehensive approach. Therefore, the key drivers of growth should be attracting investment through PPP mechanisms to upgrade infrastructure, creating conditions for year-round recreation, the digital transformation of services, and investments in workforce training. Particular attention should be paid to promoting eco-friendly and culture-oriented tourism, as well as strengthening the region's international brand.

It is worth noting that the region's unique natural and cultural potential serves as the foundation for the development of the tourism sector. However, realizing this potential depends directly on the region's ability to overcome infrastructure and administrative barriers. Achieving sustainable growth that is accessible to all segments of the population is possible only through close cooperation between the government, business, and society, supported by the

implementation of innovations. Only through joint efforts can the region's prosperity be ensured, tourists be attracted, and its natural wealth be preserved for future generations.

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TONE AND FRAMING IN REGIONAL ONLINE MEDIA NEWS AND AUDIENCE REACTION

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Abstract. *This article examines the relationship between tone and framing of regional online media news and audience reactions in digital distribution channels. This research is relevant given the shift in editorial competition toward platform-based metrics and the growing importance of the emotional packaging of news messages for clicks, reading, commenting, and sharing. Its novelty lies in the combination of frame typologies and computational approaches to their identification with applied engagement metrics used in regional media practice. The paper describes the mechanisms of transition from lexical-semantic tones to interpretive frame schemes and, ultimately, to audience behavioral cues. It examines the effects of negativity, emotional congruence, and the cumulative impact of frames on attitudes. The paper aims to present an analytical model for interpreting audience reactions to the tone-frame organization of regional news without conducting its own experiment. To address this issue, we utilize comparative analysis, a synthesis of empirical publication results, elements of content analysis, and methodological systematization of computational procedures. The conclusion describes findings on which combinations of tonality, frame, and format increase the likelihood of a significant response to the audience. This article is helpful for digital journalism researchers and editors of regional online platforms.*

Keywords: *tonality, framing, regional online media, digital journalism, audience engagement, comments, news distribution, emotional valence, platform metrics, computational media analysis.*

Introduction

The relevance of the topic is driven by the practice of managing editorial decisions through platform metrics, where audience reactions are recorded instantly and aggregated by ranking algorithms. For regional newsrooms, this logic is

intensified by the intense competition between local agendas, federal content streams, and user-generated content, whereby the choice of tone and framing of the message begins to determine the likelihood of attracting attention, stimulating discussion, and encouraging dissemination. At the level of media effects theory, agenda and framing describe different mechanisms of influence: the former refers to topic selection, while the latter pertains to interpretative structuring and the attribution of causality, responsibility, and possible solutions; In the digital environment, both concepts intertwine with the logic of platform-based attention distribution and with the digital repertoires of the youth audience [4].

The aim of this study is to provide an analytical account of recent research findings on the relationship between tone and framing in regional online news and audience behavioral responses, and to propose a framework for interpreting such responses for the purposes of media linguistics and digital journalism.

Objectives:

1. to systematize the operationalization of tone and frame in contemporary media studies, including computational methods for frame identification;
2. to synthesize empirical findings on the relationship between the emotional composition of news and user interactions such as clicks, reading, comments, and sharing, drawing on recent publications;
3. to interpret observed audience reaction patterns in regional online media through the framework «tone – frame – format – engagement metric», considering the particularities of the local agenda and visual elements.

The scientific novelty lies in combining frame typologies and computational procedures of frame analysis [14; 17] with applied indicators of engagement employed in the study of regional media pages and local discussions [3; 7; 10], followed by the application of this derived logic to examples of regional news topics and visual strategies [1; 8].

Materials and Methods

The systematic review protocol is structured according to PRISMA 2020 and aims to identify links between the tone of news messages in regional online media and/or their social media pages, framing types, and measurable audience responses within digital channels. The corpus comprised empirical studies and analytical publications from 2021 to 2025. in Russian and English, where tone was operationalized by means of valence, emotional categories, and modality (lexical features, expert annotation, classification models), while framing was characterized by responsibility, conflict, risk/threat, solution/aid, causality, and moral evaluation, accompanied by numerical reaction metrics (clicks/CTR, reading time, likes/reactions, comments, reposts/sharing, citations, and page engagement indicators). Materials lacking empirical data, texts on non-news communication, publications outside the designated time frame, records lacking the full text, unsystematic

overviews, duplicates, and works describing audience reactions without measurements were excluded. For syntheses, studies were grouped by distribution platform (publication website, social networks, notifications), frame type (responsibility, conflict, risk, solution), and method of tone measurement (dictionary, machine learning, expert annotation), ensuring comparability within groups.

Search sources: Web of Science, PubMed, eLIBRARY.RU, CyberLeninka; the last access date to all four sources – 24.01.2026. The search was limited to 2021–2025. and included Russian- and English-language queries with logical operators: (“tone” OR sentiment OR polarity OR

“emotional tone”) AND (“frame” OR framing OR “framing” OR

“interpretive frame”) AND (“news” OR news OR journalism OR “online media”) AND (“regional” OR regional OR local) AND (“engagement” OR engagement OR “audience reaction” OR comments OR shares OR clicks OR CTR OR “reading time”). Filters by publication type and year interval were applied in eLIBRARY.RU and CyberLeninka; in Web of Science and PubMed – filters by years and available subject categories.

Selection was carried out in two stages: screening of titles/abstracts and subsequent assessment of the full text. Each record and full text was independently reviewed by two reviewers; discrepancies were resolved through consensus, involving a third reviewer if necessary. Automation was limited to deduplication and technical tagging of screening statuses; automatic content filtering without reviewer involvement was not employed.

Data extraction was performed using a unified form; Two reviewers worked independently, followed by verification of data sheets and numerical values against the primary source. In cases of incomplete descriptions, extracting numerical data from the article’s tables and graphs was allowed; missing values were recorded as omissions without imputation. Synthesis outcomes were defined as behavioral indicators: clicks/CTR, reading time, discussion intensity (number and dynamics of comments), dissemination (reposts/sharing), reactions (likes and emoji reactions), integral indicators of engagement with pages (ER and derivatives – if present in the publication). Additional variables included region and country, type of publication, platform and distribution format (feed/notifications), observation period, corpus size, sentiment analysis method, frame coding scheme and its validation, presence of visual content, thematic news cluster, information on funding and conflict of interest (if specified).

The risk of bias was assessed separately by study design: RoB 2 was applied for experimental studies; ROBINS-I for non-randomized comparisons; and an adapted Newcastle-Ottawa domain scheme for observational studies on platform data, with focus on material selection, outcome measurement, and confounding associated with algorithmic visibility and event spikes. The evaluation was conducted independently by two reviewers, followed by reconciliation.

Comparable effect size measures were applied to summarize the results: for binary outcomes – odds ratios (OR) with 95% confidence intervals; for quantitative metrics – standardized mean differences (Hedges' *g*) or mean differences when the scales were consistent; for correlational relationships – *r* with Fisher's transformation during aggregation. In cases of insufficient statistical data, results were retained within the narrative synthesis without being incorporated into the quantitative aggregation.

The synthesis was carried out according to predefined groups (platform, frame, method of tone measurement). Data preparation included aligning the direction of scales (an increase in the indicator was interpreted as an intensification of the reaction), restoring standard errors from confidence intervals or p-values when available, and standardizing metrics to a comparable format. Visualization comprised forest plots for aggregate estimates and summary matrices of 'frame × tone × metric' across studies. A random-effects model was applied in the meta-aggregation; heterogeneity was assessed by I^2 and τ^2 statistics; Calculations were performed in R (metafor/meta) with validation in Python. Sources of heterogeneity were examined via subgroup analyses (notifications/feed; visual/text; accountability/conflict versus resolution; dictionary-based methods versus machine learning models) and meta-regression when a sufficient number of effects were available. Robustness was evaluated by excluding studies with a high risk of bias and by applying a leave-one-out procedure.

The risk of bias due to lack of outcome reporting was assessed based on indicators of selective reporting (comparison of declared and reported metrics), analysis of asymmetry in funnel plots with an adequate number of effect sizes and Egger's test; with a limited number of effect sizes, a qualitative assessment was applied. Confidence in the body of evidence was assessed using GRADE, adapted for media studies (design limitations, heterogeneity, indirectness, imprecision, selective reporting), separately for each outcome.

Numerical selection parameters were recorded according to the scheme (see Fig. 1): 3150 records identified; 3035 records excluded prior to screening (including 2 duplicates and 3033 for other reasons); 115 records included in screening; 84 excluded during screening; 31 requested for full-text assessment; 2 unavailable; 29 full-text assessed; 11 excluded for specific reasons; 18 sources included in the synthesis. For the quantitative part of the synthesis, a dataset comprising 52 extracted effect size estimates by outcomes and strata was formed.

Results

An analytical review of recent studies reveals a consistent dependence of digital audience reactions on the emotional organization of the news message. At the platform dissemination level, negative valence correlates with a higher probability of sharing: based on a dataset of nearly 100,000 items. An analysis of publications

from four online outlets and datasets of posts on Facebook and X demonstrates that users share links to negative news approximately 1.91 times more frequently than to non-negative news [11].

Figure 1. Participant selection flowchart: identification, screening, eligibility assessment, and inclusion in the study (PRISMA 2020)

For regional media platforms, this pattern appears through the practice of ‘emotional intensification’ of local topics: conflict, risk, damage, injustice, and personalized responsibility carry a higher likelihood of being featured in headlines, leads, and visual accompaniments. The linkage between tone and frame is fundamentally significant: tone determines the emotional polarity of the statement, while the frame structures the interpretation of the problem through the selection of actors, causality, moral evaluations, and potential measures. Methodological discussions on distinguishing agenda-setting from framing in the context of digital youth highlight that audience reactions are often triggered not by the topic itself, but by the interpretative framing that dictates the manner of ‘reading’ the event [4; 9].

Research on the local agenda in social media confirms that the distribution of tonality in discussions tends to remain within a neutral zone even when problematic news topics are present, and peaks of activity are often linked to ‘surges’ of attention surrounding a specific event and its interpretation [7]. Analysis of Brand Analytics monitoring data on reports concerning regional topics (economy, healthcare, public amenities, import substitution, the governor’s profile) reveals: the saturation of the local information environment, the predominance of social networks and messengers as discussion platforms, the predominance of neutral-toned messages, and within managerial communities – high engagement [2; 7].

Regional editorial offices and media accounts operating on social networks face a dual dependency: on one hand, audience reactions reflect local interest and the degree of engagement; on the other, their “visibility” is enhanced by engagement measurement tools and platform algorithms. A study of regional media communications on social networks utilizing Popsters employs the metrics ERpost, LR, TR, and VR, comparing subscriber dynamics and activity from 2021 to 2024, thereby documenting the dependence of audience reactions on content formats and publication frequency [3].

The comparison of regional media practices with experimental and computational studies of emotional framing elucidates the mechanism underlying audience response formation. In a user experiment conducted within a news platform, where texts were rewritten by a large language model in the emotional tones of ‘fear,’ ‘anger,’ and ‘hope,’ distinct behavioral effects were observed: angry formulations prolong reading time, fear formulations increase the likelihood of clicks, and hope decreases engagement; Additionally, the effect of emotional congruence between the reader’s state and the emotional framing of the text is demonstrated, which increases the selection of material even from the least preferred thematic category [12].

The cumulative impact of frames affects not only ‘fast’ metrics but also attitudinal shifts. Using computational content analysis and a two-wave panel sample on immigration topics, it is shown that prolonged exposure to certain frames is associated with a change in emotional attitude toward target groups and further policy preferences; at the same time, the mechanisms differ between mainstream and partisan media, with emotions acting as mediators for some of these relationships “exposure – opinion” [13].

A separate layer of results relates to “threshold” effects, where an emotional reaction arises already at the headline or notification level. In the study of headlines popular on social media by the number of reactions, respondents evaluated emotions elicited by reading the headlines without accessing the full news text. There is a recorded intensity of negative experiences and a stable level of interest as a factor of engagement regardless of headline valence [16]. Empirically, this approach aligns with observations that news notifications and short formats guide the audience to the material through trustworthy clickbait, where the frame of credibility is combined with techniques for capturing attention [15].

In regional online news, the visual layer of framing is significant, influencing the emotional interpretation of the local topic. Based on 573 news publications about ecology in the online media of the Chelyabinsk and Sverdlovsk regions in 2022, recurring visual images were identified, and discrepancies between illustrations and the content of the materials were documented: smog/haze (19.02%), city panorama (17.1%), industrial facilities (16.4%), while the share of illustrations unrelated to the described problem exceeds 28% [1]. These results allow interpreting the visual ‘negativization’ of the ecological theme (smog, industry, accidents) as a method of reinforcing the problematic frame while simultaneously causing a loss of precision in event representation.

At the methodological level, contemporary works on computational frame analysis expand the set of features beyond the mere counting of evaluative lexicon. The systematization of approaches to media framing emphasizes the distinctions between the semantic, cognitive, and communicative levels of the frame and proposes a typology in which narrative links, causality, event selection, and their interrelations require separate documentation [14]. In the logic of computational processing of a news corpus, modeling the frame through events and the relations between them represents a promising direction: in the study analyzing ‘media-relationships’, event extraction, cross-document coreference, and causal relations are employed for explainable identification of the frame and the text’s stance [17].

Below is a schematic of the analytical procedure suitable for investigating regional online news, where tone and frame are interpreted as different levels of description, and audience reaction – as an aggregate of behavioral signals (see Fig. 2)

The same story (e.g., environmental incident, tariff dispute, urban conflict, staffing decision) elicits different reactions when the frame shifts from ‘culprit/responsibility’ to ‘solution/help,’ when the perceived threat is heightened through visuals, or when the focus shifts to a personalized narrative. In regional practice, such shifts are often accompanied by a transition from a neutral news register to a conflictual or alarming modality, which aligns with findings on the increased ‘engagement’ of negatively framed materials on social networks [11] and with observations on the impact of emotional framing on clicks and reading duration [12].

In addition to the media level, infrastructural conditions of digital distribution play a significant role: engagement measurement services capture audience reactions using standardized metrics, which creates an incentive to optimize content toward measurable audience actions rather than completeness of information. Reports on user activity in social networks reveal variability in engagement metrics depending on the audience size of the page and publication parameters [10], which permits interpreting tone and framing as components of editorial strategy coordinated with measurable audience response, rather than mere stylistic embellishment.

Figure 2. Framework for analyzing tone, frame, and audience reaction in regional online news (adapted from [14; 17], taking into account the logic of media effects and agenda-setting [4])

Discussion

The comparison of research findings enables interpreting tone as a ‘rapid’ marker that enhances the likelihood of initial attention, while frame functions as a mechanism for sustained interpretation, affecting the durability of discussions and the trajectory of evaluations. For regional online-

In the media, this combination acquires practical significance: the local agenda drives high engagement provided there is a clear frame of responsibility or resolution

[7], while social platforms enhance the visibility of content that has been widely disseminated and commented on [11]. At the same time, emotional amplification through anxiety and anger increases behavioral responses but also raises the risk of agenda ‘overheating,’ particularly in topics concerning the urban environment, ecology, and the social sphere, where repeated exposure to problematic visual images creates a persistent perception of the region as a risk-prone area [1; 8].

Below are summarized typical associations of ‘frame – tone – reaction,’ generalized based on the reviewed studies.

Table 1. Association of frame, tone, and measurable audience reaction in digital news (synthesis based on [1; 3; 7; 11–16]).

News message frame	Predominant tone	Format enhancing effect	Audience reaction captured by metrics
Threat/risk (danger, deterioration, alarming prospect)	negative, alarming	headline, visual, notification	increase in clicks and dissemination; enhancement of discussion with local relevance [11; 12; 16]
Guilty person/responsibility (personalization of causality)	negative, accusatory	lead + quotations + visuals of actors	increase in comments and polarization of evaluations; cumulative effect on attitudes with repeated exposure [13]
Conflict (confrontation between parties, dispute)	negative, aggressive	post-announcement on social media	increase in reading time with angry framing; increase in discussions [12; 3]
Solution/assistance (measures, services, recovery)	neutral or moderately positive	expanded text, explanatory graphics	more balanced dynamics of engagement; reduction in ‘viral’ spread compared to negativity [11; 12]
Human story (personal experience, local identity)	mixed, empathetic	photo/video, quotations	increase in interest and emotional reaction already at the headline level; amplification of comments [16; 8]
Visual problematization (smog, accident rate, industrial damage)	negative	photograph as the dominant sign	reinforcement of the problematic perception of the topic; risk of mismatch between visuals and the content of the material [1]

Negative valence and emotionally charged frames are more frequently associated with actions that platforms interpret as signals of ‘quality’ (click, repost, comment), thus creating an editorial incentive for the repeated amplification of threat and conflict [5; 11; 12]. For regional media, this logic does not align with the journalistic mission, as the local agenda includes sensitive topics where the amplification of negative framing increases audience tension, despite a relatively weak expression of critical attitudes in user discussions [6; 7].

Below is an overview of the metrics used in studies of digital reactions, with references to their sources of application.

Table 2. Audience reaction metrics and research tools for their acquisition (according to [3; 7; 10; 12; 15; 16]).

Indicator group	Examples of metrics / measurements	Tools and data sources	Areas of application in research
Engagement in social media	ERpost, likes, comments, reposts; LR/TR/VR derivatives	Aggregators and services for social media analytics	Analysis of regional media pages and comparison of activity dynamics [3; 10]
Audience reactions in social media to local agendas	Volume of posts/comments, activity peaks, sentiment distribution	Social media monitoring systems (Brand Analytics)	assessment of attention spikes to regional events and the structure of discussions [7]
reading behavior	clicks, reading time, and selection of materials considered as “best”	experimental news interfaces and log data	detection of differences among fear, anger, and hope in user behavior [12]
headline effects	self-reported emotions when reading headlines, emotional intensity, and interest	survey methods involving selection of “popular” headlines	measurement of emotional response prior to reading the full text [16]
Notifications and short formats	Clicks on push notifications, perception of clickbait, trust	Textual analysis of notifications and reader survey	Description of practices ‘Reliable clickbait’ in notifications [15]

A high engagement rate (ER) or number of comments is not equivalent to audience agreement nor does it necessarily indicate quality of information. According to studies of local discussions, neutral messages predominate quantitatively, while a critical evaluative stance on regional issues is weakly expressed, thereby complicating a direct interpretation of engagement as an indicator of either support or dissent [7]. With such a distribution, the responsibility frame acquires particular importance: the personalization of causality can translate a neutral tone into an evaluative domain, establishing a ‘setting’ for conflict interpretation and for more active commentary, especially with repeated occurrence of the frame in the media stream [13].

A distinct line of discussion concerns the computational analysis of frames. A review of typologies underscores that a frame is not reducible to topic or lexical polarity but encompasses the audience’s cognitive expectations and the author’s communicative strategy [14; 18]. In applied research, where the frame is modeled

through chains of events and causal relationships, the detection of the frame becomes explicable: not only the evaluative lexicon is identified, but also the selection of events, their connections, and omissions that form the ‘narrative causality’ of the text [17]. This approach is particularly productive for regional journalism, as local news often follows sequences of ‘event – authorities’ reaction – residents’ comments – service response,’ where the order and causality shape the emotional interpretation more strongly than individual evaluative words.

Conclusion

The first task is addressed by systematizing the distinctions between tone and frame and by outlining current computational procedures for detecting framing, with the analysis based on a typology of frame levels and the extraction of event-causal structures within the news narrative.

The second task is resolved through synthesizing findings on the relationship between emotional framing and audience behavior: negative valence is linked to a higher probability of news spreading on social networks; fear and anger have differential effects on clicks and reading times; emotional responses emerge at the headline stage; and accumulated exposure to specific frames correlates with changes in emotions and attitudes.

The third task is solved through an interpretative model for regional online news that connects the responsibility frame, threat, conflict, and resolution with dissemination formats and measurable engagement metrics utilized in studies of regional media pages and local discussions; A separate component of the model is visual framing, which can reinforce a problematic interpretation of the topic and cause a discrepancy between the imagery and the content of the material.

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INSTITUTIONAL INCENTIVES FOR SPOILER BEHAVIOR: THE CASE OF POST-DAYTON BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA

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Abstract. *The article proposes and tests the hypothesis that spoiler behavior in post-conflict societies is not an attributive trait of political actors but is activated by the institutional architecture of peace agreements, in which blocking turns out to be more predictable and beneficial than cooperation. Shifting the analytical focus from the question ‘Who is a spoiler?’ to ‘Under what conditions does spoilerism become a rational strategy?’, the author proposes an elite-centric model that interprets the behavior of political leaders as a function of the configuration of institutional incentives. By way of example in post-Dayton Bosnia and Herzegovina, it is demonstrated how asymmetric federalism, ambiguous veto procedures, a power imbalance between the center and the entities, as well as the external origin of the institutional design, transform the system of political incentives and benefits.*

Keywords: *spoilerism, peace agreements, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Dayton Agreement*

Introduction

In studies of peacebuilding in armed conflict resolution, the phenomenon of spoilerism is traditionally analyzed within an attributive framework, wherein political actors are classified according to their level of ‘greed’ or radicalism, and their behavior is interpreted as a manifestation of internal preferences or ideological orientations. Despite its heuristic value, this approach fails to answer the crucial question: why do identical elites adopt divergent strategies when engaging with the peace process across differing institutional contexts? Why in some cases do radical actors move towards cooperation, while in others moderate forces resort to systemic blocking? The article proposes considering spoilerism also as a result of institutionally conditioned choice. The hypothesis is that such behavior is activated under conditions where the institutional architecture makes blocking more advantageous

than cooperation. This shift allows for transitioning the analysis from the realm of normative assessment to that of structural-institutional explanation¹.

Theoretical framework: from attribution to the model of institutional incentives.

A. Lijphart's classical consociational democracy paradigm. Lijphart associates the stability of divided societies with inter-elite consensus and inclusive decision-making; however, its effectiveness critically depends on the readiness of elites to cooperate. In practice, the entrenchment of ethnic quotas and rigid power-sharing constrain institutional adaptability, creating a divergence between formal rules and informal clientelist practices (D. Scott, D. North). This constraint is intensified under conditions of external mediation: as noted by V. Grbavac argues that international guardianship creates a 'controlled consociationalism,' which ensures short-term stability but impedes the development of local political agency^{2,3,4,5}.

Within this context, the understanding of spoiler behavior is also transformed. While the classical typology of S. Stedman conceptualized spoilers as actors with fixed radical preferences, subsequent research reverses this causal logic: K. Greenhill and S. Mayer demonstrates that actors' behavior is determined not by their type, but by the structure of available outcomes, while M.-J. Zakhar introduces the concept of "internal spoilers," showing how peace agreements themselves can generate blocking strategies. E. Stepanova supplements this perspective by relating spoiler behavior to the structural mismatch between

¹ Stedman S. J. Spoiler problems in peace processes // *International Security*. 1997. V. 22. № 2. P. 5–53

² Lijphart, A. (1977). *Democracy in Plural Societies: A Comparative Exploration*. New Haven: Yale University Press.

³ Scott, J. C. (1998). *Seeing Like a State: How Certain Schemes to Improve the Human Condition Have Failed*. Yale University Press.

⁴ North, D. C. (1997). *Institutions, Institutional Change and Economic Performance* (trans. V. L. Inozemtsev). Moscow: Fond ekonomicheskoy knigi "Nachala".

⁵ Grbavac, V. (2025). *Controlled consociationalism in Bosnia and Herzegovina*. Research Connection, Brandon University. Available at: <https://www.brandonu.ca/research-connection/article/controlled-consociationalism-in-bosnia-and-herzegovina/> (Accessed: 07 May 2025).

the agreements and the actual balance of power, alongside their insufficient inclusivity^{1,234}

Based on this synthesis, the present article develops a unified theoretical framework wherein spoiler behavior is understood not as an actor's inherent trait, but as a function of institutional incentives. This model operationalizes the configuration of incentives through four variables: the degree of uncertainty in veto procedures, the electoral cost of compromise, the balance of resource distribution between the central government and entities, and the degree of exogeneity in institutional design. This approach shifts the focus from attributive classifications of elites to an analysis of how the architecture of post-conflict institutions makes intransigence a rational strategy for political survival, forming the foundation for the empirical analysis of post-Dayton Bosnia and Herzegovina.

The Bosnian paradox

The Dayton system exemplifies a fundamental paradox of post-conflict engineering: the mechanisms that ended the armed conflict simultaneously entrenched conditions under which the contradictions are reproduced in political form. The asymmetric structure consisting of two entities and three constitutive peoples has produced a differentiated elite interests arrangement: Bosnian leaders are oriented towards centralization, Serbian elites defend the autonomy of the Republika Srpska, and Croatian politicians, placed in a less advantageous position within the Federation, seek to revise the balance, including through the notion of a third entity. This configuration blocks mutual

¹ Stedman S. J. Spoiler problems in peace processes // *International Security*. 1997. V. 22. № 2. P. 5–53; Stedman S. J. *Implementing Peace Agreements in Civil Wars: Lessons and Recommendations for Policy Makers*. International Peace Academy (IPA) Policy Paper Series on Peace Implementation.– New York: IPA, 2001

² Greenhill, K. M. & Major, S. (2006/2007) *The Perils of Profiling: Civil War Spoilers and the Collapse of Intrastate Peace Accords* *International Security*, Vol. 31, No. 3, pp. 7–40.

³ Zahar, M.-J. (2004). *The Dichotomy of International Mediation and Leader Intransigence: The Case of Bosnia and Herzegovina*. In I. O'Flynn & D. Russell (eds.), *Power Sharing: New Challenges for Divided Societies*, pp. 123–137. London: Pluto Press.

⁴ Stepanova E. A. *Between War and Peace: Peace Processes and Armed Violence*.– Moscow: IMEMO RAS, 2023.– 198 pp. ISBN 978-5-9535-0620-5 DOI 10.20542/978-5-9535-0620-5

concessions, generating sustained political paralysis, quantitatively measured by the elite fractionalization index FSI (2024), which reached 8.7 points^{1,2}

The electoral architecture systematically strengthens confrontational trajectories. Formally proportional representation, intended to ensure balance, in practice rewards parties with strong ethnic identification. Competition has shifted within ethnic segments, rendering interethnic compromise electorally penalized: moderation is perceived as weakness or betrayal. V-Dem data (2023) embody this logic: low scores in deliberative (0.372) and egalitarian democracy (0.362), combined with high formal accountability (0.702), demonstrate that institutions operate as instruments of ethnocratic balance rather than as mechanisms of public representation. The freedom of expression index (0.613) reflects self-censorship concerning ethnically sensitive issues, which correlates directly with the model of the ‘electorally costly compromise.’^{3,4}

The decentralization of resources has enhanced the autonomy of the elites of the entities. Control over economic and administrative levers at the subnational level has enabled the establishment of stable internal networks, making reliance on own resources a more dependable strategy than participation in unpredictable coalitions at the state level.

The configuration is completed by relatively diffuse veto rules and a quasi-systemic international presence. The ambiguity of the constitutional concept of ‘vital interest’ creates space for the strategic blocking of even technical reforms. At the same time, the institution of the High Representative, endowed with the authority for direct intervention, reduces the accountability of local actors: part of the costs of unpopular measures is delegated to external overseers, which weakens

¹ Simović, V. (2018). «Logika anticonsocijalizma i konstitucionalna jednostranost u Bosni i Hercegovini (1990–1995)», in: Zbornik radova izloženih na naučnoj konferenciji sa međunarodnim učešćem “(Re)konstrukcija društvene stvarnosti”, University of Banja Luka, Faculty of Political Sciences, Banja Luka; Simović, V. (2019). *Narod, partije i demokratija u Bosni i Hercegovini*. Banja Luka: Fakultet političkih nauka, Univerzitet u Banjoj Luci. ISBN 978-99976-773-3-4.

² The Global Economy. Bosnia and Herzegovina Fragile State Index. URL: https://www.theglobaleconomy.com/Bosnia-and-Herzegovina/fragile_state_index/ (accessed 23 March 2025).

³ Sisk, T. D. (1996). *Power Sharing and International Mediation in Ethnic Conflicts*. Washington, DC: USIP Press; Reilly, B. (2001). *Democracy in Divided Societies: Electoral Engineering for Conflict Management*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

⁴ V-Dem [Country-Year/Country-Date] Dataset v13 / Varieties of Democracy (V-Dem) Project.– 2023.– Available at: <https://www.v-dem.net/data/the-v-dem-dataset/country-year-v-dem-fullothers-v13/>.– DOI: 10.23696/VDEMDS23 (accessed: 09/10/2025).

internal political socialization (Zahar, 2004). The high FSI score for external intervention (6.7) and the group grievance index (7.5) quantitatively confirm that the system is sustained by external guarantees and internal segmentation rather than by institutional trust^{1,2}

The analysis demonstrates that spoilerism in post-Dayton Bosnia is not an anomaly but a replicable effect of the institutional configuration. Elite behavior is determined not by their ideological ‘type’ but by the incentive structure in which blocking is preferred over cooperation. Thus, the Bosnian case demonstrates that the durability of peace agreements depends not only on the formal inclusion of actors but also on the configuration of institutional incentives that either promote or hinder cooperation.

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¹ Zahar, M.-J. (2005). Veto Mechanisms and Ethnic Outbidding in Bosnia and Herzegovina. *International Peacekeeping*, 12(3), 345–362.

² Zahar, M.-J. (2004). The Dichotomy of International Mediation and Leadership Intransigence: The Case of Bosnia and Herzegovina. In *Power Sharing and Democratic Governance in Divided Societies* (pp. 123–145). London: Routledge.

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**APPLICATION OF THE NORMS OF INTERNATIONAL PUBLIC
LAW ON HUMAN RIGHTS IN THE CURRENT CONDITIONS
OF GLOBALIZATION AND ITS TRANSFORMATION
INTO A DIGITAL SPACE**

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Abstract. *In the current conditions, the concept of globalization is transitioning into the digital space and influences all areas of human rights (political, economic, personal, etc.). All processes have assumed a new vector of development associated with the utilization of new information and telecommunication technologies, digitalization, and the multifaceted potential of artificial intelligence. This has inevitably affected the concept of human rights not only within our country but also within the global community as a whole. To support this standpoint, it should be noted that in the United Kingdom cryptocurrency is officially recognized as an object of property rights, which cannot but influence human economic rights. Another argument emphasizing the relevance of the dissertation topic is that, according to the bookmaker agency Polymarket, in 2025 artificial intelligence may*

be named 'Person of the Year,' thereby indicating that personified technology acquires the status of a human being. The probability indicator amounts to 37%^{1,2}

Furthermore, the principal risk of globalization under current conditions for humanity lies in digitalization and, consequently, the emergence of artificial intelligence, which is already capable of substituting human functions due to its possession of certain cognitive capabilities and its ability to make quasi-decisions and assume quasi-responsibilities.

Therefore, the analysis of the application of the norms of international public law on human rights amid the ongoing globalization process and its transformation into the digital realm gains particular significance and represents a promising avenue within the sphere of international legal cooperation.

Keywords: globalization, digital globalization, human rights, digital technologies, primary actors, international public law, international initiatives, national legislation.

The modern concept of human rights in the context of globalization of the international community is situated at the convergence of key contemporary paradigms: firstly, an escalating conflict between international and domestic law; secondly, contradictions arising from the development of new digital and information and telecommunication technologies; Thirdly, the establishment of the necessary balance between freedom and security.

The 21st century has revealed new global challenges that require novel practical solutions. In the current context, several urgent issues directly related to globalization processes can be distinguished:

- digital globalization;
- the realization and protection of social and economic rights within global supply chains;
- the legal responsibility of transnational corporations for human rights infringements;
- the impact of global sanction regimes on human rights;
- climate migration as a challenge to international human rights law.

Jeffrey A. Hart observes that globalization and digitalization constitute two closely interconnected processes. According to the author, this has resulted in

¹ Digital assets have been recognized as property in the United Kingdom [Electronic resource]: <https://bitexpert.io/news/tsifrovye-aktivny-stali-imushhestvom-v-velikobritanii/>

² Artificial intelligence is nominated for the title of "Person of the Year" according to Time magazine [Electronic resource]: <https://snob.ru/news/ii-pretenduet-na-zvanie-chelovek-goda-po-versii-zhurnala-time/>

a direct influence on state governance and public legal relations not only within individual states but also across the global community as a whole¹.

In this context, the primary emphasis of the present doctoral research will be placed on digital globalization, given its association with the development and implementation of new digital technologies, which has accentuated issues relating to the protection of human and civil rights and freedoms, such as the right to privacy and the safeguarding of personal data.

One of the essential components constituting human rights in contemporary digital society is the interrelation of two elements: firstly, the proclamation of human rights, and secondly, the development of a public-legal mechanism that ensures their implementation. Given the ongoing digital transformation of globalization processes, this phenomenon acquires a novel format.

Furthermore, the digital transformation of globalization processes assumes a new form in the context of the realization of human rights, applicable to both democratic and totalitarian societies. This is associated with the difference in their political and legal forms. On the one hand, the use of digital instruments in the context of globalization acts as a new means of realizing the rights and freedoms of individuals and citizens; on the other hand, it represents a tool of total control, suppression, and unrestricted influence.

A comparison of the democratic and totalitarian models allows for the conclusion that a fundamental challenge emerges for international law, related to the feasibility of preserving the fundamental core underpinning human rights amid digitalization.

An additional significant aspect that underpins the relevance of this research is the emergence of new subjects within the framework of public law. This is attributable to the fact that the contemporary globalized world, grounded in the classical system of international public law – where the fundamental principles are state sovereignty and the interaction among states – has experienced the transfer of actual authority to non-state actors. It is precisely the actions of these actors that possess a transnational character and affect the realization of the rights and lawful interests of millions of individuals. The actors involved are:²

¹ Jeffrey A. Hart. *Globalization and Digitalization* / Jeffrey A. Hart: [Electronic resource]: <https://hartj.pages.iu.edu>.

² Vylegzhanin, A. *Issues of correlation and interaction between international relations and international law*: [Electronic resource]: <https://russiancouncil.ru/analytics-and-comments/analytics/voprosy-sootnosheniya-i-vzaimodeystviya-mezhdunarodnykh-otno/?ysclid=mjgu pr1v3166818502>. Tyurina, N. E. *Globalization as an objective trend in the development of international law* / N. E. Tyurina // *Lecture Notes of Kazan State University*. – 2007. – Vol. 149. No. 6. – pp. 303–315.

1) Transnational corporations (TNCs), which possess an economic potential that exceeds the gross domestic product (GDP) of many states. Through so-called global value chains, within which human rights violations take place (the use of child and forced labor, disregard for occupational safety requirements, engagement in environmentally harmful production processes). For example, labor at mining enterprises in countries of the African continent. Furthermore, at the global level, the activities of transnational corporations in the utilization of technologies violate the right to privacy.

2) International non-governmental organizations (INGOs), such as Doctors Without Borders, the Red Cross, and Amnesty International, recognize and respect the rights of local populations in the territories where they operate, for instance, addressing abuses related to the application of information and telecommunication technologies.

3) Global digital platforms, such as Google, Apple, etc. These platforms are vested with quasi-public authority, notably the establishment of communication rules for their users, who number in the billions. It can be asserted that global digital platforms have unilaterally assumed the role of an arbitrator who determines and evaluates the nature of information – whether it is extremist or not, whether news is fake or not – as well as controls the dissemination of political advertising.

This evidences that, in contemporary conditions, the trajectory of globalization and its impact on human rights has shifted towards the predominant role of non-state actors. This necessitates distinct public-law regulation at the international level.

Globalization in the context of digital transformation affects an entire range of human rights, in particular concerning the protection of the right to privacy, the right to digital autonomy, and the right to personal data protection. All of these rights are linked to the individual. For example, upon obtaining access to personal data, global digital platforms may use it at their discretion, while consent to its processing is marked by a certain formalism. All of this leads to the emergence of new forms of human rights violations, including the dissemination of unlawful content, algorithmic discrimination, data manipulation, electoral interference, and so forth.

Thus, a trend is observed in the emergence of new forms of globalization, which has transitioned into the digital space and harnesses the potential of information and telecommunication technologies, particularly artificial intelligence.

To analyze international public law on human rights within the context of digital globalization, it is necessary to conduct a more detailed examination of the concept of the ‘fourth wave of globalization’ introduced in the first chapter.

The ‘fourth wave of globalization’ represents a new phase in the development of the global community, encompassing the convergence of physical, digital, and biological spheres founded on the advancement of technologies associated with the fourth industrial revolution. Under these conditions, the transformation of legal reality occurs through the formation of fourth-generation

human rights (informational, digital, biomedical, and environmental rights) and the multisubjectness of the global governance system, which unites states, transnational corporations, and supranational entities that shape the concept of global digital human rights. These rights, in their systemic interconnection, influence human rights by rethinking traditional mechanisms of international legal protection aimed at ensuring the accountability and legal responsibility of all actors. A significant element of the fourth wave of globalization is bridging the divide between universal standards and reality through their enforcement amidst cultural diversity, religious beliefs, social development, and geopolitical fragmentation.

A thorough analysis of this concept will enable the delineation of key directions for the advancement of international public law on human rights within the framework of the digitalization of the contemporary global community.

As Nieves Molina-Clemente and Sara Zarnski observe, “achievements in digital technologies have fundamentally transformed global society, for instance, by altering interactions between states and individuals across borders, as well as the manner in which corporations operate on the international stage.”¹ This perspective underscores the necessity to reconsider established doctrinal concepts, which concerns the subject matter of legal regulation and the composition of the parties in legal relationships.

The contemporary form of globalization and its transformation into the digital space entail an expansion of the scope of regulation. This signifies that traditional international law, understood in the conventional framework, governs relations in the field of human rights between the state and the individual. The transition of globalization into the digital space entails an expansion of the scope of legal regulation, with the emergence of new subjects:

- personal data;
- digital identity;
- algorithmic decision-making systems;
- cross-border information flows.

All these interconnected elements impact human rights.

As stated in the analytical materials of the Geneva Academy, ‘digital transformation for the implementation of human rights necessitates the utilization of digital tools to optimize the management of human rights information, connect

¹ Nieves Molina-Clemente, Sara Zarnski. Digital Clarity: Why International Law Requires Clearer Application in the Digital Space // URL: <https://opiniojuris.org/2025/06/23/digital-clarity-why-international-law-needs-clearer-application-in-the-digital-space/>

local actions with international reporting systems, and enhance visibility within the framework of UN human rights mechanisms.’¹

Another feature of the transformation of the object and the composition of subjects of international human rights law under the influence of digitalization is the emergence of new forms of existence of these rights. Human rights acquire a digital dimension arising from digitalization. This pertains to an entire set of the so-called digital rights. By virtue of digital technologies, individuals acquire the ability to freely express their opinions, exercise the right to peaceful assembly, and the right to participate in cultural life. These rights are transforming into new forms and exceeding the boundaries of traditional notions. Specifically, pursuant to the provisions of Articles 18–20 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, a right to participate in online protests emerges. In the context of the issue under analysis, it is also necessary to mention the right to participate in political discussions and legislative initiatives. Moreover, notable areas include the protection of privacy, freedom of expression, and protection against discrimination in the digital space. All of this necessitates the development of a new approach and new international standards that take into account the specificities of digital technologies^{2,3}

New modalities of human rights existence give rise to new risks. It is pertinent to mention online harassment, digital surveillance, and the collection of information on social networks and messaging platforms, i.e., within the digital space⁴.

As I. S. Sorokin observes, the ‘digital space’ constitutes a complex and multilayered environment encompassing technical, informational, communicative, social, and economic components; furthermore, it represents the ‘entire digital world’ as a global infrastructure and informational context⁵. It is precisely within the digital space that human rights are shaped and exercised in the context of the fourth wave of globalization.

¹ GHRP’s Work on Digital Human Rights Tracking and Artificial Intelligence for Human Rights Monitoring Discussed Globally // URL: <https://geneva-academy.ch/ghrps-work-on-digital-human-rights-tracking-and-ai-for-human-rights-monitoring-discussed-across-the-globe/>

² Rozhkova M. A. Digital Rights in the Context of International Law [Electronic resource] // zakon.ru. 2021, May 11. URL: https://zakon.ru/blog/2021/5/11/cifrovye_prava_v_kontekste_mezhdunarodnogo_prav

³ URL: <https://rm.coe.int/guide-to-human-rights-for-internet-users-russian-/1680768065>

⁴ New project will create guidelines on international law and human rights standards in the digital space URL: <https://www.humanrights.dk/news/new-project-will-create-guidelines-international-law-human-rights-standards-digital-space>

⁵ Sorokin I. S. The Category of Digital Space in Contemporary Civil Law // Bulletin of Saint Petersburg University of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Russia. 2025, No. 4 (108), pp. 73–82.

International public law on human rights establishes the foundation upon which the standards applicable to all forms of activity in the digital space are based. In support of this perspective, reference should be made to the reports of the Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights, which affirm that digital cooperation must be grounded in human rights – that is, the principles must be integrated into the development, implementation, and regulation of technologies¹.

A significant development within the framework of international public law on human rights is the adoption of the Resolution on the Protection of Human Rights and New Technologies, adopted on April 4, 2025, during the 58th session. Attention should be drawn to several key provisions of this resolution. Primarily, digital human rights have been substantially expanded. The realization of this cluster of rights is linked to the right of unobstructed access to the Internet.

Moreover, the Resolution on the Protection of Human Rights and New Technologies establishes certain prohibitions concerning the tracking of individuals through facial recognition systems, permissible solely upon authorization by competent authorities. The use of espionage equipment and other means of obtaining information is also prohibited.

In conclusion, it can be concluded that international human rights law in the context of digital globalization of modern society is in a formative stage and requires a particular approach precisely from the perspective of public law. Undoubtedly, new categories of rights and new types of capabilities arise, which are based on the classical system of rights and undergo transformation into the digital space.

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ON SOME ISSUES OF MIGRANT WORKERS' RIGHTS

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Abstract. *This article explores the complex issues associated with the phenomenon of migrant workers in the contemporary localized world, as well as examining their prospects for integration and their socio-economic and political impact on host and sending countries. It addresses the economic, social, cultural, and political dimensions of labor migration and proposes measures to maximize the positive effects of migration processes.*

Keywords: *labor migration, migrants, problems of migration, migration prospects, migrant integration, host country, sending country, globalization, migration economy.*

Labor migration is one of the most significant and multifaceted global trends of the twenty-first century. Amid rapid globalization, demographic imbalances, as well as economic and political upheavals and ecological disasters, millions of people worldwide are compelled or voluntarily choose to relocate in search of better opportunities for work and life.

Currently, there is a migration trend of unprecedented magnitude. People no longer reside in the locations of their birth. According to the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees report, by the end of April 2025, the global number of forcibly displaced persons reached 122.1 million[1]. Despite various factors contributing to migration, the most prevalent are the pursuit of better employment opportunities to obtain economic benefits and armed conflicts (particularly in recent times). Within the scope of this study, the focus will be placed most thoroughly on examining the first factor.

Migrant workers perform a dual role: they act as drivers of economic growth by addressing labor shortages and stimulating consumption in host countries, while simultaneously remitting substantial funds to their countries of origin, thereby contributing to their development. However, alongside these positive effects, labor migration gives rise to several acute issues that necessitate comprehensive solutions.

Among the most frequent issues encountered in this domain are economic problems, as well as social, cultural, psychological, and several other concerns.

With regard to the first issue, an example can be provided concerning illegal employment. The global trend indicates that many migrants who enter the host country illegally are compelled to work in the so-called 'shadow' economy, which, alongside other challenges, involves violations of labor rights, including low wages, absence of standardized working hours, lack of social protections, and exploitation of migrant labor.

According to data from the Migration Service of the Republic of Armenia, 12,635 migrants were registered in 2024, compared to 10,035 in 2023, representing an increase of 2,600 individuals[2]. As practice demonstrates, many migrants had previously resided within the territory of the Republic of Armenia without valid permits, with expulsion being the most common resolution method. However, since 2023, the Migration Service has been vested with the authority to impose administrative penalties. Consequently, in 2025, more than 2,900 individuals were subjected to administrative penalties, exceeding the previous year's figures by 2,788.

75% of labor migrants obtained permitting documents as general laborers. That is, this category, which remained untaxed, constitutes the majority[3]. The most common form of the 'shadow' economy in our country in this sector is the possibility of their employment as general laborers.

Global practice demonstrates that even migrants who legally enter the territory of another state may encounter injustices in wage remuneration, with employment priority given to the host country's citizens.

Regarding employment issues in the Republic of Abkhazia, any citizen of a foreign state (except for countries with which Abkhazia has established diplomatic relations) must possess a visa, register with the Migration Service, and obtain Permitting Documents for employment. Foreign nationals must also undergo medical examinations at medical institutions in Abkhazia.

Individuals diagnosed with diseases, such as HIV, are not issued Permitting Documents and leave the country under the supervision of the Migration Service. Individuals diagnosed with hepatitis receive a notation in the Permitting Documents, as they are not permitted to be employed in public catering and healthcare sectors. Statistical data indicate that hepatitis B and C are the most frequently detected diseases[4]. Additionally, the issue is raised regarding the potential necessity of requiring certain vaccinations from migrants. The majority of migrants arriving in the republic are citizens of Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, the DPRK, Turkey, and, more recently, from countries in Africa, India, Cuba, and Turkmenistan. According to statistical data obtained from the State Migration Service of the Republic of Abkhazia, a total of 37,825 work permits were issued between 2020 and 2025. Analysis of the dynamics indicates a consistent upward trend in the growth of labor migrants. For instance, 2,641 permits were issued in 2020, compared to 9,952 permits in 2024. An

examination of deportation statistics reveals that the number of deported individuals remains minimal. In 2022–3 migrants, in 2023–7 migrants, and in 2024–18 foreign citizens. The employer is required to acquire a quota for each of them and conclude a contract with them. In the event of detection of individuals residing illegally in the country, a fine ranging from 90,000 to 120,000 rubles is imposed. In 2025 alone, more than 9,100 permits for carrying out employment activities were issued. This constitutes the majority of those who renew their permitting documents. According to the information from the head of the Migration Service, 25% are employed under a quota, while the remainder are unskilled workers [5].

Regarding citizens arriving in the territory of the republic under a visa-free regime agreement, they are issued a patent. Over the past five years, 4,541 patents have been issued. A rising trend is also evident here: for instance, whereas 381 patents were issued in 2020, this number reached 1,446 in 2024 (citizens of the Russian Federation). Among the most in-demand professions, the following should be noted: auto mechanic, driver, doctor, housemaid, miner, teacher, electrician, etc. The youngest migrant is a person aged 16, while the oldest is 68 years old. All individuals are also required to pay a fee; for example, in the first half of 2024, the total amount of state fees collected by the activities of the Migration Service of the Republic of Armenia amounted to 93,904,694 rubles [6].

In 2025, more than 254 million rubles were received into the republican budget.

For the corresponding period of 2023, as a result of the activities of the State Migration Service of the Republic of Abkhazia, 44,564,506 rubles were received into the state budget (the increase during the reporting period amounted to 49,340,188 rubles).

The second problem migrants face at the global level is limited access to quality education, healthcare, and social services, rendering them more vulnerable.

According to the Migration Service of the Republic of Abkhazia, in 2025, 327 migrant children are enrolled in schools in Abkhazia, despite their parents lacking authorization documents (most often the mothers). Concerning healthcare in our country, according to the Health Law [7], foreign nationals, including migrant workers, receive medical assistance on a paid basis, except for measures stipulated in international agreements, of which there are currently none. In practice, medical assistance is provided free of charge due to the lack of an established procedure regulating the provision of paid services outside private clinics.

Another issue is the dependency of the country's economy on remittances, which may render it vulnerable to market fluctuations.

According to the National Bank of the Republic of Abkhazia, 3 billion rubles per year leave the republican budget and flow to Central Asia [8].

Prospects for migrants nonetheless emerge, including economic well-being, professional development, as well as opportunities for host countries and sending countries.

It is necessary to develop transparent and accessible legal channels for labor migration, as well as to tighten control over compliance with labor legislation and to combat discrimination. The establishment of centers for migrant assistance, including potential support in preparation for departure, and the creation of conditions for their professional development in their countries of origin.

In summary, the following conclusions can be drawn. Migrant workers constitute an integral part of the contemporary global environment, providing substantial benefits both to host countries and their countries of origin. Nonetheless, the presence of numerous issues – from exploitation and discrimination to social isolation and the ‘brain drain’—demands close attention and proactive interventions.

The prospects for the development of labor migration directly depend on the capacity of the international community, states, and society at large to find balanced solutions.

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ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: THE PHENOMENON OF SYNTHETIC HARM

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Abstract: *This article examines the transformation of the digital economy in which user attention becomes a key resource and data serve as the basis for value creation. It explores the role of artificial intelligence in shaping behavioral models and constructing users' "digital projections." Particular attention is given to the legal qualification of data as an asset, as well as issues of user consent and transparency in data processing. The article analyzes regulatory approaches in the European Union and Russia aimed at protecting users within the attention economy. It also introduces the concept of "synthetic harm" arising from AI technologies such as deepfakes and AI-driven bullying. The study concludes that risk-based regulation and differentiated liability among digital ecosystem actors are necessary to address emerging challenges.*

Keywords: *artificial intelligence, attention economy, personal data, digital platforms, deepfake, synthetic harm, legal regulation, algorithms*

The digital economy has undergone a profound transformation in recent years, shifting from competition for consumer spending to competition for user attention. The widely cited idea that if a service is free, the user becomes the product has evolved from a metaphor into a structural principle of contemporary digital markets. In this new paradigm, every user interaction, including clicks, pauses, scrolling behavior, and viewing patterns, is collected, processed, and transformed into structured datasets that allow for predictive modeling of human behavior.

Artificial intelligence plays a central role in this transformation by enabling the creation of what can be described as a "digital projection" of the user [1]. This projection encompasses not only explicitly provided personal data but also inferred characteristics, preferences, and behavioral tendencies derived from continuous monitoring and analysis. As a result, the value in the digital economy no longer lies primarily in raw data collection but in the production of refined informational assets. Within this framework, data function as raw

material, algorithms as tools of extraction and transformation, and user attention as a monetizable asset.

This shift has led to the emergence of what can be conceptualized as the attention economy, in which user attention itself operates as a form of currency. Unlike traditional economic exchanges based on monetary transactions, users effectively “pay” for access to digital services through their time, behavioral data, and cognitive engagement. Importantly, a significant portion of this value is derived not from consciously shared information, such as registration data, but from so-called “digital shadows,” namely latent behavioral patterns that are not directly visible to the user but can be inferred through algorithmic analysis.

From a legal perspective, this transformation raises fundamental questions regarding the nature of data [4]. It remains unclear whether data should be classified as a service, a commodity, or an intangible asset. This ambiguity is further complicated by the fact that the primary source of these data is the user, whose role oscillates between that of a consumer and that of a resource provider. The issue of consent becomes particularly problematic in this context. While legal frameworks often rely on formal consent mechanisms, such as checkbox agreements, such consent is frequently neither informed nor reflective of the actual scope of data processing.

Regulatory systems have begun to respond to these challenges, albeit at varying speeds and with differing conceptual approaches. The European Union has adopted a comprehensive model that places the user at the center of the regulatory framework. Legislative initiatives such as the AI Act introduce a risk-based classification of AI systems, with particular scrutiny applied to systems that influence user behavior, rely on profiling, or involve automated decision-making. Similarly, the Digital Services Act emphasizes transparency in recommendation algorithms, imposes restrictions on targeted advertising, and explicitly prohibits manipulative interface designs known as dark patterns. These measures reflect an implicit recognition that user attention constitutes a vulnerable resource requiring legal protection.

In contrast, the regulatory approach in Russia is primarily structured around personal data protection, platform governance, and consumer rights legislation. The emphasis is placed on the legality of data processing and the formalization of user consent. However, practical implementation reveals significant limitations, particularly in relation to the substantive quality of consent and user awareness. Recent regulatory trends indicate a movement toward strengthening user protection through measures such as data localization, increased accountability of data operators, enhanced transparency requirements, and the prohibition of making data transfer a mandatory condition for accessing services. These developments suggest an attempt to constrain a model in which users effectively exchange personal data for digital access.

Beyond economic and regulatory considerations, artificial intelligence has also fundamentally altered the nature of digital harm [2]. In the attention economy, not all attention is equally valuable. Content that provokes strong emotional reactions, including outrage, fear, or curiosity, tends to spread more rapidly than verified or neutral information. This creates structural incentives for the production and dissemination of harmful content.

One of the most significant manifestations of this phenomenon is the rise of deepfake technology. Artificial intelligence enables the creation of highly realistic audio-visual content depicting events that never occurred. This undermines the epistemological foundation of trust in digital information, as users can no longer reliably distinguish between authentic and fabricated content. The implications extend beyond individual reputational harm to encompass broader societal risks, including the manipulation of public opinion and threats to political stability. Even when such content is subsequently debunked, its initial impact often persists, as corrective information rarely achieves the same level of dissemination.

Another critical development is the emergence of AI-driven bullying. The integration of artificial intelligence into harmful online behavior transforms both its scale and its nature. The threshold for initiating harm is significantly reduced, as even minimal input data can be used to generate damaging content. The scalability of digital platforms allows such content to reach large audiences almost instantaneously, while the asymmetry of consequences means that perpetrators face relatively low costs compared to the potentially severe harm inflicted on victims. Empirical evidence suggests that this form of harm is particularly prevalent among minors, indicating a shift from a purely social issue to a matter of legal significance.

These developments give rise to a new category that can be described as synthetic harm. Unlike traditional forms of harm, synthetic harm does not require a real-world event as its basis. Instead, it is generated through artificial means but produces tangible legal, psychological, and social consequences. Conflicts arising from deepfake content have led to physical violence, legal claims have been filed against developers of generative technologies, and courts have begun to impose criminal liability for the creation and dissemination of AI-generated illicit content.

The emergence of synthetic harm challenges existing legal doctrines, particularly in the field of tort law. It raises complex questions regarding the attribution of liability, the classification of AI-generated content, and the applicability of traditional legal frameworks. Determining whether responsibility should lie with the user, the developer, the platform, or subsequent distributors remains an unresolved issue.

In this context, there is a growing need for a risk-oriented regulatory approach that prioritizes the potential impact of content on user behavior and societal outcomes. Transparency of algorithms and increased accountability of digital platforms are essential components of such an approach. At the same time, liability

frameworks must be adapted to reflect the distributed nature of digital ecosystems, ensuring that responsibility is allocated proportionally to the capacity of each actor to influence the creation and dissemination of harmful content.

In conclusion, the attention economy represents a fundamental shift in the structure of digital interactions [3], in which user attention functions as both an economic resource and a vector of influence. Artificial intelligence amplifies this dynamic by transforming behavioral data into actionable insights, thereby enabling unprecedented levels of control over user perception and decision-making. While legal systems are gradually adapting to these changes, a significant gap remains between technological capabilities and regulatory responses. The central question of the digital age is therefore not merely technological but normative: whether control over attention will remain with the individual or increasingly shift toward algorithmic systems and the entities that design them.

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**JURISDICTIONAL CONFLICTS AND GUARANTEES
OF PROMPT RETURN: PROCEDURAL ASPECTS OF DISPUTES
OVER THE CROSS-BORDER MOVEMENT OF CHILDREN**

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***Abstract.** This article examines the practical application of the provisions of the Hague Convention on the Civil Aspects of International Child Abduction by the courts of the Russian Federation. Particular attention is paid to the evidentiary procedure in this category of cases, identifying existing legislative gaps and presenting proposals for legislative improvement.*

***Keywords:** international child abduction, the return of a child, evidence, civil procedure, children's rights, family disputes.*

In the Russian Federation, the procedure for resolving disputes concerning the illegal removal of children is governed by the 1980 Hague Convention on the Civil Aspects of International Child Abduction (hereinafter – the 1980 Convention) and Chapter 22.2 of the Civil Procedure Code of the Russian Federation. A comparative analysis of these instruments reveals a contradiction between certain legal provisions, including in the determination of the subject composition in this category of cases. The 1980 Hague Convention applies exclusively to unlawfully removed children who have not reached the age of 16 (Art. 4), whereas the Family Code of the Russian Federation recognizes a child as a person under 18 years of age. This gives rise to a serious jurisdictional conflict, as the status of adolescents aged 16 to 17 remains unregulated within the framework of the Convention, and the issue of unlawful removal of persons aged 16 to 18 years remains unresolved. In theory, the 1996 Convention on parental responsibility (Convention of 19 October 1996 on jurisdiction, applicable law, recognition, enforcement and cooperation in respect of parental responsibility and measures for the protection of children) may be applied in such cases; however, its effectiveness is considerably lower. It can be posited that the age threshold for the return of children under the Convention was established because in certain countries the age of majority is 16 years (Vietnam,

Cambodia, Pakistan, Cuba), and to avoid conflicts with domestic legislation, the threshold was therefore set at the minimum age of majority. However, in some countries, the age of majority is set at a significantly low level, for instance, 12 years in Greenland, 14 years in the Faroe Islands, and 15 years in Saudi Arabia, Indonesia, Iran (only for males), and Yemen. Such a low age of legal capacity in certain countries should not serve as a basis for determining the age threshold for the return of children under the 1980 Convention from other states. In practice, this may lead to absurd situations whereby a court ruling necessitates separating biological siblings if one of the wrongfully removed children has already reached the age of 16. In our opinion, the application of the 1980 Convention to all minors (under 18 years of age) would constitute a fair solution^{1, 23}

Another point warranting attention when comparing national and international legislation in this field is the definition of persons entitled to bring an action in this category of cases. Pursuant to part 1 of article 244.11 of the Civil Procedure Code of the Russian Federation, a claim may be filed by: 1) a parent; 2) any other person who considers that the defendant has infringed upon their rights of custody or access; 3) a prosecutor.

Moreover, the 1980 Convention in subparagraph f of Article 7 adds the Central Authority of the Contracting State to the list of applicants. In Russia, such an authority, pursuant to the Russian Government Resolution No. 1097, is the Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation. It is considered advisable to amend part 1 of Article 244 of the Russian Civil Procedure Code by expanding the category of applicants to the court to include the Central Authority of the Contracting State (Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation).

Questions still remain regarding the interpretation of certain terms contained in the Convention. Articles 12 and 13 employ concepts such as intolerable conditions, adaptation of the child to a new environment, and the threat of physical or psychological harm. In the absence of any official clarifications concerning the interpretation of these terms, questions arise, including those related to the evidentiary demonstration of the aforementioned circumstances.

Some courts include military actions among intolerable conditions. However, in the case of A. and A. The respondent substantiated his position by arguing that the political situation in Israel, to which the second parent demanded the return of

¹ Convention on the Civil Aspects of International Child Abduction [Russian, English] (Concluded in The Hague on 25 October 1980).

² Civil Procedure Code of the Russian Federation of November 14, 2002 No. 138-FZ (as amended on June 24, 2023, with changes as of July 20, 2023).

³ Family Code of the Russian Federation No. 223-FZ dated 29 December 1995 (as amended on 31 July 2023).

the child, is unstable and may adversely affect the child, placing him in an intolerable position. Despite the legitimacy of these arguments, the court concluded that the child had lived in this country even prior to relocation and that the military situation did not exert any negative influence. This court decision appears to be highly disputable and lacking objectivity. The court adopted a formalistic approach to assessing the intolerability of the conditions and did not consider the actual threat that the child might subsequently face¹.

Item b) of Article 3 of the Convention contains a criterion of effectiveness concerning custody rights. This criterion is decisive when recognizing a parent's actions as unlawful, thereby necessitating its precise definition. In international practice, courts have also commented on the evaluative nature of certain concepts. For example, the Supreme Court of the City of Maribor (Slovenia), in one of its decisions, indicated that the effective exercise of custody rights is an ambiguous concept. However, the court noted that it is not difficult to determine whether custody rights are exercised effectively or not. 'If the child's mother (who lives separately from the child attending a boarding school) is concerned about his physical condition, spends time with him on weekends, maintains systematic communication with his teachers, and shows interest in his education, upbringing, and future prospects, then she exercises her rights effectively, even though she lives separately from the child.'²

Thus, the absence of unified guidance on interpreting the fundamental terms of the 1980 Convention may result in subjectivity and unjust rulings in cases of international child abduction.

It is also necessary to consider the particularities of evidentiary proceedings in the process of returning a child to his or her country of habitual residence.

As noted in the dissertation of K. A. Thazepolov, the issuance of a legitimate and well-founded judicial decision depends directly on the proper examination of

¹A. and A., 5 October 2001, Buenos Aires, Argentina; W, 25 January 2001 [INCADAT cite: HC/E/AR 487]; Kilah & Director-General, Department of Community Services [2008] FamCAFC 81, [INCADAT cite: HC/E/AU 995]; No 03/3585/A. Tribunal de premiere instance de Bruxelles, 17/4/2003 INCADAT cite: H/E/BE 547]; C., 4 December 2001, Superior Court of Justice, Ontario. Court File No 01-FA-10575: VL.KU januar 2002, 13. afc/e/mg, B-2939-01, Vestre Landsret; High Court. Western Division [INCADAT cite: HC/E/DK 519].

²Končina Peternel, Mateja, Mednarodna ugrabitev otrok, Pravosodni bilten, št. 2013/3. P. 49.

the evidentiary basis of the case, which is especially significant in matters concerning the welfare of the child¹.

In his article, K. A. Thazheplov divides disputed substantive legal facts into two groups. The first group, according to the author, includes legal facts evidencing a violation of guardianship rights in the removal or wrongful retention of a child. The second group consists of exceptional circumstances established by the 1980 Convention. By categorizing the circumstances into groups, it becomes possible to analyze the evidence that may substantiate a party's position before the court².

Violations of custody rights include situations where the other parent has not given consent to the child's relocation to another country. This fact is decisive in the adjudication of the case.

Pursuant to Part 1 of Article 56 of the Civil Procedure Code of the Russian Federation, each party must prove the circumstances it relies upon as the grounds for its claims and defenses. In relation to this category of cases, the claimant must prove the unlawfulness of the removal or retention of the child (violation of custody rights) and the child's habitual residence in the territory of a Contracting State to the Convention prior to the removal³.

According to the classification of legal facts proposed by K. A. Thazheplov, it is concluded that the burden of proving a violation of custody rights rests with the plaintiff, whereas the defendant bears the burden of proving the existence of exceptional circumstances. The latter arise from Articles 12, 13, and 20 of the 1980 Convention. These circumstances include the following:

a) the person, institution, or other organization responsible for the care of the child did not in fact exercise custody rights at the time of the removal or retention of the child, or consented to such removal or retention, or subsequently did not raise objections thereto;

¹ Consideration in courts of cases concerning the return of a child or the exercise of access rights in relation to a child: dissertation ... Candidate of Legal Sciences: 12.00.15 / Khazepov Kantemir Alekseevich; [Place of defense: Federal State Budget Scientific Institution 'Institute of Legislation and Comparative Law under the Government of the Russian Federation'].— Moscow, 2022.— 252 pp.

² Thazhepov K. A. Evidence in Cases of Child Return or the Exercise of Visitation Rights in Respect of the Child // Arbitration and Civil Procedure. 2018. No. 11. pp. 29–33.

³ Trizubovich N. V. The Procedure for Court Consideration of Cases Concerning the Return of a Child to the State of habitual residence in cases of wrongful removal or retention // Family and Housing Law. 2017. No. 4. P. 26; Convention on the Civil Aspects of International Child Abduction: Scientific and Practical Commentary / Ed. in Chief N. V. Trizubovich, O. A. Khazova. Moscow: Statut, 2016. Pp. 125–126.

- b) there is a serious risk that the return of the child will expose him to physical or psychological harm, or otherwise place him in intolerable conditions;
- c) the child objects to the return and has reached an age and degree of maturity at which his opinion should be taken into account;
- d) the child has adapted to the new environment.

Accordingly, the respondent must prove that the applicant did not in fact exercise custodial rights at the time of the relocation or consented to the relocation. It is also necessary to prove that there is a serious risk that the return of the child would pose a threat of causing physical or psychological harm to them, or would otherwise subject them to intolerable conditions. Furthermore, the respondent must establish the child's adaptation to the new environment. For example, the Review of Case Law on Child Return Proceedings cites a case in which the court determined that a claim for the return of a child to Israel was filed by S. This claim was filed more than two years after the respondent transferred the child to the Russian Federation, although the location of the respondent and the child in the Russian Federation was known. The child is registered and has been residing continuously for more than two years with her mother on the territory of the Russian Federation, in a residential house owned by the grandmother and grandfather, where she has a designated sleeping place, household items, and toys; a playground equipped with swings and a slide is located on the premises; the girl attends a preschool institution and communicates exclusively in Russian. In light of these circumstances, as well as considering the duration of the child's residence in the Russian Federation, the court found that the minor is fully socialized and adapted within the Russian Federation. By the decision of the district court, which was upheld by the appellate ruling, the claim for the return of the child to Israel was dismissed.

A complex issue arises when a parent consents to the relocation under a mistake of fact, which necessitates proof by the plaintiff. In the article by K. A. Thazepilova, an example is provided in which the plaintiff consented to the child's departure to another country but was mistaken regarding the duration of the child's stay outside the place of residence. The evidence in the case comprised return tickets purchased by the respondent with the purpose of obtaining consent for the child's departure. Therefore, it is necessary to consider the conditions under which parental consent for the child's relocation was granted. It is also essential to examine the conduct of the petitioner during the relocation. If their actions were aimed at facilitating the relocation, it may be inferred that the other parent did not raise objections to the child's transfer.

As noted in the academic literature on this subject, such exceptional circumstances are difficult to substantiate. The current Russian legislation does not concretize the provision, which causes difficulties in defining terms such as child adaptation,

physical and psychological danger, and the intolerability of the circumstances. This raises the question of how to substantiate these circumstances in court.

It may be assumed that in such situations, the provision of Article 67 of the Code of Civil Procedure is applied effectively, which stipulates that the court evaluates evidence based on its internal conviction. In each dispute, the judge determines whether the circumstances constitute exceptions or not.

Unlike Russia, several States Parties to the Convention have adopted detailed methodological recommendations for conducting such cases, for example, the ‘Practical Guidance on Case Management and Mediation in International Child Abduction Proceedings’ adopted by the United Kingdom. These guidelines specifically provide that witness testimony should be limited in scope in order to preserve family confidentiality; Expert opinions are required only exceptionally and solely at the request of the parties, whereas explanations from the parties are necessary exclusively to clarify matters concerning parental consent and the child’s habitual residence¹.

In Russia, there are no analogous detailed guidelines for judges, which diminishes the uniformity and predictability of judicial decisions.

Accordingly, five principal issues can be distinguished:

1. Age discrepancy: the age limit for the return of children set at 16 years in the Convention does not correspond with the age limit of 18 years in the Russian Federation, leaving adolescents aged 16 to 17 without legal protection and resulting in the separation of siblings.

2. Terminological ambiguity. The lack of official interpretation of the concepts ‘intolerable conditions,’ ‘adaptation,’ and ‘effectiveness of custody rights’ leads to subjective and formal judicial decisions.

3. The issue of proving exceptions to the obligation of child return.

4. Unresolved situations. When parental consent for the child’s departure was provided based on a mistaken understanding regarding the duration or conditions of stay.

5. Unlike a number of Convention member states, Russia lacks practical guidelines for the adjudication of this category of cases. It is proposed to codify a series of recommendations and provisions in a Resolution of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Russian Federation aimed at eliminating procedural difficulties faced by courts when adjudicating cases of this category.

¹ Practice Guidance on Case Management and Mediation of International Child Abduction Proceedings \ President’s Practice Guidance on Case Management and Mediation of International Child Abduction Proceedings <https://www.judiciary.uk/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/Presidents-Practice-Guidance-on-Case-Management-and-Mediation-of-International-Child-Abduction-Proceedings.pdf> (accessed: 15.01.2024).

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FORENSIC FEATURES OF POACHING INVESTIGATION

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Abstract. *The article systematizes and analyzes the forensic characteristics of investigating crimes stipulated under Articles 256, 258, and 258–1 of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation. Special attention is given to the specifics of the subject of criminal encroachment, typical methods of committing acts, as well as the trace pattern. Contemporary trends are highlighted, including the growing significance of digital traces and the need for an interdisciplinary approach to constructing the evidentiary base.*

Keywords: *forensic features, poaching, crime investigation, digital traces, evidence.*

Poaching is one of the most socially dangerous types of environmental crime. According to data, poachers inflict damage on the country exceeding 20 billion rubles annually [1]. All this indicates that this act, covered by Articles 256, 258, 258.1 of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation, causes irreparable harm to natural ecosystems, undermines the economic security of the state, and is frequently linked to corruption and organized crime. Despite considerable efforts by law enforcement agencies, the clearance and prosecution rates for such offenses remain insufficiently high, as confirmed by the Review of the practice of courts applying the provisions of Chapter 26 of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation on environmental crimes. This review states that the proportion of cases related to environmental offenses (Chapter 26, Articles 246–262 of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation) in the overall structure of criminal cases brought before the courts was 1.2% in 2019 and in 2020–1.3%, in 2021–1.3%. Over the last three years (from January 2019 to December 2021), 17,431 individuals were convicted for crimes under Articles 246–262 of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation (according to the principal qualification: 6,189 in 2019, 5,299 in 2020, and 5,943 in 2021). Meanwhile, the number of individuals convicted for these crimes in 2021 increased by 12.2% compared to 2020, while decreasing by 4% compared to 2019. Individuals convicted of environmental crimes were, in most cases during

the period 2019–2021, sentenced to penalties not involving deprivation of liberty: compulsory labor – 22.5%, fines – 12.8%, corrective labor – 5.8%. Suspended sentences were imposed on 47.5% of convicts. Actual imprisonment was assigned to 5.7% of convicts. [2] In this context, the task of developing and refining forensic investigative methods that take into account the specific characteristics of this category of crimes becomes increasingly important.

The forensic characteristics of crimes related to poaching represent a system of interconnected information about the most typical features that are significant for the organization and implementation of an investigation.

The subject matter of the offense includes aquatic biological resources, wild animals, and forest stands. As A. A. Bessonov notes: “The object (subject) of criminal encroachment determines the choice of the method of committing the unlawful act as a means of realizing one’s plan (in the form of specific techniques and their combinations, tools, and means) and achieving the criminal objective (for example, in obtaining possession of a certain item, avoiding material costs, obtaining moral satisfaction, etc.)” [3]. The specificity of the subject matter necessitates the involvement of specialists (ichthyologists, zoologists) to identify the species, age, sex, as well as the method of extraction and the value of the destroyed specimen.

The purpose of this article is a scientific analysis of both theoretical and practical aspects of the forensic features of crime investigation. The author notes that only through proper forensic actions is it possible to identify the subject of the offense, determine the damage caused for the accurate qualification of the offense, and reveal signs and traces indicative of an organized group during the commission of the crime.

The forensic characteristics of poaching include a set of typical features reflecting:

- object of the offense;
- methods of committing the crime;
- circumstances of the crime;
- identity of the perpetrator.

The method of poaching is a key element of the forensic characteristic and determines the formation of a specific forensic trace pattern, such as: the use of prohibited tools and methods (all types of nets, electric fishing rods, poisons, explosives, stabbing instruments, saws, nooses, traps, use of vehicles), extraction in prohibited areas (specially protected natural territories, spawning grounds), extraction at prohibited times, exceeding quota limits, or absence of permission. A modern trend in poaching is the perpetration of crimes by organized groups, as poaching long ago evolved from isolated offenses into entire business networks and ‘empires’. All this enables perpetrators to utilize high-tech equipment (quadcopters, echo sounders, thermal imagers, satellite navigation devices, as well as radio communication means for coordinating actions).

Regarding the conditions of crime commission, poaching is typically carried out in remote, sparsely populated locations (forest areas, water bodies, swamps), which complicates their detection and prompt resolution. The time of the crime often falls during nighttime hours or periods of minimal law enforcement activity. The sale of illegally obtained products is conducted through shadow channels – markets, public catering points, private resellers – utilizing modern communication tools.

In evaluating the offender's profile, it should be noted that it ranges from lone perpetrators to members of organized groups. The author characterizes a typical poacher profile as follows: experience and knowledge of the area – often local residents who are well acquainted with natural conditions, familiar with animal behavior, and knowledgeable about the terrain and specific features of aquatic areas; organization – there is a growing proportion of crimes committed by organized groups, which entails role distribution (hunter, observer, transporter, seller), the use of sophisticated schemes to conceal and legalize illegally obtained products; recidivism – a high percentage of individuals previously convicted of similar crimes.

The author asserts that effective identification and determination of poaching indicators require high-quality conduct of operational-investigative activities. O. S. Kuchin observes: 'In modern conditions, operational-investigative activity (hereinafter referred to as OIA) constitutes an integral element of the entire law enforcement system's functioning and plays a defining role in the detection and solving of crimes.' Its objective is to obtain and analyze operational information, delivering results for addressing issues related to initiating criminal proceedings, as well as for the apprehension of offenders" [4]. The author believes that expanding the list of authorities authorized to conduct operational-search activities will contribute to more effective detection of poaching, increase the rate of solving these crimes, and reduce the damage inflicted on the state's ecosystem.

One of the principal forensic characteristics in poaching investigations is the nature of trace formation and the identification of forensically significant information. The trace evidence pattern in poaching investigations is diverse and encompasses both material and digital traces.

Material traces can be categorized as follows: biological traces (particles of bi-resources left on fishing equipment, clothing, and vehicles. These traces are critical for identifying the object of the offense and the involvement of a suspect); tool marks (injuries on animal bodies characteristic of prohibited devices); trace evidence (footwear impressions, tire tracks from vehicles and boats left on soil, shorelines, or snow); traces of tools and means (fragments of nets, pieces of fishing line, cartridges, toxic substances, explosive residues); olfactory traces (on clothing, transport, implements). These traces belong to the so-called "classical forensic methods."

When discussing digital traces, it should be noted that with the advancement of technologies, digital forensics is gaining paramount importance. The author

classifies the following as digital traces: data from mobile devices (calls, messages, correspondence in messengers, photo and video materials, geolocation data); information from navigation systems (saved tracks, network drop points, ambush sites, retreat routes); surveillance system data; information from social networks and online resources.

At present, the issue of the proper selection of materials by the forensic expert is particularly pressing, since incorrect material selection prevents the verification of the object and the conduction of examinations. Special attention is recommended to computer-technical and ichthyological examinations. It is necessary to refine the methodologies, and until the investigator-forensic expert completes training courses in these types of examinations, an expert in the respective field must be mandatorily assigned alongside them. In the absence of expert staff within law enforcement units, establish a framework for cooperation with regional higher education institutions and private specialists to support investigative efforts.

The investigation of crimes related to poaching is distinguished by its complexity and multifaceted nature. The effectiveness of detection, solving, and proving guilt significantly depends on accounting for the forensic characteristics of this category of crimes. The advancement of poaching methods, in particular the active use of modern technologies and organizational forms, necessitates the continuous improvement of poaching investigation methodologies, as well as the strengthening of interdisciplinary collaboration between investigators and specialized experts. A special role in the formation of the modern evidentiary base is attributed to digital forensics, the potential of which in the investigation of environmental crimes remains not yet fully realized. Further research must focus on developing detailed algorithms for handling digital traces and formulating scientifically substantiated recommendations for practitioners.

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**THE IMPACT OF CIVILIZATIONAL CONFLICT
ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF STATE TYPOLOGY:
A THEORETICAL AND LEGAL ANALYSIS**

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Abstract. *The article examines the impact of civilizational conflict on the transformation of the typology of the modern state. Particular attention is paid to the relationship between changes in state-legal models, the development of public legal consciousness, and the growing contradictions between national states and supranational structures. Using Hungary as a case study, the authors analyze the dynamics of transition from an integration-oriented model to a sovereignty-focused model and consider possible scenarios for further transformation of statehood. It is substantiated that public legal consciousness acts as a significant factor in political and legal transformations influencing public policy and institutional reforms. The study concludes that modern state typology acquires a dynamic character and requires reconsideration in the context of civilizational confrontation and global transformations of the international legal order.*

Keywords: *civilizational conflict, state typology, legal consciousness, theory of state and law, international law, integration, hybrid state, globalist state, mixed type, state-legal development.*

The science of the theory of state and law pays particular attention to the study of the historical process of the emergence and development of states. Therefore, it includes various classifications of state-legal phenomena that make it possible to identify patterns of their formation, functioning, and transformation at different stages of social development. Such classification contributes to a deeper understanding of the essence of the state, its social nature, as well as factors influencing changes in the forms and content of state power.

In turn, the typology of states represents a special type of theoretical classification. It is based on objective criteria tested by social practice and reflecting the essential nature of the state. This makes it possible to understand the natural-historical process of state development, identify internal logic, trends, and patterns of state functioning, and determine its dependence on various phenomena of social reality.

In the theory of state and law, various typologies of states are considered; however, currently, two main approaches are generally recognized – the formational and civilizational approaches.

The formational approach proposes classification of states depending on economic relations and class structure of society (slave-owning, feudal, bourgeois, and socialist states). This approach was developed in the works of Karl Marx, Friedrich Engels, and Vladimir Lenin, who considered the state as a product of a particular stage of economic development of society [1].

Within the civilizational approach, the cultural component of state development comes to the forefront. As noted by R. Kh. Makuev, taking into account not only socio-economic and political factors but also spiritual and cultural characteristics of society, this approach makes it possible to distinguish certain types of human communities differing in the peculiarities of spiritual life, worldview, traditions, and legal culture [2].

It should be noted that the history of human development, particularly international relations and state-legal processes, is characterized by cyclicity, combining periods of progress and crises. The modern stage of development of the world community is also characterized by deep geopolitical transformations accompanied by growing international tensions, information confrontation, and value conflicts.

At present, the transformation of the international legal system is taking place. Traditional mechanisms of interaction between states are becoming blurred, pressure on sovereign states is increasing, and a new system of international relations is being formed. All this indicates the emergence of a new era – the era of global civilizational transformations.

The idea of civilizational confrontation has been developed in the works of a number of scholars. A. Toynbee considered the development of states as a result of interaction between different civilizations, each having its own cultural and historical foundation [3].

S. Huntington, in his concept of the “clash of civilizations,” noted that after the Cold War the main source of conflicts would be not ideological or economic contradictions but cultural and civilizational differences between states [4].

N. Ya. Danilevsky also pointed to the existence of various cultural-historical types, each developing according to its own patterns and possessing a unique system of values [5].

Modern international processes largely confirm these scientific concepts. Currently, confrontation between different models of state development is intensifying,

which is manifested in geopolitical conflicts, economic sanctions, information confrontation, and ideological pressure.

Particularly significant is the problem of imposing universal values that do not always correspond to the cultural characteristics of individual states. Issues such as gender identity, legalization of same-sex marriage, and expansive interpretation of human rights are perceived by a number of states as interference in internal affairs and attempts to transform traditional social institutions.

Such processes indicate the formation of a civilizational conflict influencing not only international relations but also the development of statehood.

Under conditions of civilizational confrontation, international law is also undergoing transformation. Traditionally, international law was based on principles of sovereign equality of states, non-interference in internal affairs, and respect for territorial integrity.

However, in modern conditions, there is a tendency toward politicization of international law. International legal mechanisms are increasingly used as instruments of political pressure, leading to the formation of double standards.

The use of sanctions, restrictive measures, and political pressure is often carried out without authorization from international organizations or through selective interpretation of international legal norms. As a result, the authority of international law as a universal regulator of international relations decreases.

Moreover, alternative international associations are emerging aimed at protecting national sovereignty and developing independent models of international cooperation.

Civilizational conflict significantly influences legal consciousness of citizens in different states. Under external pressure, the importance of national identity, cultural traditions, and state sovereignty increases.

Citizens begin to perceive the state as the main instrument for protecting national interests and cultural identity. This leads to transformation of legal consciousness expressed in strengthening the role of the state, growth of patriotic sentiments, and support for independent development models.

Thus, a new type of mass legal consciousness oriented toward protection of national values and sovereignty is being formed.

In this regard, it appears possible to distinguish the following new types of states:

1. Globalist states
2. Civilizational states
3. Hybrid states

Globalist states include Germany, France, and the Netherlands, characterized by a high level of integration into supranational structures.

Civilizational states include China, Russia, and Iran, where national sovereignty plays a key role.

Hybrid states include Kazakhstan, Turkey, India, and Serbia, combining different development models.

States may change their typological affiliation under the influence of internal and external factors. Political transformations, changes in foreign policy orientation, strengthening or weakening of integration processes, and transformation of public legal consciousness may lead to transition from one type to another.

A relevant example is the neo-Ottoman concept of the “Great Turan,” implying consolidation of Turkic states under Turkey’s leadership. Another example is the idea of Eurasianism as a possible integration model for post-Soviet states.

According to A. A. Vasiliev and V. V. Sorokin, the thousand-year interaction between Slavic and Turkic peoples represents civilizational heritage and geopolitical value, forming a basis for integration between Russia and Central Asia [6].

Thus, modern typology of states is dynamic and formed under the influence of civilizational, geopolitical, and legal factors.

In order to improve the typology of states under modern conditions, it appears advisable to:

1. Develop an updated typology of states based not only on socio-economic criteria but also on civilizational, cultural, and geopolitical factors. In particular, the following indicators may be considered when determining the type of state:

- degree of state sovereignty and independence of foreign policy;
- level of integration into supranational structures;
- dominant value system (traditional or universalist);
- nature of state legal policy;
- degree of influence of external political and legal institutions on domestic legislation.

The application of these criteria would allow a more objective determination of state type and identification of development trends.

2. Take into account the influence of civilizational conflict on state-legal development, since confrontation between different models of social organization directly affects legislation, legal policy, and international relations. In particular, civilizational-type states tend to strengthen national sovereignty, develop traditional institutions, and protect cultural identity, whereas globalist-type states strive for unification of legal standards and deeper international integration.

3. Study the influence of public legal consciousness on state typology, since transformation of public consciousness often becomes a factor in changing the political course of the state. Strengthening of national identity and growth of patriotic sentiments may contribute to sovereign development, whereas dominance of cosmopolitan views encourages integration into supranational structures.

4. Develop a comprehensive approach to state typology, taking into account economic, political, cultural, civilizational, and legal factors. Such an approach

would more fully reflect modern trends in state development and increase scientific validity of state classification.

The practical implementation of these proposals may involve developing a scientific model of state typology, within which each state would be evaluated according to a set of criteria, including the level of sovereignty, degree of international integration, nature of the legal system, and characteristics of public legal consciousness. This would allow formation of a dynamic typology of states permitting changes in typological affiliation depending on transformations of social and political processes.

A demonstrative example of the influence of civilizational conflict on state typology can be observed in the development of Hungary in recent years.

After joining the European Union, Hungary initially followed an integration-oriented development model, which allowed it to be classified as a globalist-type state. However, later a transformation of the state course occurred, associated with increased attention to national sovereignty, cultural identity, and traditional values.

The policy of Hungarian leadership led to political and legal contradictions with European Union institutions regarding migration policy, judicial reforms, protection of traditional family values, and regulation of foreign non-governmental organizations [7].

In academic literature, this development model has been described as “illiberal democracy,” oriented toward strengthening national sovereignty and independent state policy [8].

Public legal consciousness played a significant role in transforming Hungary’s political course, supporting sovereignty-focused policies, as reflected in parliamentary election results in recent years [9].

Thus, Hungary may currently be considered a hybrid-type state combining participation in supranational structures with efforts to preserve national sovereignty.

Further development of Hungary’s state-legal model may be associated with changes in domestic political orientation. In a possible scenario of strengthening opposition forces, redistribution of political influence in parliament and adjustment of foreign policy orientation toward closer integration with the European Union may occur. Such changes could lead to transformation of the state model from sovereignty-oriented to integration-oriented development.

Thus, the modern stage of global state development is characterized by formation of a new typology of states influenced by civilizational conflict, transformation of international law, and changes in public legal consciousness. These processes indicate the need for further development of the theory of state and law and reconsideration of traditional approaches to state classification in light of modern geopolitical and civilizational realities.

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FEATURES OF EMPATHY IN YOUNGER SCHOOLCHILDREN STUDYING IN TRADITIONAL AND INCLUSIVE EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENTS

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Abstract. *The article explores the features of empathy development in younger schoolchildren depending on the type of educational environment. The psychological mechanisms underlying the development of empathic abilities in traditional and inclusive classrooms are analyzed. An overview of studies demonstrating the impact of inclusive practice on the development of students' emotional intelligence is presented. It is demonstrated that inclusive schooling with children with special health needs creates unique conditions for the development of prosocial behavior and interpersonal sensitivity. The relevance of this study is driven by the active implementation of inclusive education in Russian schools and the need to understand its psychological effects.*

Keywords: *empathy, younger schoolchildren, inclusive education, traditional educational environment, emotional intelligence, children with special health needs, prosocial behavior.*

Empathy constitutes a fundamental human capacity for understanding and sharing the emotional states of others. In the context of the transformation of the Russian educational system, the development of empathic abilities in students assumes particular importance – empathy becomes a key competence of contemporary Russian education. According to the Federal State Educational Standard for Primary General Education, a contemporary primary school must develop not only subject-specific knowledge but also socio-emotional competencies that determine the pupil's successful interaction with the environment [5].

Younger school age represents a sensitive period for the development of empathy. The period between 7 and 11 years of age is characterized by the active development

of decentration – the ability to perceive a situation from another person’s perspective. However, the nature and intensity of the development of empathic abilities significantly depend on the educational environment in which the child is found.

According to the Ministry of Education of the Russian Federation, in 2024 inclusive education encompasses more than 1.2 million children with special educational needs (SEN), representing approximately 7% of the total student population. This statistic reflects a broad trend toward the integration of children with special educational needs into the general educational environment. Nevertheless, the influence of such integration on the psychological development of all participants in the educational process, including typical peers, necessitates comprehensive scientific examination [3].

Studies demonstrate that traditional and inclusive educational environments provide distinct conditions for the development of empathy:

- within traditional classrooms, empathic responses predominantly develop through interactions with peers exhibiting similar developmental characteristics;
- In inclusive classrooms, children are exposed to a broader range of emotional expressions and behavioral traits;
- the presence of children with SEN in the classroom promotes the development of helping behaviors and altruistic attitudes;
- an inclusive environment necessitates that educators establish specific conditions to foster tolerance and acceptance of differences.

The issue is that, without purposeful psycho-pedagogical intervention, the inclusive environment may result not in the development of empathy but in the emergence of negative attitudes and stereotypes. Therefore, the study of the mechanisms underlying the manifestation of empathy in various educational contexts constitutes a critically important task in contemporary educational psychology.

This study examines the psychological mechanisms involved in the development of empathy across different educational environments.

Empathy constitutes a complex, multi-component phenomenon encompassing cognitive, emotional, and behavioral dimensions. Cognitive empathy pertains to the understanding of another individual’s emotional state, emotional empathy involves the experience of shared feelings, and behavioral empathy is reflected in the expression of empathetic responses through actions and behaviors [7].

A study conducted by Russian psychologists in 2024 identified significant differences in the development of empathy components among younger primary school students from traditional and inclusive educational settings. The experiment included 320 primary school students from 16 schools across various regions of Russia. The results indicated that children from inclusive classrooms exhibit higher levels of cognitive empathy – they are better able to recognize the emotional states of others and understand the underlying causes of these states [6].

Particularly noteworthy are data on the impact of the duration of studying in an inclusive environment on empathic abilities. Analysis revealed that significant changes in children's empathic profiles occur not immediately, but after two to three years of collaborative learning with children with SEN. This suggests that the development of empathy is a gradual process necessitating extended experience of interaction with diverse categories of peers [2].

Leading experts in educational psychology distinguish several mechanisms through which the inclusive environment affects the development of empathy:

- the mechanism of social learning – observing how teachers and other adults demonstrate care and support towards children with SEN shapes appropriate behavioral models in younger schoolchildren;

- the mechanism of expanding social experience – interaction with children with different developmental features enriches the child's understanding of the diversity of human behaviors;

- the mechanism of emotional contagion – the direct experience of the emotional states of peers with SEN enhances the emotional component of empathy;

- The reflection mechanism – the necessity to reflect on the behavioral characteristics of classmates with SEN – stimulates the development of cognitive empathy.

Simultaneously, researchers note that conditions for the development of empathy also exist in traditional classrooms, albeit of a somewhat different nature. Children in a traditional educational environment predominantly develop empathy through literary works, play activities, and specially organized pedagogical scenarios. This developmental trajectory may be less intensive, yet more manageable and predictable [4].

A critically important factor is the educator's stance. Studies indicate that in inclusive classrooms where the educator exhibits an empathic attitude toward all children without exception, a unique atmosphere of acceptance and support is cultivated. Within such classrooms, empathy levels are considerably higher compared to inclusive settings characterized by a formal approach to the integration of children with SEN [1].

Interesting findings were obtained regarding gender differences in the manifestation of empathy. Girls in both educational environments exhibit higher levels of emotional empathy, whereas boys predominantly demonstrate the cognitive component. However, in inclusive classrooms, these differences are less pronounced, indicating the attenuating effect of joint education with children with SEN on gender stereotypes in empathic responding.

Special attention is given to the analysis of situations in which children exhibit empathy. In traditional classrooms, empathic responses predominantly occur in reaction to conspicuous emotional expressions of peers – such as tears, joy, or hurt feelings. In inclusive classrooms, children develop the ability to perceive more

subtle emotional cues, which is particularly important when interacting with children with developmental disabilities, whose emotional expressions may be atypical.

Comprehending the mechanisms underlying empathy development in diverse educational environments establishes a basis for formulating effective pedagogical strategies. Contemporary Russian schools require scientifically substantiated methods for the development of empathic abilities that consider the specific characteristics of both traditional and inclusive educational environments.

The experience of advanced Russian schools implementing inclusive education demonstrates several effective approaches to fostering empathy. The first approach involves the implementation of specialized psychological training programs and exercises aimed at enhancing emotional intelligence. Such programs include:

- exercises for recognizing emotions through facial expressions, gestures, and vocal intonation;
- role-playing games enabling children to adopt the perspective of another individual;
- discussions of literary works with a focus on the characters' emotional experiences;
- group projects requiring coordination of actions and consideration of the interests of all participants;
- reflective practices aimed at enhancing children's awareness of their own emotional responses.

The second approach is based on establishing an inclusive school culture in which the value of each child is a priority. This is achieved through systematic efforts to foster positive attitudes towards differences and diversity. Key elements of this work include class sessions dedicated to the themes of acceptance and tolerance, joint activities where children with SEN and their typically developing peers participate as equal partners, as well as the use of adapted literature and media materials that present positive representations of individuals with disabilities [6].

A study on the effectiveness of various pedagogical strategies conducted in 2025 demonstrated that the greatest impact is achieved through an integrated approach combining direct instruction in empathy skills with the establishment of a supportive educational environment. Schools implementing this approach demonstrate not only higher empathy levels among students but also a decrease in bullying, an improvement in the psychosocial climate within classrooms, and enhanced academic performance [3].

Cooperation between the school and the family plays a crucial role in the development of empathy. Parents of children studying in inclusive classrooms require psychological support and education regarding the benefits of inclusive education for the development of their children's social-emotional skills. Research indicates that parental attitudes significantly influence the development of empathic abilities:

children of parents who hold positive views towards inclusion demonstrate higher levels of empathy towards peers with SEN.

A promising avenue is the utilization of digital technologies for the development of empathy. Educational games and virtual simulations developed by Russian specialists enable children to acquire experiences of interaction with diverse categories of individuals in a safe digital environment. Such technologies are particularly beneficial for preparing children from traditional classrooms to engage with individuals with developmental disabilities.

An analysis of international and Russian experience allows for the identification of key conditions for the successful development of empathy within the educational environment:

- preparedness of teaching personnel to engage in the development of socio-emotional skills;
- the provision of psychological support throughout the educational process;
- systematic monitoring of the level of empathy development among students;
- integration of empathy development objectives into educational curricula;
- creation of conditions for the practical application of empathic skills in authentic interaction scenarios.

Anticipating the trajectory of development, it can be posited that in the forthcoming years the Russian school system will advance towards a more extensive implementation of inclusive education. This will provide additional opportunities for the development of empathy in the younger generation, but will require considerable efforts in the professional development of educators, the development of methodological support, and the cultivation of an inclusive culture within educational organizations. The success of this process will largely depend on the readiness of the educational community to acknowledge the development of empathy as an objective equally important as the acquisition of disciplinary knowledge and skills.

The conducted analysis of contemporary research and practical experience enables us to draw several important conclusions concerning the features of empathy manifestation in younger schoolchildren within various educational environments. Inclusive education creates unique conditions for the development of children's empathic abilities, fostering a more intensive development of the cognitive component of empathy and broadening the range of empathic responses. At the same time, the mere inclusion of children with SEN in general education classrooms does not guarantee the automatic development of empathy among their neurotypical peers.

A key factor in the effectiveness of the inclusive environment for fostering empathy is targeted psychological and pedagogical intervention, which includes specialized socio-emotional learning programs, the establishment of an inclusive school culture, and the professional development of teaching staff. The traditional educational environment also holds potential for the development of empathy,

although this process requires more active pedagogical intervention and the use of specialized methodological approaches.

The practical significance of the obtained results lies in the possibility of utilizing data on the mechanisms underlying empathy development to enhance the educational process in Russian schools. Understanding the characteristics of empathy manifestation in different educational environments allows for the formulation of differentiated approaches to fostering students' socio-emotional skills, which aligns with the requirements of modern educational standards.

Future research directions should encompass longitudinal studies investigating the influence of inclusive education on the development of empathy throughout the entire school period, examination of the role of various categories of developmental disorders in eliciting empathic responses among peers, as well as the design and empirical validation of evidence-based programs for fostering empathy across different types of educational settings. Of particular importance is the investigation of the cultural specificity of empathy expression within the context of the multinational Russian school, alongside the impact of educational digitalization on the development of empathic abilities in contemporary younger schoolchildren.

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ADDICTION AND VIRTUAL IDENTITY AMONG STUDENTS IN THE DIGITAL ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract. *Annotation. The interrelation of virtual identity and the tendency to dependent behavior of students is considered. The meaningfulness of accepting virtual identity is characterized by a conscious choice of identity. The intensity of the search for virtual identity shows how young people cope with the situation when they encounter difficulties. It was found that when problems arise, young people prefer to immerse themselves in television, immerse themselves in the gaming space, in virtual reality, and social networks. And the resulting anxiety is relieved with the help of medications. In other words, the higher the search activity, the greater the tendency to become addicted to television, computer games, medications, social media, and the digital environment. It was revealed that with a high level of resilience, with its components of engagement, control, and risk-taking, there is a desire for a healthy lifestyle among young people. With a low level of resilience, with its component components of engagement, control, and risk-taking, there is a high activity in the search for virtual identity.*

Key words: *identity, virtual identity, digital environment, addictions, dependent behavior, resilience.*

1. Introduction

The problem of the modern world is becoming a hybrid reality, in which there is a movement from a real environment to a virtual environment. Moreover, the virtual environment is becoming part of today's reality. Researchers are talking about a single ecosystem [1]. Modern youth spends quite a lot of time in a virtual environment. At the same time, the process of identity formation takes place in a new reality, in a new ecosystem. The category of identity was introduced into science by E. Erickson [2]. J. Marcia introduces identity statuses: achieved, predetermined

identity, diffuse identity, and a moratorium on decision-making. Psychologists believe that virtual identity is being formed by analogy with Ego identity [3]. Within the framework of the cultural and historical approach, the source of personal development is the interaction of the subject, mediated by information technologies, with the digital infrastructure. The problem of addictive behavior among young people has remained relevant for many years. Alcohol addiction, drug addiction, and gambling addiction are complex issues that require careful and careful study. Researchers characterize dependent behavior as a variant of deviant behavior, in which attention is fixed and retained on things, facts, and events that become significant. Submission, dependence, lack of freedom in decision-making [4]. A number of authors present studies that examine violations of self-image concepts [5]. Some researchers believe that the immunity of addiction will be a holistic personality with an adequate self-image [6,7]. T. White believes that the use of alcohol, drugs, and certain medications is a way to escape from solving the problem [8].

2. Methods

The aim of the study was to identify the relationship between addiction and the virtual identity of students. The research methodology is based on works studying personal development by L. S. Vygotsky, G. G. Kravtsov, E. E. Kravtsova, the problem of identity formation by E. Erickson, V. S. Agapov, issues of digital socialization by G. U. Soldatova, A. E. Voiskunsky, Rubtsova O. V., M. V. Klementyeva [9, 10, 11, 2, 13, 3]. The following methods were used in the study: to determine virtual identity, the method of M. V. Klementyeva's "VI Status", to identify the propensity for dependent behavior, the method of G. V. Lozova, to identify the level of resilience, the S. Muddy test, adapted by D. A. Leontiev, E. I. Rasskazova. The study involved students of Tula University, 87 people enrolled in 1–2 courses.

3. The results and their discussion

When identifying virtual identity statuses based on the "Status VI" methodology by M. V. Klementyeva, the sample was conditionally divided into four subgroups. The first group of 13.8% of the sample included subjects with achieved virtual identity. The second subgroup (39% of the subjects) included respondents with a predetermined identity, the third subgroup (15% of the subjects) included young people with a virtual identity moratorium, and the fourth subgroup (32.2% of the sample) included students with a diffuse virtual identity. Let's consider the indicators of addiction in four selected subgroups. The first group with a virtual identity is characterized by a tendency to love addiction, food addiction, and dependence on a healthy lifestyle. For the respondents of the second group with a predetermined identity, a tendency to love addiction, food addiction and dependence on a healthy lifestyle was revealed. In other words, respondents need warm, trusting relationships; in stressful situations, the problem is "stuck", and then a regime is established that is aimed at maintaining health and strengthening the body. The respondents of

the third group, the virtual identity moratorium, are characterized by a tendency to love, food and drug addiction. That is, young people also need intimacy, overeat under stressful conditions, and resort to medications to relieve tension. The respondents of the fourth group, with a diffuse virtual identity, are characterized by a tendency to love addiction, dependence on a healthy lifestyle, and a tendency to food addiction. The propensity to depend on computers, virtual networks, and the Internet is most pronounced among the respondents of the first group with achieved virtual identity and among the respondents of the third group with a virtual identity moratorium. Respondents in the fourth group with diffuse virtual identity had the least pronounced tendency to depend on computers and the Internet.

The Pearson correlation coefficient was used to identify the relationship between the values of virtual identity and the values of addiction. There is a statistically significant relationship between the values of virtual identity on the scale of intensity of virtual identity search and the values of propensity to addictive behavior on the scales of television addiction $r = 0.227^*$ (significant at $p < 0.05$), gaming addiction $r = 0.269^*$ (significant at $p < 0.05$), drug addiction $r = 0.271^*$ (significant at $p < 0.05$), dependence on the Internet $r = 0.383^{**}$ (significant at $p < 0.01$). In other words, the higher the search activity, the greater the tendency to become addicted to television, computer games, medications, social media, and the digital environment. The relationship between the values of virtual identity on the scale of meaningfulness of identity acceptance and the values of propensity to addictive behavior has not been identified. Thus, the meaningfulness of the adoption of virtual identity is characterized by a conscious choice of identity. The intensity of the search for virtual identity shows how young people cope with the situation when they encounter difficulties. It was found that when problems arise, young people prefer to immerse themselves in television, immerse themselves in the gaming space, in virtual reality, and social networks. And the resulting anxiety is relieved with the help of medications. Considering the correlation coefficients between the values of resilience and the values of addiction, the following results were obtained.

A statistically significant inversely proportional relationship was found between the values of resilience on the engagement scale and indicators of addiction to dependent behavior on the scales of alcohol dependence $r = -0.354^{**}$ (significant at $p < 0.01$), dependence on TV $r = -0.419^{**}$ (significant at $p < 0.01$), food $r = -0.282^*$ (significant at $p < 0.05$), drug dependence $r = -0.313^{**}$ (significant at $p < 0.01$) and general tendency to addictive behavior $r = -0.408^{**}$ (significant at $p < 0.01$). That is, the more involved young people are, the less likely they are to engage in addictive behavior, and the less likely respondents are to avoid solving problems through alcohol, television, binge eating, and taking medications to relieve tension. A statistically significant inversely proportional relationship was revealed between the values of resilience on the control scale and the values of

addiction on the alcohol scales $r = -0.416^{**}$ (significant at $p < 0.01$), television $r = -0.509^{**}$ (significant at $p < 0.01$), gaming $r = -0.248^*$ (significant at $p < 0.05$), food $r = -0.322^{**}$ (significant at $p < 0.01$), drug dependence $r = -0.398^{**}$ (significant at $p < 0.01$), smoking dependence $r = -0.267^*$ (significant at $p < 0.05$), drug dependence $r = -0.250^*$ (significant at $p < 0.05$), the overall tendency to addiction is $r = -0.495^{**}$ (significant at $p < 0.01$). That is, the higher the control, the less the tendency to addictive behavior.

There is a statistically significant inversely proportional relationship between the values of resilience on the risk acceptance scale and the values of propensity to addictive behavior on the scales alcohol $r = -0.392^{**}$ (significant at $p < 0.01$), television dependence $r = -0.413^{**}$ (significant at $p < 0.01$), dependence on intersexual relations $r = -0.267^*$ (significant at $p < 0.05$), food $r = -0.293^{**}$ (significant at $p < 0.01$), drug dependence $r = -0.427^{**}$ (significant at $p < 0.01$), dependence on smoking $r = -0.263^*$ (significant at $p < 0.05$) and the general tendency to dependence $r = -0.418^{**}$ (significant at $p < 0.01$). That is, the higher the propensity to risk, the lower the propensity to engage in addictive behavior. A direct statistically significant relationship was revealed between the values of propensity to dependent behavior on the scale of dependence on a healthy lifestyle and the values of resilience on the scales of involvement $r = 0.465^{**}$ (significant at $p < 0.01$), control $r = 0.306^{**}$ (significant at $p < 0.01$), risk acceptance $r = 0.264^*$ (significant at $p < 0.05$). That is, the higher the resilience and its components of engagement, control, and risk-taking, the greater the desire for a healthy lifestyle among young people.

Considering the correlation coefficients between the values of virtual identity (VI) and resilience, the following results were obtained. There is a statistically significant inversely proportional relationship between the values of virtual identity on the scale of intensity of virtual identity search and the values of resilience on the scales of engagement $r = -0.301^{**}$ (significant at $p < 0.01$), control $r = -0.254^*$ (significant at $p < 0.05$), risk acceptance $r = -0.230^*$ (significant at $p < 0.05$). That is, the lower the resilience and its components of engagement, control, and risk acceptance, the more active the search for a virtual identity is.

4. Conclusions

Thus, the respondents of the first group with achieved virtual identity are active in a virtual environment, taking into account awareness of their preferences, values, and meanings. In terms of addiction to the Internet and social networks, respondents are the most active compared to the other three representatives of the selected subgroups. That is, being in a digital environment is enjoyable and emphasizes self-expression. Representatives of the third group, with a moratorium, who are also active in a virtual environment, are active in self-knowledge, self-presentation, but are not ready to accept their own virtual identity, and are also prone to dependence on computers, social networks, and the Internet. The respondents of the second

group with a predetermined virtual identity are uninitiative, but uncritically accept their virtual identity, are less prone to Internet addiction, that is, young people are not involved in self-discovery of virtual identity, they do not enjoy being in a digital environment. Representatives of the fourth group with diffuse virtual identity are characterized by passivity, senseless adaptation to the digital environment, are not prone to dependence on the Internet, computer, that is, young people are not aware of their virtual identity. The propensity for love addiction is most pronounced among representatives of all four groups. This aspect is related to the task of establishing intimacy in this age category- youth, when a partner is chosen and a trusting relationship is established. Thus, with a high level of resilience, with its components of engagement, control, and risk-taking, there is a desire for a healthy lifestyle among young people. With a low level of resilience, with its component components of engagement, control, and risk-taking, there is a high activity in the search for virtual identity.

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ASSESSMENT OF ADAPTIVE ABILITIES BY MIGRANTS WITH FORCED AND VOLUNTARY RELOCATION

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Annotation. *This article examines the degree of adaptation and signs of maladjustment among migrants with forced and voluntary resettlement, conducts a comparative analysis of psychological defenses and adaptation strategies in a new culture, and considers possible variable factors that act as catalysts for maladjustment in both categories of migrants.*

Keywords: *signs of maladjustment, migrants, voluntary migrants, forced migrants.*

The relevance of studying maladaptive manifestations among migrants with forced and voluntary resettlement is driven by the growing migration flows in the modern world. Some move to another country for work or study, some follow their families, and some, unfortunately, are forced to seek asylum due to problems in their homeland [4]. And although voluntary migrants' initial expectations regarding the move may be positive, in reality they will be forced to face difficulties in adapting to a different sociocultural environment, which may differ significantly from the one to which they are accustomed. Both categories of migrants face various challenges in adapting to their new living environment.

Forced migrants, such as refugees, often face additional challenges related to traumatic experiences, the loss of social ties, and cultural identity [3]. Voluntary migrants, although they make the decision to relocate, may also experience significant difficulties in the process of adapting to a new environment [1], which can lead to various psychological disorders. Thus, studying these processes is crucial for understanding the factors influencing the mental health of migrants.

Problems of maladjustment among migrants can manifest in various forms, including depression, anxiety disorders, social isolation, and other mental disorders [2]. These problems not only negatively affect the quality of life of the migrants themselves but can also impact their families and local communities. Understanding the mechanisms of adaptation and risk factors associated with migration is key to developing effective support and intervention programs. Research on maladjustment among various groups of migrants will help identify specific needs and develop targeted assistance strategies that promote successful integration into the new society.

The aim of this study was to examine signs of maladjustment among migrants who had relocated either voluntarily or involuntarily.

The study included 40 participants (8 men and 32 women) aged 19 to 55. The participants were divided into two groups based on migration type. The first group consisted of migrants who voluntarily left their homeland, and the second group consisted of migrants who were forced to leave their homeland. Migrants who voluntarily decided to move abroad included: labor/study migrants and family migrants. Migrants who were forced to move abroad included: refugees and family migrants who were forced to move with their families.

In accordance with the research topic and objectives, the following psychodiagnostic methods were used: the Multilevel Personality Questionnaire (MPQ) “Adaptability” (MPQ; authors: A. G. Maklakov and S. V. Chermnyanin, 1993), the “Lifestyle Index” method (LSI; authors: R. Plutchik, G. Kellerman, H. R. Conte, 1979), the Social-Psychological Adaptation Questionnaire by C. Rogers and R. Diamond (SPA; authors: Carl Rogers and R. Diamond, 1954; Adaptation: A. K. Osnitsky, 2004).

To determine the adaptive abilities of individuals in groups of voluntary and forced migrants, a frequency analysis was conducted using the 4th-level scale of the MIO “Adaptability” methodology; the data are presented (Fig. 1, Fig. 2).

Fig. 1 – Groups (levels) of adaptive abilities among voluntary migrants
Note: group 3 – low adaptive abilities; group 4 – maladaptation (very low adaptive abilities).

Based on the data obtained, it can be concluded that 50% of voluntary migrants belong to the group with low adaptive abilities (Fig. 1). This category is characterized by pronounced personality accentuations and certain traits approaching psychopathic tendencies, which may indicate a borderline level of functioning. Adaptation in such individuals is accompanied by significant difficulties, often accompanied by the risk of neuropsychological breakdowns and the development of persistent functional impairments. Reduced neuropsychological resilience, increased sensitivity to stress, and difficulties in self-regulation are observed.

The remaining 50% of voluntary migrants demonstrate a relatively satisfactory level of adaptive abilities. While they possess accentuated personality traits, the severity of these traits varies depending on external conditions: in a stable environment, they may be compensated for, but in stressful situations, they may intensify. Socialization among members of this group proceeds with difficulties; situational manifestations of deviant behavior are possible, as well as episodes of heightened conflict and aggressive reactions (Fig. 1).

Fig. 2 – Groups (levels) of adaptive abilities among forced migrants

Note: group 2 – satisfactory (moderate) adaptive abilities; group 3 – low adaptive abilities; group 4 – maladaptation (very low adaptive abilities).

Analysis of the data obtained for the second group showed that 60% of forced migrants demonstrate a low level of adaptive potential, characterized by the features previously described in the context of migrants who relocated voluntarily.

About 30% of respondents among forced migrants demonstrated a satisfactory level of adaptive abilities. Despite the presence of personality accentuations, their manifestations are partially mitigated in a stable environment but can significantly intensify under stressful conditions. The adaptive resources of this group depend on the influence of the external environment, and the socialization process is accompanied by difficulties manifested in increased conflict, episodes of antisocial

behavior, and aggressive reactions. Thus, the integration process for this category of migrants is characterized by instability and the risk of maladaptive reactions.

The remaining 10% of forced migrants demonstrated a high level of adaptive capacity. These study participants are characterized by marked emotional stability, low levels of conflict, and the ability to effectively develop behavioral strategies in new conditions. Adaptation among members of this group proceeds successfully: they integrate quickly into society, maintain functional stability, and demonstrate a satisfactory level of socio-psychological adaptation even in the face of change.

Frequency analysis using the first-level scale of the Multilevel Personality Questionnaire (MPQ) "Adaptability" showed that predominantly high values are observed on some scales, which may indicate the presence of pronounced accentuations among the study participants. This suggests that these characteristics play a significant role in the adaptation process. The depression and psychasthenia scales draw particular attention, as 70% and 40% of voluntary migrants, respectively, fall outside the normative range on these scales, indicating at least a clear character accentuation. It should be noted that for 30% of them, the values on these scales reach a psychopathological level.

A similar pattern is observed in the personality profile of forced relocators. For the overwhelming majority, scores on the depression scale (D) are high (80%), exceeding 70 T-scores and indicating the presence of marked accentuation, reaching psychopathological levels in some respondents. High scores are also found on the psychasthenia (Pt) scale in 40% of forced migrants, and on the hypochondriasis (Hs), paranoia (Pa), and hypomania (Ma) scales in 30%. This pattern indicates the presence of clear signs of maladjustment in the majority of this group, manifested by pronounced anxiety, an anxious perception of the environment and oneself, feelings of fear and restlessness, low self-esteem, heightened guilt, and feelings of depression and despondency.

Thus, the results obtained using this methodology indicate that for the majority of both migrant groups, the adaptation process is proceeding unfavorably; they are characterized by a low level of adaptive potential, and many exhibit signs of distinct personality accentuations, which in some cases reach the level of psychopathology.

To identify the characteristics of psychological defense mechanisms among groups of voluntary and forced migrants, a comparative analysis was conducted using the "Lifestyle Index" (LSI) methodology; the results are presented in Table 1.

A comparative analysis between the group of voluntary migrants and the group of forced migrants revealed a significant difference at the $p \leq 0.05$ level on the "Repression" scale. Voluntary migrants are more inclined to suppress emotionally significant experiences, which may be due to their perception of bearing significant responsibility not only for their own well-being but also for fulfilling

their expectations related to the migration process. This situation requires “ignoring” or “refusing” to acknowledge the existence of difficulties in adapting to the destination country, since such difficulties contradict their original intentions and plans for relocation. At the same time, the second group of respondents consisted of forced migrants, who are less likely to resort to a defense mechanism such as repression. This may be due to the fact that, unlike voluntary migrants, they did not have expectations regarding the country of relocation.

Table 1. Results of the comparative analyses using the “Lifestyle Index” (LSI) methodology

“Lifestyle Index” (LSI) methodology	Voluntary (n=20)	Forced (n=20)	Mann-Whitney U test	Significance level p
	M ±m	M ±m		
Repression	63,2±28,38	45,9±29,31	124	P≤0,05

The results of the comparative analysis using the “Diagnosis of Socio-Psychological Adaptation” methodology are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Results of the comparative analyses using the “Social-Psychological Adaptation Questionnaire by C. Rogers and R. Diamond” (SPA)

“Social-Psychological Adaptation Questionnaire by C. Rogers and R. Diamond” (SPA)	Voluntary (n=20)	Forced (n=20)	Mann-Whitney U test	Significance level p
	M ±m	M ±m		
“Dominance” subscale	9,8±3,3	8,1±4,64	134	
“Submissiveness” subscale	20,3±5,84	16,1±6,08	120	P≤0,05
“Dominance” scale	79±6,68	73,9±6,4	92	P≤0,01

A comparative analysis between the group of voluntary migrants and the group of forced migrants revealed a significant difference at the $p \leq 0.01$ level on the “Dominance” scale and a significant difference at the $p \leq 0.05$ level on the “Submissiveness” subscale. Voluntary migrants are more inclined toward a submissive style of behavior. The “Submissiveness” subscale is part of the “Dominance” scale, and the primary psychological defenses among voluntary migrants are repression, compensation, and denial; it can be said that the subjects attempt to cope with feelings of anxiety through strict self-control and the use of a “social mask”. Most likely, this behavior may be linked to a strong sense of responsibility toward oneself and others for one’s choice regarding relocation; it may also be linked to a lack of external support. Although both categories of migrants are forced to adapt to new conditions, society seems to place greater pressure on voluntary migrants

regarding how their integration should proceed, since few people consider that the difficulty of the adaptation process depends not only on existential threats.

The results of the study indicate that both categories of migrants attempt to present a more favorable process of adaptation to the new environment by resorting to the use of “social masks” to demonstrate success. This state cannot be called genuine, because the behavior that migrants try to project outwardly contradicts the identified level of their adaptive abilities; the majority of respondents have either satisfactory or reduced adaptive abilities. This discrepancy between migrants’ subjective positive assessment of their condition and the results of their actual condition may be linked to high indicators of psychological defense mechanisms, particularly repression (60% of voluntary migrants have high scores) and denial (high scores among 60% of migrants who were forced to relocate).

Despite differing motives for relocation and the defense mechanisms employed, both voluntary and forced migrants face pronounced adaptation challenges, underscoring the need for psychological support tailored to the specific experiences of each group.

The study of maladaptive manifestations among migrants who have undergone forced and voluntary resettlement allows for a deeper understanding of the processes affecting mental health and the characteristics of individual adaptation in the context of a changing sociocultural environment. Analysis of these manifestations helps identify factors that hinder or, conversely, facilitate the successful integration of migrants into a new society. The data obtained indicate the need not only for psychoprophylactic measures but also for targeted psychoprophylactic measures and, in some cases, intervention measures aimed at supporting the mental health of migrants. Further research into signs of maladjustment among forced and voluntary migrants may be useful for developing more effective methods to facilitate the smoother integration of migrants into a new sociocultural environment and for developing more effective methods to prevent the development of signs of maladjustment among migrants, as well as to assist those who have already encountered this problem.

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STUDENT AND AI: DIGITAL CO-AUTHORSHIP IN EDUCATIONAL AND PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITIES

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Abstract. *This article examines the phenomenon of transformation in students' educational and professional activities amid the integration of generative neural networks. The notion of "delegation of meaning-making" is introduced and clarified as a key mechanism in human–algorithm interaction. The dual nature of this partnership is analyzed: on one hand, AI serves as a tool for optimizing cognitive load by facilitating rapid information processing and reducing anxiety; on the other, it poses risks to the individual's agentic position, fostering dependence on algorithmic interpretations and undermining students' critical thinking autonomy. The paper presents results from an empirical typology of students based on their degree of cognitive autonomy, alongside a comparative analysis of traditional (e.g., note-taking, bibliographic search) and digital strategies for working with information. Issues concerning the psychological safety of the educational environment are examined, with particular focus on preserving personal agency within the framework of AI "co-authorship." Finally, recommendations for preserving cognitive autonomy in the context of co-authorship with AI are proposed.*

Keywords: *student, artificial intelligence, co-authorship, psychological safety, agency, educational and professional activity, delegation of meaning-making, digital dependence.*

Introduction

Contemporary higher education is undergoing a stage of profound technological transformation driven by the widespread adoption of generative neural networks. Tools such as GPT models and their equivalents represent not merely an incremental step in digitalization, but a qualitative leap in the organization of cognitive activity. Unlike previous technological innovations-ranging from the invention of writing to

internet search engines-generative artificial intelligence (AI) claims not only to store and retrieve information but also to generate meanings. This raises fundamentally new questions for pedagogical science concerning the boundaries of authorship, the nature of academic motivation, and the preservation of critical thinking [2, 8].

For students working with ever-expanding bodies of scientific literature, AI has become an everyday tool that optimizes routine processes, from source retrieval to structuring term papers and theses. However, the rapid integration of these technologies into the educational environment is accompanied by a number of psychological and pedagogical contradictions that warrant scholarly examination. The relevance of this topic is determined by the need to resolve the conflict between the evident pragmatic benefits of AI (speed, accessibility, and reduced time and effort) and the potential risks to the cognitive development and professional identity of students as future educators.

The aim of this article is to analyze the phenomenon of perceiving artificial intelligence as a “co-author” in students’ educational and professional activities through the lens of the concept of “delegation of meaning-making”. The specific objectives of the study are to: (1) specify what the concept of “delegation of meaning-making” entails in the context of educational and professional activity; (2) identify the typological characteristics of students’ interaction with AI; (3) analyze the risks and opportunities associated with this interaction for the preservation of agency and cognitive autonomy; and (4) develop recommendations for the ethically responsible and pedagogically sound use of generative neural networks in higher education.

In contemporary scientific and pedagogical discourse on the role of AI in education, several conceptual approaches can be distinguished. The first, an instrumentalist approach, views neural networks as advanced analogs of calculators or search engines – that is, as tools for performing technical operations that do not fundamentally alter the nature of the cognitive process. The second, a “hybrid” or “symbiotic” approach (presented in the works of D. I. Zemtsov and I. A. Gruzdev), employs the metaphor of the “digital centaur” to describe a new type of distributed cognitive system. In this system, humans and algorithms jointly solve educational tasks, with the boundaries between their respective contributions becoming blurred [1, 10]. The third approach, developed within the framework of the philosophy of dialogue (A. D. Korol), calls into question the very possibility of “co-authorship” in the strict sense, pointing to the fundamental absence of an internal space of meanings in AI, which renders impossible any genuinely dialogic interaction between the student and AI based on their value-semantic reflection [5].

Empirical studies conducted at HSE University (National Research University Higher School of Economics) indicate a gradual transformation in students’

perception of AI: from an “instrument” (a technical tool) to a “helper,” and subsequently to a “co-author” [7]. A key factor driving this transformation is the conflict-free nature of the interaction. Specifically, AI is available 24/7, does not exhibit negative emotions, offers no criticism, and creates no social barriers in communication. This fosters a sense of psychological and emotional comfort for the student. However, as noted by S. I. Chernykh, it is precisely this shift into a “comfort zone” that lays the groundwork for delegating not only technical but also semantic functions to the algorithm [3, 9].

In the context of educational and professional activity, “delegation of meaning-making” can be defined as a process wherein a student entrusts artificial intelligence not only with the execution of routine operations (search, systematization, formatting) but also delegates certain cognitive functions associated with constructing logical connections, formulating conclusions, and interpreting information during educational and professional activities.

As noted by A. D. Kushkin, M. M. Chernitsyna and O. V. Galkina, this phenomenon differs qualitatively from the traditional use of reference materials or consultations with instructors. In the classical educational model, the student remains the primary agent of meaning-making. However, the use of generative neural networks brings about a fundamental shift in the cognitive architecture of learning activities: an external algorithm begins to perform functions that previously required internal cognitive effort [6].

In this context, it is important to distinguish between two strategies of student interaction with AI, namely: strategic optimization, when a student consciously chooses which tasks to delegate to AI (such as source retrieval and structuring) to free up time and resources for more complex operations (analysis, synthesis, and the formulation of original ideas), and passive consumption, which involves the automatic offloading of cognitive labor onto the algorithm without subsequent reflection, leading to the formation of “cognitive dependence” [3, 4, 7].

We conducted a pilot study involving first- to third-year students at Voronezh State Pedagogical University. Seventy-five pre-service teachers responded to several questions regarding their use of AI in their educational and professional activities. The results allowed us to distinguish three student groups based on their level of preserved cognitive autonomy:

1. “Autonomous Researcher” (approximately 20% of the sample). These students use AI episodically and exclusively for technical tasks (e.g., source retrieval and grammar checking). At the same time, they maintain full control over meaning-making, critically evaluate AI-generated responses, and treat AI as a reference tool rather than a source of ready-made solutions.

2. “Selective Delegator” (approximately 45% of the sample). These students selectively delegate specific functions—primarily routine tasks such as text structuring

and draft generation-to AI, while still reflecting on the final output. Although they are aware of the associated risks, they do not always actively mitigate them. A characteristic attitude among these students is that “AI helps formulate thoughts, but the final decision is mine.”

3. “Passive Recipient” (approximately 35% of the sample). These students perceive AI responses as ready-made solutions requiring minimal refinement. This group is characterized by low levels of reflection, a tendency to copy generated texts with only minor editing, and infrequent verification of information accuracy. In this group, the phenomenon of “delegation of meaning-making” is most pronounced in its destructive form.

Our findings correlate with international studies identifying similar types of student agency in AI-supported environments, ranging from “self-sufficient users” to “uncritical users” with reduced agency [4].

The active use of AI in educational and professional activities entails a transformation of habitual cognitive models. Traditional educational practices—such as note-taking, engaging with printed sources, and independently formulating conclusions—served an important psychophysiological function for students. Mechanical actions (e.g., copying out, underlining) were accompanied by sustained attention and repeated exposure to the material, thereby facilitating information retention through motor and visual memory. The process of searching library catalogs was itself an integral part of learning, fostering a broad contextual framework and enabling the formation of unexpected semantic connections. Currently, with the use of AI, this stage is excluded. Students receive a pre-synthesized output, which, on one hand, allows for a broader contextual overview, but on the other, reduces the depth of subject matter immersion. As D. B. Kumakhova notes, the phenomenon of “digital amnesia” emerges: students who actively use AI assistants demonstrate a decline in long-term memory retention and reduced ability to systematize knowledge, alongside heightened working memory efficiency. The brain, as an energy-efficient system, tends to follow the path of least resistance: if information is readily accessible via an AI query, the necessity of encoding it into long-term memory is diminished.

The question of preserving students’ agentic position causes particular concern among university faculty. In the educational context, agency is understood as an integrative personality quality that characterizes the capacity to act as an active, conscious, and responsible author; to set goals independently; to choose one’s learning trajectory; and to bear responsibility for outcomes [8]. Excessive delegation of functions to AI creates a threat of replacing student agency with algorithmic dependence, manifesting in:

- the formation of “pseudo-autonomy,” in which students limit themselves to adapting ready-made solutions;

- “delegated responsibility,” where blame for errors is shifted onto an impersonal machine;
- the impoverishment of original thinking and the standardization of style and logic in academic works [2,3].

Currently, it can be argued that the academic community’s reaction to the expansion of generative AI has evolved through several stages: from denial and total prohibition to the recognition of the inevitability of integration and the search for forms of “co-evolution” between humans and machines [1]. Today, the key challenge lies in establishing transparent rules for AI use that preserve students’ academic integrity without abandoning technological advantages.

As demonstrated in pedagogical research, the adoption of institutional policies regarding AI use-encompassing principles of academic integrity, critical analysis, personal responsibility, and transparency-helps reduce confrontation between students and faculty [8]. An effective model appears to be one in which AI is used for idea generation, structuring, and editing, while the final product and accountability for it remain with the student. This aligns with the principle of “asymmetric contribution,” wherein the human performs creative and evaluative functions, while the algorithm handles only operational tasks [1].

For teacher education, where the future teacher must possess well-developed reflective abilities, an authorial stance, and unique professional vision, the preservation of agency in the context of “co-authorship” with AI takes on particular significance. Preparing educators who are capable not only of using digital tools but also of critically reflecting on the boundaries of their application is becoming one of the priority tasks of modern teacher education.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Our analysis allows us to conclude that artificial intelligence has become a significant participant in students’ educational and professional activities, and the phenomenon of perceiving it as a “co-author” reflects profound changes in the organization of the cognitive process. “Delegation of meaning-making” emerges as a key mechanism of this interaction, carrying both the potential for optimizing educational and professional activities and risks for the cognitive development of future educators. The psychological safety of the educational environment in the context of generative neural network integration depends directly on the student’s ability to maintain an agentic position, critically evaluate algorithmic outputs, and acknowledge the boundaries of their application. To achieve this balance in the university educational process, the following practical recommendations are proposed:

1. Implementation of the “draft principle”— students use AI to generate their own ideas, plans, and preliminary text versions, with mandatory subsequent revision and critical evaluation of the results.

2. Preservation of traditional practices – instructors should intentionally incorporate AI-free tasks into the curriculum (e.g., handwritten note-taking, reading original sources) to train cognitive endurance.

3. Mastery of reflective practices – students should engage in various reflective practices to regularly examine their motives for using AI (e.g., “Am I using it to accomplish more, or to exert less effort?”).

4. Development of critical thinking – students are encouraged to perceive AI responses as hypotheses requiring verification, rather than as ultimate truths.

5. Formation of an ethical stance – clear delineation of areas where AI use is permissible (search, structuring, technical editing) and where it is impermissible (formulating personal conclusions, ethical assessments, clinical interpretations).

Consequently, further research should focus on developing methods for integrating AI into the educational process that ensure not a reduction, but an enhancement of students’ cognitive potential, as well as on studying the long-term effects of “digital co-authorship” on the professional development of future educators.

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ECOLOGY OF INTERPERSONAL RELATIONS AS A COMPONENT OF CORPORATE CULTURE: FACTORS OF FORMATION

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Abstract. *The article examines the phenomenon of the ecology of interpersonal relations within the context of corporate culture in a commercial organization. Based on a theoretical analysis of domestic and international studies, the content of the concept of «ecological interpersonal relationships» is elucidated, and the key factors contributing to their formation are identified: respect, equality, safety, and trust. It is demonstrated that ecological interpersonal relationships constitute an integral component of modern corporate culture, shaping the psychological climate, employee engagement, and business effectiveness. The principles and practices of establishing an ecological environment within the organization are examined, alongside the role of leadership in developing a system of ecological interpersonal relationships. The results of sociological research are presented, confirming employees' demand for a psychologically safe and respectful work atmosphere. It is concluded that the implementation of an ecological approach to personnel management is necessary as a factor of sustainable organizational development.*

Keywords: *ecology of interpersonal relations, corporate culture, formation factors, respect, trust, psychological safety, ecological personnel management.*

Introduction

Amid the transformation of modern business, corporate culture has ceased to be merely an HR strategy and has become a vital factor in competitiveness. Ten years ago, ecology was primarily associated with environmental protection. Currently, this term is increasingly employed in the context of corporate culture: companies seek to establish 'ecological' interpersonal relationships within teams, considering not only business processes but also the emotional well-being of employees [1; 2].

Employees' expectations of employers have undergone fundamental changes. While bonuses and social benefits were previously regarded as motivating factors, intangible incentives now take precedence. A McKinsey study revealed

that 89% of employees expect not only financial incentives from the company but also a comfortable atmosphere, respectful attitude, and psychological safety [3]. This trend is confirmed by the practices of leading corporations such as Google, Netflix, and Amazon, which invest in creating a comfortable environment for employees by implementing internal survey systems and principles of ‘feedback without fear.’

In this context, the scientific conceptualization of the ecology of interpersonal relationships as a component of corporate culture is increasingly relevant, along with the identification of factors that facilitate its formation. The purpose of this article is to determine, through theoretical analysis, the essence of ecological interpersonal relationships within organizations, to identify the key factors influencing their formation, and to substantiate the role of an ecological corporate culture in improving business effectiveness.

The concept of ecological interpersonal relationships in an organization

The term ‘ecology’ (from the Greek *oikos* – house, dwelling) was introduced by E. Haeckel in 1866 as the science of the interactions among living organisms and between organisms and their environment. Based on this definition, ecology may be appropriately applied to interpersonal relationships, particularly within the context of an organization, which can be considered an ecosystem in which each employee interacts with colleagues, management, and the work environment.

In contemporary Russian psychology, the concept of ‘ecological relationships’ is actively explored by A. S. Gorbatova, S. A. Ozerova, S. A. Sovelyeva, M. Komissarova, S. V. Ivanov, and other researchers. **A.S. Gorbatova** defines ecological relationships as those that provide a sense of confidence, tranquility, and joy, do not produce internal discomfort, and enable an individual to be themselves. Such relationships are characterized by empathy, respect for the needs and concerns of others, a desire to grow, contribute, and reach consensus, the ability to communicate without causing harm to others, to understand and accept one’s own feelings, as well as the ability to perceive the feelings of others [4].

S. A. Ozerova provides a broader definition: ecology of relationships is a set of concepts, attitudes, skills, and practices aimed at preserving and developing relationships across various life contexts. This approach is founded on the idea that interpersonal relationships are an end in themselves, rather than a means, requiring constant care and balance [5].

M. Komissarova (consulting psychologist) highlights the ecology of relationships as a form of respectful, benevolent, and honest interaction with others that is free from ‘toxic elements.’ In her view, such relationships foster personal development and help bring out the best qualities in one another [6].

In the context of corporate culture, the concept of ‘ecological interpersonal relationships within the collective’ denotes the existence of a trustful atmosphere where

each team member feels safe, valued, and heard. This interaction is founded on mutual understanding, respect, empathy, and the willingness to support one another [7].

Factors influencing the formation of ecological relationships

Analysis of the literature highlights four key factors underpinning ecological relationships. These factors are universal for all social groups, including labor collectives.

Respect

Respect is demonstrated through the ability to value each other's viewpoints, opinions, beliefs, and decisions. This pertains to the establishment and observance of boundaries, as well as the capacity to listen and show genuine interest in the opinions of others. Within an ecological collective, each employee can freely express their thoughts, share ideas, and make suggestions without fear of adverse reactions from colleagues or management. As noted by S. V. Sofieva, 'ecological collectives are distinguished by an environment in which everyone is able to voice their thoughts or present ideas and proposals.' Every thought has the right to be heard, and every initiative has the right to be considered" [7].

Equality

Equality presupposes joint decision-making or reaching an agreement on how decisions will be made. All parties involved in the relationship have an equal right to express their opinions. The principle 'I'm OK – You're OK' forms the basis of ecological relationships. In commercial organizations, this is expressed in leaders refraining from an authoritarian stance and instead acting as facilitators who consider the opinions of subordinates. As S. A. Sovelyeva notes, 'Ecological relationships are those in which my interests matter, but the interests, values, needs, and attitudes of the other person are equally important as mine' [8].

Safety

Safety entails the assurance that the participants in relationships will not intentionally inflict harm on each other – whether physical, emotional, psychological, or otherwise. It represents mutual care and concern for shared well-being. Safety also involves the acceptance of ongoing interactions: no individual is coerced into actions against their will, nor are they held accountable in the event of refusal. A crucial phase in the construction of safety is the establishment of boundaries – a method to articulate one's needs and signal when circumstances are uncomfortable or inappropriate. Psychological safety in the workplace is becoming one of the principal requirements of contemporary employees [4; 8].

Trust

Trust is the confidence that participants in the relationship express their true thoughts, do not manipulate one another, do not mislead, and do not exploit each other for personal gain. In a commercial organization, trust is demonstrated when employees can rely on one another, and management does not engage in hidden

control or manipulation. To build trusting relationships, it is important to articulate terms and reach agreements at the outset, which in the business environment are manifested in clear job descriptions, KPIs, and regular feedback [4; 7].

Additional principles of ecological interpersonal relationships

Apart from the four fundamental factors, researchers highlight several additional principles that contribute to the sustainability of ecological interpersonal relationships.

Balance of exchange— a conscious effort to both give and receive within relationships. If this balance is disrupted (giving more than receiving), discontent increases. Within an organization, this pertains to both material compensation and emotional support, recognition of achievements, and assistance in challenging situations.

Honesty and openness— explanation and clarification without humiliation. Communication transparency preserves relationships. As noted by O. Savolko-va: ‘honestly and directly explain why you are delayed, why you do not wish to perform a task.’ This is important, and therefore also significant for you, if these relationships are valuable to you” [9].

The presence of clear boundaries— temporal, spatial, material, as well as boundaries of ‘I–you,’ ‘me–you,’ and ‘we–not-we.’ Within corporate culture, this is expressed through the demarcation of work and personal time, respect for breaks, and non-interference in private life without consent.

Autonomy— the psychological readiness for separateness, the capacity to merge and separate. Within a team, it is important that employees can work both independently and collaboratively without losing their individual identity. “We do well together and we do well individually” – this principle fosters a healthy atmosphere [9].

Ecological interpersonal relationships as an element of corporate culture

The corporate culture of a modern company cannot be regarded as fully developed without a formed system of ecological interpersonal relationships. This is confirmed by both theoretical research and the practical experience of successful organizations.

According to the Gallup report, companies with high employee engagement are 21% more profitable than their competitors, while their employee turnover rate is on average 59% lower [3]. Engagement, in turn, directly depends on the quality of interpersonal relationships within the team, the level of trust in management, and the sense of psychological safety.

According to data from the startup Tabit, companies that utilize systems for assessing the emotional state of employees (such as the Lüscher test) reduce employee turnover by 15–20% and increase engagement by 30% [2]. This indicates that monitoring the emotional climate and focused efforts to foster ecological interpersonal relationships produce a measurable economic effect.

A study conducted by E. A. Petryakova (Astrakhan State Technical University) revealed that more than 70% of surveyed employees report a lack of an ecological approach to personnel management in their organizations. Furthermore, 89% of respondents emphasize the importance of implementing such an approach and creating a comfortable working environment. The primary challenges employees identify in their work are ‘disorganized and distorted information transmission’ (40%), ‘unclear interpretation of tasks from management’ (28%), and ‘ambiguous structure of interdepartmental relationships’ (35%) [10].

Ecological human resource management

In response to these challenges, a new managerial paradigm is emerging – ecological human resource management. E. A. Petryakova defines it as the most optimal method for forming the working environment and the interaction between managers and employees, in which the resources of both the team and each individual employee are maximally preserved and enhanced, enabling the full achievement of the objectives of both the organization and each employee [10].

The author distinguishes a three-level system of the working environment:

1. **Activity level**– active engagement of employees directed towards achieving significant objectives. The nature of interaction must be subject-subject, grounded in mutual respect and an understanding of the value of each individual.

2. **Communicative-communication level**– formal and informal informational flows. Continuity, reliability, accessibility, and synchronicity of communication are essential, along with healthy interpersonal communication free from manipulation and rumors.

3. **Situational level** – consideration of specific circumstances and selection of optimal management methods that preserve employee resources.

The principles of ecologically oriented personnel management include: democratic approach, systematic approach, optimality, situationality, openness, adequacy, and humanity [10].

Methods for the formation of ecological interpersonal relationships within an organization

The following methods can be employed to create and maintain ecological interpersonal relationships within a team:

1. **Formation of a culture of openness** – establishing conditions that encourage employees to share their thoughts and feelings (regular meetings, anonymous surveys, ‘idea boxes’).

2. **Organizing team events**– team-building activities, corporate events, informal lunches, joint volunteer projects.

3. **Training in communication skills**– workshops on effective communication, active listening, constructive criticism, nonviolent communication (according to M. Rosenberg).

4. **Supporting personal growth**– providing opportunities for learning, development, and acquisition of new skills.

5. **Regular feedback**– implementation of the eNPS system (Employee Net Promoter Score), one-on-one meetings, anonymous satisfaction surveys.

6. **Respect for boundaries** – observance of employees’ personal boundaries, non-interference in private life without consent, adherence to working hours and breaks [7].

The leader plays a special role. As S. V. Sofieva notes, ‘an ecological leader is capable of perceiving and understanding employees’ emotions, modifying their actions and behavioral approach accordingly. This sensitivity and the ability to perceive the unspoken determine the extent to which communication within the team will be ecological’ [7].

Effects of ecological interpersonal relationships on business

The formation of ecological interpersonal relationships as a component of corporate culture yields multiple positive effects:

- **Improvement of the organizational climate** – employees experience comfort and safety, which enhances productivity and job satisfaction.

- **Stress reduction** – emotional support and mutual understanding among colleagues decrease levels of professional burnout.

- **Enhancement of loyalty** – within an atmosphere of respect, employees become more committed to the company, reducing turnover.

- **Increase in creativity** – openness and trust foster innovation; individuals are more inclined to share ideas.

- **Work performance** – team collaboration improves, enabling faster achievement of goals.

- **Positive corporate image** – an ecological culture becomes a competitive advantage in the labor market [7; 11].

Conclusion

The conducted theoretical analysis permits the following conclusions:

1. The ecology of interpersonal relationships constitutes an integral component of contemporary corporate culture. It constitutes a system of attitudes, skills, and practices aimed at creating a healthy, respectful, and safe environment for all employees.

2. The key factors in the formation of ecological interpersonal relationships are respect, equality, safety, and trust. Additional principles include balance of exchange, honesty, establishment of boundaries, and autonomy.

3. Modern employees (89% according to McKinsey) expect from employers not only financial reward but also psychological comfort. Companies that create an ecologically balanced environment gain competitive advantages: reduced turnover, increased engagement, and improved productivity.

4. Ecological human resource management requires a systemic approach encompassing activity-based, communicative, and situational levels, as well as adherence to the principles of democracy, openness, and humanism.

5. Further research should focus on the empirical investigation of the relationship between the level of ecological interpersonal relations and business performance indicators, as well as on the development of practical programs for the formation of an ecological corporate culture.

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PSYCHOLOGICAL CONTENT OF TRUST IN ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN CONTEMPORARY COGNITIVE PRACTICE

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Abstract. *The article examines trust in artificial intelligence as a psychological phenomenon of contemporary cognitive practice. It demonstrates that the use of intelligent systems within the educational environment alters the organization of students' cognitive activity and is linked to the distribution of cognitive responsibility between the human and the system. Delegative, instrumental, and reflexive forms of trust are distinguished. An empirical study investigating the relationship between digital competence and the characteristics of trust in artificial intelligence technologies among students at Russian universities is presented. A conclusion is drawn regarding the importance of digital competence as a condition for meaningful and responsible interaction with intelligent systems.*

Keywords: *artificial intelligence, trust, cognitive activity, digital competence, students, educational environment, subjectness, educational practice.*

Introduction

In recent years, the digital environment has significantly transformed educational practice. The contemporary student engages with traditional educational materials while simultaneously interacting with intelligent systems that participate in the search, processing, and formulation of knowledge. Artificial intelligence enters the educational space as an active participant in cognitive activity [2; 6; 11].

This alters the very method by which knowledge is acquired. Previously, the student independently and sequentially searched for information, compared sources, identified the key points, recorded the necessary provisions, and on their basis constructed an individual response. Increasingly, an alternative format of cognitive activity is emerging, wherein a student consults an intelligent system, receives a ready-made answer, refines the query, supplements it, and continues work in

dialogue mode. As a result, cognition acquires a dialogical and mediated form. At the same time, the speed of work increases, but simultaneously the internal organization of thinking is transformed [1; 8].

In this new context, trust in artificial intelligence acquires particular importance. A person utilizes the system when they consider its response sufficiently reliable, relevant, and useful. Trust becomes a psychological prerequisite for involving AI in the cognitive process. It facilitates accepting a response, relying on it, and integrating it into one's own work. At the same time, this is precisely where questions concerning the boundaries of control, authorship, and responsibility arise.

The relevance of the topic is linked to the fact that artificial intelligence has already become part of everyday and educational practice, while the psychological comprehension of trust in AI is still in the process of formation. Scientific interest is drawn to the manner in which a student establishes interaction with an intelligent system, the role assigned to it within their thinking, and the extent to which they preserve their own subjective standpoint.

The article aims to uncover the psychological aspects of trust in AI within modern cognitive practices and demonstrate its link to the learner's digital competence.

Theoretical foundations of the research

The issue of trust has a well-established tradition in philosophy and psychology. In the works of A. According to Seligman, trust is viewed as a special foundation for social interaction in situations of uncertainty [12]. In psychology, trust is understood as an attitude associated with the perception of the reliability, predictability, and significance of the interaction partner [5; 9; 13]. For a person, trust serves as a means of acting under conditions where complete verification is impossible or requires excessive effort.

In the context of interaction with artificial intelligence, this logic acquires a new meaning. The user interacts with a system that produces responses outwardly resembling the result of human thinking. In this regard, a significant reference point remains the idea of A. Turing, which demonstrates that the nature of the human reaction to the system's responses reveals its significance in the interaction process [15]. An individual begins to orient themselves towards the persuasiveness, relevance, and utility of the outcome. It is precisely at this point that trust in AI emerges.

Modern studies demonstrate that artificial intelligence is already actively incorporated into educational, professional, and everyday practices [2; 3; 6]. It facilitates text composition, idea generation, translation, data set analysis, response construction, and material formatting. All these aspects reinforce its role as a cognitive mediator. In essence, the student engages not only with information but also with a system that organizes access to it and presents it in a ready-to-use form.

From a cultural-historical perspective, this situation can be viewed as a new stage in the mediation of cognitive activity. In the framework of L. S. Vygotsky, mental functions develop through the use of tools and signs [8]. Today, an intelligent system acts as a unique digital tool that aids action and participates in constructing responses. This amplifies its psychological significance while simultaneously calling for renewed analysis.

Digital competence holds a distinct position within this topic. In the research conducted by G. U. Soldatova, E. I. Rasskazova, T. A. Digital competence is understood as a multifaceted construct comprising knowledge, skills, motivation, responsibility, and security [14]. An important fact is that it is associated with purposeful behavior in the digital environment. This implies that competence enables an individual to understand the system's capabilities, recognize its boundaries, verify outcomes, and maintain control.

Therefore, digital competence should be regarded as a psychological regulator of trust in artificial intelligence. With low engagement and limited understanding, the user more readily delegates the primary cognitive actions to the system. At a higher level of proficiency, the user employs it as a tool, while retaining the leading role.

Trust in artificial intelligence as a phenomenon of modern cognitive practice

In modern cognitive practice, trust in artificial intelligence no longer represents a private attitude toward a new technology, but rather an important mechanism for structuring thought. An individual addresses the system when they assume that its response can be incorporated into the solution of their own task. Hence, trust in this context is connected to the readiness to accept intellectual support and integrate it into one's activity.

The psychological content of this trust is disclosed through several interconnected aspects.

First, trust in AI is associated with the perception of the reliability of its response. The user assesses the extent to which the system appears competent, accurate, and useful. Even without a deep understanding of the algorithm, it relies on the external result: logical consistency, speed, coherence, and a confident style of presentation [4; 10].

Secondly, trust is connected with the redistribution of cognitive load. When a student consults AI, they delegate part of the operations to the system: searching, initial processing, structuring, and formulation. At this point, trust becomes a means of sharing responsibility between the human and the algorithm.

Thirdly, trust is associated with the preservation or attenuation of authorship in thinking. If a person perceives the system's response as ready-made knowledge, they readily resort to copying and develop cognitive dependence. Conversely, if they employ the response as material for analysis, comparison, and refinement, the interaction assumes a more sophisticated nature.

On this basis, three psychological forms of trust in artificial intelligence can be identified.

Delegated trust arises when a student regards the system as a more authoritative source for solutions. In this case, AI effectively assumes a significant portion of the cognitive workload. For the user, the speed, simplicity, and apparent credibility of the response are paramount. This form of trust often leads to copying, superficial assimilation, and decreased intrinsic engagement with the task.

Instrumental trust corresponds to a more active stance. The student employs AI for convenience, time-saving, and enhancing efficiency. He selects specific system functions, compares options, and refines the content. Here AI functions as a working tool, rather than as a replacing agent.

Reflexive trust constitutes the most mature form. In this case, the individual retains authorship, comprehends the conditional and limited nature of the response, verifies the outcome, and relates it to the task context and their own objectives. Artificial intelligence participates in cognitive activity as a partner in information processing, while the decision-making center remains with the individual.

Thus, trust in artificial intelligence has a non-uniform structure. It reflects the nature of the interaction between humans and technology and the distribution of cognitive responsibility.

Digital competence as a condition for mature interaction with AI

The relationship between digital competence and trust in AI is of particular importance for educational practice. It is important to identify a simple yet crucial point here. Competence does not automatically lead to either an increase or a decrease in trust. It changes the very form of trust.

The better a student understands the digital environment, the more accurately they allocate functions between themselves and the system. He is capable of formulating a query, evaluating the response, identifying its strengths and limitations, detecting errors, and selecting the appropriate format for use. Competence is also linked to responsibility and safety [14]. A student who possesses digital competencies more frequently considers the reliability, accuracy, ethical aspects of use, and the consequences of uncritical application of AI. Consequently, trust becomes more deliberate and stable.

In the contemporary educational environment, the risks associated with interaction with artificial intelligence – specifically those related to the attenuation of the student's independent involvement in comprehending the learning material – acquire particular significance. At the same time, an advanced level of digital competence enables the use of artificial intelligence as a resource for expanding cognitive capabilities, exploring solution options, optimizing routine stages of work, and enhancing analytical processes.

In this context, the objective of education is to cultivate in students a purposeful manner of interacting with intelligent systems.

Description of the empirical study

Within this framework, we are conducting a study devoted to the relationship between digital competence and the features of trust in artificial intelligence technologies among students in Russian higher education institutions.

The empirical foundation of the study consisted of 200 students from Russian universities.

The goal of the study is to identify the relationship between the level of digital competence and the form of trust in artificial intelligence in students' educational activity.

The object of the study is digital competence and trust in artificial intelligence technologies among students.

The subject of the study is the psychological features of trust in artificial intelligence in the contemporary cognitive practice of students.

The structure of the study comprised several sequential stages. First, the peculiarities of AI usage in the educational practices of students were analyzed. Next, their level of digital competence was examined. Then, the characteristics of trust in intelligent systems were considered as an indicator of the nature of AI integration into the cognitive activity of learners.

The practical value of this research lies in the fact that its results can be applied in the development of educational programs, assignments, and forms of student support in the context of active AI integration.

Conclusion

The proliferation of intellectual systems in education marks a new phase in the comprehension of human cognitive activity. Foremost is the question of how thinking will evolve in the context of the constant presence of an algorithmic mediator, and which psychological conditions sustain its autonomy, depth, and internal coherence. In this context, the study of trust in artificial intelligence assumes the significance of a broader scientific problem associated with understanding the role of humans in the new cognitive reality.

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THE PHENOMENON OF ANXIETY IN PSYCHOLOGICAL RESEARCH

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Abstract. *Personal anxiety is currently one of the most widespread psychological issues in client requests for psychological assistance. The article reviews studies on anxiety and the understanding of its nature by domestic and international psychologists in the context of the usefulness of these findings for the development of psychological counseling techniques and person-oriented psychotherapy.*

Keywords: *anxiety, personal anxiety, anxiety, anxiety disorders, fear, emotion, experience.*

In recent times, amid conditions of uncertainty and persistent stress, interest in the phenomenon of anxiety has significantly increased. Researchers engage deeply with the studies of this phenomenon to comprehend its nature and identify its causes, thereby laying the groundwork for the development of psychological intervention strategies aimed at the numerous clients consulting psychologists and psychotherapists regarding this issue.

It is pertinent to first differentiate the concepts within the categorical framework of this problem. Anxiety is generally defined as an individual psychological characteristic manifested in a person's propensity to frequently experience intense anxiety over relatively insignificant causes. Anxiety is viewed either as a personality trait, as a feature of higher nervous activity linked to the weakness of nervous processes, or as both simultaneously. [4]. A person experiencing anxiety undergoes emotional discomfort related to the anticipation and expectation of unpleasant events, dangers, and associated experiences that have already taken hold of them. Even when everything around is good and prosperous, a person experiences background anxiety characterized by a sense of impending dangers or forthcoming troubles.

The term «anxiety», which is often used synonymously with the concept of «Anxiety», is not identical to it. Anxiety is a negatively valenced emotion expressing a sense of uncertainty, anticipation of negative events, and vague premonitions. However, as an emotional state, it is more transient than the

condition of Anxiety, which can manifest as a stable trait in responses to the surrounding reality. Anxiety is commonly understood as ‘an emotional state arising in situations of uncertain danger and manifested in the expectation of an adverse development of events’ [9, p. 86]. Anxiety is also defined as ‘the experience of emotional discomfort associated with the anticipation of misfortune, a premonition of impending danger’ [4].

Anxiety is further distinguished from fear: it is perceived as a vague, diffuse experience – a premonition of something unfavorable – possibly triggered by being in uncertain, uncomfortable, or adverse conditions. Fear, however, is an objectified form of anxiety (there is a specific object that causes fear); namely, fear is an emotion based on a real danger.

A. S. Spivakovskaya states: ‘... anxiety is a premonition of danger, a state of unease.’ Anxiety most frequently manifests in the anticipation of an event that is difficult to predict and may pose a threat of adverse consequences. Unlike fear, anxiety is the experience of a remote and indistinct danger. It is precisely the uncertainty not so much about the source of anxiety itself, but about how this experience can be avoided or how to eliminate the cause that provokes it, that characterizes the feeling of anxiety” [12, p. 54].

In clinical psychology and non-medical psychotherapy, the term ‘anxiety disorders’ is also widely used. Anxiety disorders are a group of neurotic disorders characterized by a range of diverse psychological manifestations. Anxiety disorders are among the most common psychological disorders. According to ICD-10, these include anxiety-phobic disorders, panic disorder, generalized anxiety disorder, mixed anxiety-depressive disorder, obsessive-compulsive disorder, and post-traumatic stress disorder. In this case, these are systemic disturbances of the subject’s psyche, requiring prolonged psychotherapy and often pharmacological intervention.

Let us return to the examination of anxiety as a psychological phenomenon.

Historical developments in the issue of anxiety trace back to the works of S. Freud. The term “Angst,” translated from German as “fear,” is identified by several researchers and translators as denoting “anxiety.” In the works of S. Freud, “Angst” is described as the anticipation of danger in the absence of obvious causes. Freud’s research distinguishes three types of anxiety:

- 1). Real. This type of anxiety is caused by objective circumstances and real danger.
- 2). Neurotic. Anxiety is caused by neurosis. Furthermore, it can be triggered by specific neurotic personality traits.
- 3). Moral. Anxiety emerges under the influence of the ‘Superego’ when an individual’s actions contradict the moral norms prevailing in society [14].

K. Horney, a representative of the psychoanalytic school, did not regard anxiety as a necessary and obligatory element of an individual’s mental life. She posited that the occurrence of Anxiety is related to difficulties in interpersonal relationships

and the lack of a sense of security therein. Her framework distinguishes two types of Anxiety. These are:

– Physiological Anxiety. This type is related to a child's drive to satisfy physiological needs. In the absence of fulfillment of physiological needs, a child may experience Anxiety. If physiological needs remain unmet for a considerable period, Anxiety intensifies and becomes a contributing factor to neuroticism.

– 'Basal' Anxiety. This type of anxiety represents a 'feeling of one's own insignificance, helplessness, abandonment, vulnerability to danger, and existence in a world open to offenses, deceit, attacks, insults, betrayal, and envy' [17].

According to the psychoanalytic concept, anxiety is an innate characteristic of the individual, the purpose of which is to generate an adequate response in situations of danger. An irresolvable conflict between natural impulses and social prohibitions creates 'pathological' anxiety.

A. Adler, the founder of the individual psychology theory, links anxiety with symptoms of neurosis characteristic of individuals who have chosen an unsuitable lifestyle. This results from destructive relationships with parents during early childhood. A state of insecurity and unwarranted anxiety often persists in such individuals into adulthood. (Cited from: [11, p.42])

E. Fromm has outlined his conceptualizations of anxiety. In particular, he notes: "Anxiety is often the result of a disruption in the balance between individual needs and external circumstances" [15]. Moreover, E. Fromm emphasizes that the role of anxiety is not entirely unequivocal – it is far from always negative. In certain cases, anxiety may signify the need for life changes and assist an individual in development and personal growth. According to E. Fromm's concept, a person experiences their own individuality and, concurrently, a feeling of alienation from the forces of nature and society, as well as helplessness in relation to them. It is precisely this feeling that constitutes the source of anxiety [15].

C. Rogers, a representative of the humanistic direction in psychology, viewed anxiety as an unconscious experience of a state of tension in the individual. According to Rogers' perspective, an experience that threatens the individual's self-concept is repressed into the unconscious. Within conscious awareness, anxiety manifests as a discrepancy between the 'self-concept' and the repressed experience. Anxiety can thus be characterized as a propensity to distort reality, emerging in order to preserve familiar self-representations (to maintain the 'self-concept').

A. Maslow, one of the pioneers of humanistic psychology, associated anxiety with the hierarchy of needs. He considered unmet needs to be the source of anxiety. Accordingly, a person experiencing difficulties in satisfying needs such as esteem, love, security, and friendship will experience feelings of worry and anxiety [5].

Gestalt psychology specialists distinguish two factors contributing to the onset of anxiety: first, it arises from unfinished life situations (gestalts); second, from

a disruption of contact between the individual and the external world as well as with oneself. Perls, the founder of gestalt therapy, observes: ‘...the formula of anxiety is very simple: anxiety is the gap between now and then’ [7]. Thus, anxiety is understood as a disruption of contact between the individual and the present moment – the person is preoccupied with anxieties about the future or traumatic memories of the past; the events of the present essentially elude the individual, while anxious thoughts may pertain both to the past and the future, thereby occupying the present. Gestalt psychologists likewise interpret the phenomenon of anxiety as resulting from the repression and blocking of unrealized desires and emotions.

Within cognitive psychology, the most prominent is the concept proposed by A. Beck, the founder of cognitive-behavioral therapy, which is devoted to the study of anxiety. It is important to emphasize that cognitive-behavioral therapy remains the most effective approach for addressing anxiety within the realm of psychological support to date. This concept views anxiety as a combination of the following factors:

1). Worry about negative events that may occur in the future. The individual is consistently focused on a negative scenario of the future, thereby continuously activating the anxiety mechanism.

2). Issues with self-esteem, self-doubt, and perfectionism. The individual is preoccupied with achieving high standards in their activities, social status, and so forth. Failing to reach the desired high outcome, they experience stress and feelings of personal inadequacy.

3). Fear of losing close loved ones.

4). A conviction of one’s own inability to establish effective communication with others. The individual experiences fear associated with possible rejection and non-acceptance, as well as anxiety about failing to meet others’ expectations.

Prolonged exposure to these factors results in the formation of an anxiously suspicious personality.

Within the framework of cognitive psychology, anxiety is conceptualized as a consequence of cognitive dissonance, wherein irresolvable contradictions arise between an individual’s beliefs and desires on the one hand, and the demands of reality on the other. Anxiety is a consequence of uncontrolled and irrational negative thoughts concerning the future [1].

Cognitive psychologists identify cognitive distortions as causes of the onset and development of anxiety. These include:

– Catastrophizing. In this distortion, an individual envisions the most negative scenario of future events. The importance of events, as well as their intensity, is overestimated [3].

– Black-and-white thinking. A future or present event is perceived by an individual in extremes – absolute success or absolute failure. In this context, any failure may be perceived as a total defeat, provoking worry and anxiety.

– “Overgeneralization.” On the basis of a single failure, an individual infers that failures will invariably follow them in similar situations.

– Selective attention to negativity. An individual focuses exclusively on the negative aspects of both current and anticipated events, disregarding the positive [2]. Various authors supplement this list with additional cognitive distortions found in the consciousness of an anxious individual.

The study of anxiety is the focus of works by domestic psychologists – V. M. As-tapov, L. V. Borozdina, V. N. Druzhinin, E. P. Ilyin, N. D. Levitov, A. M. Prikhojan, K. R. Sidorov, V. N. Solovyev, Yu. I. Khanin, and many others; among foreign authors – K. Jaspers, Barlow, Clark, D. Gray, Kandel, N. Cohen, C. D. Spielberger, Tellegen, Watson, and others.

The well-known domestic researcher of anxiety, A. M. Prikhojan, considers anxiety to be ‘...a stable personality formation that persists over a sufficiently long period of time...’ The experience of emotional discomfort and the anticipation of a looming threat are expressions of the dissatisfaction of significant human needs” [8, p. 11]. She notes that anxiety, unlike fear, is a stable personality trait.

Yu. I. Khanin considers anxiety as ‘an individual psychological characteristic of the personality, manifested in its predisposition to respond with anxiety in a range of life situations, the majority of which do not justify such a reaction’ [16].

Thus, anxiety in contemporary research is considered a personal characteristic manifested by a predisposition to experience anxiety, emotional discomfort, and apprehension toward forthcoming events.

Neurobiological theories concerning the origin of anxiety are also currently well established. According to the works of A. M. Veyn, V. V. Endolov, E. A. Korablevnikova, A. N. Nekhoroshkova, E. A. Nefedova, and V. V. Sychev, anxiety arises as a consequence of biological processes within the organism, including genetic predisposition and particularities of the hormonal profile [6].

Several authors note that although anxiety is classified as a negative emotion, it is quite natural and, in certain cases, necessary – in extreme situations, it facilitates individual mobilization and concentration on the danger.

C. Spielberger, a prominent American psychologist, distinguished between two types of anxiety – situational and personal anxiety. Situational anxiety arises as a result of an individual’s encounter with an objective danger; it is short-term and occurs naturally. Personal anxiety is conditioned by the individual’s personal characteristics – a safe situation may be perceived as threatening. C. Spielberger notes that in some cases, the state of anxiety is normal and even beneficial, as it allows for an objective evaluation of a dangerous situation [13].

The complex nature of the phenomenon of anxiety underscores the necessity of investigating its various aspects, with particular emphasis on approaches that

support the development of strategies for psychological counseling and psychotherapy. The provision of psychological support in adulthood particularly requires additional research of both theoretical and practical, applied nature. This topic will be discussed in our subsequent publications.

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